

University of the West of Scotland

The key determinants of service quality strategies that improve the brand image of hotels in the UK

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Abstract

This research is carried out to determine how specific service quality strategies are superior to others. These service quality strategies improve brand image in a better way. This research has also focused on identifying a metric that can help measure the effectiveness of different service quality strategies in enhancing the brand images of hotels in the UK. The research revolves around the concepts of service quality and the elements that are a part of a successful service quality strategy. Evaluation of the hotel industry's issues in terms of service quality and analysis of the existing service quality strategy is also carried out in this research. Service quality is a highly subjective category within the hospitality industry; it plays a significant role in customer satisfaction. Therefore, it is essential to have measures in place that can be used to quantify service quality. There hasn't been any considerable agreement on the primary keys of the service quality construct; much insight was obtained through analysing different service quality models. Even though understating service quality is, it is also of utmost importance to measure it. Many models and measurement tools have been studied, and it has been noted that various models use the SERVQUAL dimensions to measure service quality. The SERVPERV is one of the models that leans heavily on the SERVQUAL dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, tangibility, empathy, and assurance. However, this instrument only measures the perception of service quality, and the customer perceptions are built into the customer's perceptions on service quality. Therefore, it isn't necessary to measure it on its own. This research has been carried out primarily as primary research. Literature Review was carried out to provide theoretical underpinning. A sample size of 300 people filled out an online questionnaire. Most of the data analysis was based on a simple statistical presentation. SERVQUAL can be considered the viable metric tool to measure the effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK. This research has successfully achieved its objectives: to determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in enhancing brand image; and to identify a metric to measure the degree of effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK.

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Declaration

This thesis contains no work that has been submitted to this or any other university or institute of learning in support of a degree or qualification application. I declare that this research is mine and original, and any additional resources that are not mine are identified and referenced.

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1. Chapter 1: Introduction

The hospitality industry is solely based on services, including lodging, food, recreational activities, events, leisure, and drinks. It is not about how many services are offered but the kind of experience provided to the customer (Dube et al., 2021). It is about the respect from the host to the guest and the guest to the host, more so from the host to the guest. Whether it was Harappan culture or tribal age, guests were treated with the utmost regard from ancient times. In modern times, the definitions may have changed from guests, not God, yet guests are treated and provided the respect and best services possible (Ntounis et al., 2021). Based on this policy, the hospitality industry treats guests as your God. For the longest time, it has been seen across the globe, especially in the United Kingdom, that the hospitality industry is one industry to be experimenting with the most. Their livelihood depends on it (Floritic, 2020). Repeat customers are the lifelines of the hospitality industry, and engagement with the new customers is the progress and advancement on which the future of the hospitality industry depends (Kotera et al., 2020).

With so many things to take care of from lodging to accommodation, from drinks to food, from recreational activities to evening events and leisure, it becomes difficult to fathom which one is more important, which experience will crack the customer never to let them leave the hotel (Tan et al., 2017). All the hotels and chains under the hospitality industry have struggled to figure out and, therefore, experimented to provide as much as they can, as quickly as they can, as best as they can. As a result, they stretched themselves to the extent of getting into the drain of nothingness (Hole et al., 2018). The human resource seems to be overwhelmed; the funds are burned out, ever expansion ambition of making it big and being around the customer where they go has resulted in thinning the services, which in turn hampers the brand image, eventually ruining the whole vision and goal of starting a business in hospitality (Namin, 2017). For the industry heavily based upon the services, it becomes mandatory to scrutinise the service quality daily and weekly, as the brand image falls back upon the best service quality offered by the hotel and the staff to the customer (Tan et al., 2017).

Price Perception is a significant determinant in selecting the hotel. Advertising act as a medium through which perception of the hotel is firmed; therefore, a pre-decided expectation

is followed. Customer and staff contact, for a customer to rate a hotel or their experience, the cue that plays an intrinsic role is the interaction with the staff (Oh and Kim, 2017). The tangible scope includes the building, fixtures, decor, interiors, etc. They play a significant role. Intangible contents include colour, theme, music, fragrance, and temperature. This is a deciding factor included in the post-experience and loyalty (Floridic, 2020). Core Services, including food and beverages, accommodation comfort, leisure activities, and recreational activities, this amount to a delightful experience. Pre-consumption mood, the mood of a customer before consuming these services. Experience, their experience with the hotel, if any (Dube et al., 2021). Brand image and its measurement are how the brand is perceived by the customer and therefore, after experiencing the services of the brand how loyal and trusting and reliable the brand comes out in the customers perceived expectation and final delivery, basis which whether they will stick to the brand or switch over is what makes for the brand image (Namin, 2017). These determinants will be discussed in the latter part of the research and how it matters and affects the overall service quality strategy, which involves the brand image.

Whether the hotel is catering to business to customer or business to business class, each individual who passes through the doors of the hotel expects and relaxing time, with no disturbances, a sumptuous meal, a good night rest, a spa that is as luxurious as being in nature, basically a home away from (Ntounis et al., 2021). With such expectations, the hotels will have to fall back upon a strategy to ensure whether they can get all the ticks in the tick book checked by the customer. The hotel across the globe, and especially in the United Kingdom, which depends on the hospitality revenue big time, as to determine the critical factors of service quality and design their service quality strategy accordingly to improve the image of the brand, to sustain the brand's image (Oh and Kim, 2017).

1.1 Background

The hospitality industry generates 4% of the United Kingdom's GDP. This makes it the fourth-most sought-after employment sector in the United Kingdom. The UK's hospitality more or less covers hotels, restaurants, pubs, leisure zones, etc. (Jones and Comfort, 2020).

The United Kingdom was the frontrunner in the service industry for the past two to three centuries ago. The country is synonymous with everything Royal. Royalty exudes in the blood veins of the hospitality industry in the UK (Dube et al., 2021). Whether it was the time of monarchy or democracy, the Royalty inbred and ingrained never came out of the country's hospitality (Kotera et al., 2020). Elizabeth Era and the Shakespeare era have such intricate designs and décor most sought after. The royalty has inspired the cutleries used in the servicing. Even today, the part of the UK runs and breathes royalty's grace. Even though the population has readily adopted the casual, funk style through the US, the grace and elegance of royalty has been and is the heart of the hospitality industry. It has attracted considerable tourism and spent on hospitality from within and outside of it, from the various other continents, including Asia, Australia, and The United States. This tourism has helped the hospitality industry grow leaps and bounds to become the 4th largest employed of the United Kingdom's economy (Florivic, 2020).

The hospitality industry of the United Kingdom doesn't confine itself the elegance and grace but has been experimenting through and through yet keeping it the royalty as the lifeline. It has many hotels and experiential centres ranging from 7-star luxury hotels to major brands of 5 stars. It has service accommodations to the guesthouses and the motels. The hospitality industry provides various options as per the budget, satiating the need for upper, middle, and lower scales (Ntounis et al., 2021). London is the hub of the luxury and upper segment hotels, as it is at the confluence of The United Kingdom's economic growth and advancement, Royalty, monarchy, modernism, futuristic visions, past lineage. Therefore, London attracts the creamiest crowd in their posh and luxury hotels. The budget travellers and the country's citizens prefer budget accommodations varying from peer-to-peer platforms like AirB&B to guest houses motels. The peer to peer platforms like AirB&B, Hostels, and Zostles are considered the disruptors in the industry. Still, their performance is directly proportional to the investments and the increased opportunities in the services segments.

The annual occupancy rate in 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018 & 2019. In 2015 the occupancy rate was 78.5%; in 2016, it increased to 78.8%. It dipped to 77.3% in 2017 and then was pulled up by 2018 at 78.3% and the highest in 2019 at 79.9% (Tan and Despotis, 2021).

Figure 1.1 Annual Occupancy of Hotels in London (Source: Statista.com)

Figure 1.1 shows the hotels occupancy in London from 2008 till 2019.

The occupancy of London compared to across the United Kingdom, especially from the years 2015, has been higher. Between 2008 and 2014, the occupancy rate showed an increasing trend from 80% to 83%. It dropped in the year 2015 to 82% and was constant at that till 2017. In 2018 it rapidly increased by 2%, making it to 84%, and then a slight drop in 2019 at 83.4% (Statista.com, 2021). The most significant investment in the United Kingdom hospitality industry- hotel market in 2019 happened for 40star hotels. It is clear from the graph that around 40% of the total volume of transactions and 44% of the room were occupied in 2019 by 4-start property (Vlachos, 2020).

The hotel market in the hospitality industry in terms of investment and volumes has been zestful till 2019. London markets performed better than the rest, considering the crowd London pulls with its history, royalty palace, and economic growth and advancements. In 2018 the average rate of a room everywhere except London was 85 GBP, whereas it touched 150 GBP for London (Vlachos, 2020). The occupancy rate in 2018 of the rest of the UK

except London was 78.3%, whereas, for London, it was a whopping 84%. The revenue per room for the same year for the rest of the UK except London was GBP 67, whereas for London it was GBP 125. By this data comparison, London is the most significant contributor to the hospitality industry of the UK, specifically the Hotel market of the United Kingdom (Wood, 2020).

The trends in the UK hospitality industry shows that after accommodation, food and beverage is the second largest revenue collector. Thus making the accommodation experience the most critical determinant in the service quality strategy followed by food and beverage (Legrand et al., 2020). Seeing such variant, dynamic and positive trends, the growth of the hospitality industry in the United Kingdom was expected to be at a CAGR of around 3% over the next five years from 2018, which was put to a halt because of COVID and Brexit (Jones and Comfort, 2020). The industry in the UK has always trusted their tangibles and the reliability factor in gaining momentum and growth. It is crucial to create a superior customer experience to grow and prosper.

A great customer experience goes a long way in brand awareness; brand image sustenance ensures customer loyalty while increasing the profits and growth of the hotel's market. For ages strategy team of the hotel and hospitality industry has worked on providing the best customer service yet; it has been seen how the customer still hop on to and or switch to different brands (Wood, 2020). As much as customer experience is crucial, a satisfaction scale cannot be weighed. It should be immersed in the service platform so that merely satisfying the customer should not be the aim. It should reach towards the customer delight for them to stick to the brand and for the brands to have a strong image. Such experience will promote the brand image and long-term brand loyalty (Namin, 2017).

Over the past years, many researchers and academics have argued that a well-put strategy for success in the marketplace is the certainty and stamp of customer satisfaction, loyalty, and a strong brand. However, a few argued that customer satisfaction is less with the brand, but more of the delight and pleasure lived during the immersion with the service platform. This shows a gap between the question and the response on what is responsible for the strong brand image (Taherdoost and Hassan, 2020).

Customer loyalty is generated by the smiling staff, lovely décor, interiors, and building or a customer experience through accommodation, food, and recreational activities. It has been

asserted that customer experience affects the brand image. Service quality is crucial for an industry like hospitality, and service quality has come a long way in terms of evolution through a plumage of test, hit and trial (Tan and Despotis, 2021). A phenomenal change has been experienced in the hotel industry during this last decade. The quality of service the value of service are difficult to measure. Therefore, the hospitality industry relies on perception and expectation. Service quality strategy for any hotel or hospitality sector is crucial today when competition is brimming to the tip (Dube et al., 2021). Many resources are available, yet hardly any describe it from the customer's point of view. Customers often blame their bad choices when unsatisfied with the services.

Few may complain, few may not complain. However, the staff needs to figure out the issue or the root cause and resolve it. The quality of service is a differentiating factor for the hotel and hospitality establishment (Kasiri et al., 2017). The five components of perceived service quality are Assurance, Tangibles, Responsiveness, Empathy, and Reliability. These five dimensions of SERVQUAL were further divided into twenty-two components specific to the hotel industry.

1. Tangibles: visible and modern equipment's possessed by the brand, staff grooming and appearance, visually appealing décor, interiors, music, temperature, colour, fixtures, room, etc.
2. Responsiveness: Quick serving, information to the customer on delivery time and adhering by it.
3. Reliability: Reliability in customer issues and problem-solving, reliability on assured and mentioned services, providing promised services, zero-defect policy adherence, willingness, and prompt response to customers request
4. Empathy: Individual attention to the customer.
5. Assurance: Thrusting confidence, courtesy, quick response in terms of the customer's queries (Murfield et al., 2017).

That is how the scale of the SERVQUAL (Service Quality) Model was developed.

1.2 Rationale

The dynamic hotel market of the UK, which is represented in Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, has been badly hit by the two may factors, Brexit and COVID-19. The investment, which was soring

high till about 2018, took a significant hit with the Brexit talks since 2019 (Dube et al., 2021). The industry which in 2019 was responsible for approximately GBP 60 billion in Gross Added Value to the United Kingdom economy, which turns out to be around three per cent of the total economic output of the United Kingdom, drastically reduced. The turnover was down by GBP 80 billion, equal to GBP 200m a day. The data shows that the trading dropped to 54% in the UK hospitality sector. From GBP 134 billion in 2019, the sales came down to GBP 60 billion, and deals between September till December 2020 were down by 60% of the total at GBP 14 billion (Kotera et al., 2020).

Such stark numbers mean that the hospitality industry in the United Kingdom is in dire need of government support. The hit, which Brexit instigated, got even harder by Pandemic hitting the grounds. And it does not seem to be ending as the restrictions are still in place, and the virus is still not been eradicated. An Exit strategy to support the business is crucial as otherwise, it may take decades to bring normalcy in the hospitality sector, especially the hotel market (Li et al., 2021). With Britain being the part of Europe eased a lot of movement and tourism within the countries of Europe and members of the European Union. Since Brexit has taken place, the rules and regulations have changed, which means more tussle and processes in the movement of citizens of European countries to the UK, further deepening the gap in the already falling industry (Dube et al., 2021).

The hotel market for London has been booming since 2008 and has kept a constant speed of 82% to 84% of occupancy across the hotels of London till 2019. However, there is a steep fall in 2020 due to COVID to 28.4%. The year 2021 has a positive pull to 52% of occupancy, yet the occupancy rates are down by 30%, in London alone, which is the hub of transaction and tourism of the United Kingdom. As per the PwC report, the hotel market in the United Kingdom, which took a steep fall from approximately 80% to 30%, make take four to five years to come back to pre-Covid glory (Kim et al., 2021).

In the windswept outlook, hotel occupancy in 2021 is forecasted at 50% across the United Kingdom. This means that it could take another five to six years to return to the year's ad season of normalcy, a pre-Covid era. The industry that was once growing in leaps and bounds with optimistic future growth and a decade of advancements in terms of growth from 2007 till 2019 and massive investment strategy has come to a significant halt and has been dragged seven years behind (Wood, 2020). The further if the industry seems bleak. The good news is

that 2021 is more optimistic than 2020 as the vaccines have arrived and citizens have been vaccinated at fast growth. However, the business may have bettered from nothingness to 10 to 20%, yet it is far from the usual company.

The hotel occupancy of the United Kingdom is at the lowest it is yet to be seen how the year 2021 fares in terms of new variant mutation (Dube et al., 2021). If everything is at speed, 2022 will respite the hospitality industry. But for now, nothing can be forecasted. The UK hospitality lost nearly 500,000 jobs supported otherwise by the government's furlough program. The hospitality industry is heaped on with taxes of 93 million (Kim et al., 2021). The industry is facing a vast labour shortage with the Brexit taking place, as many labourers and workers from the European countries left the UK to go back to their home countries during the pandemic and may not return due to work visa rules post-Brexit when things get normal after the Pandemic (Priporas et al., 2017).

Currently, the hospitality industry owes around GBP 3.6 billion to their landlords. This may take forever to fulfil and may be referred to as a long COVID economy post the normalcy. As the world bears the brunt of COVID, the hospitably across the continents and countries struggle to survive, the hospitality and hotel market if the United Kingdom has been hit by the double whammy of COVID-19 and BREXIT (Ali et al., 2021). A two-way sword, which may not allow the sector to come back to normalcy even after the COVID, is long gone. As the industry may try to overcome the COVID slowdown, it will be blown with the labour shortage, migrants and students going back to their countries, may not come back as the education happens online, and the work visa rule for the labourers from European countries hardens (Wood, 2020). Keeping all this in mind, it becomes mandatory to understand the hospitality market through this study and figure out the critical determinants in the service quality of such industry for the hotels to improvise on their strategy and attract footfalls (Dube et al., 2021).

Through various research across the globe and discussion between researchers and scholars, a factor which has been left out to explore much is the management-employee variance under the service quality. Shen and Tang did a study (2018) that analysed employee perception of the management service quality principle with personality and motivation. There has been a gap between the customer expectation and perception or customer expectation and management perception. This gap deepens the discrepancies. The five holes responsible are:

1. Gap between the customer perception and expectation
2. Gap between management perceptions of customers expectation
3. Gap between the service quality specifications and actual deliverables.
4. Gap between service quality and the promising company makes to the customer through advertising and external communication
5. Gap in the customer's perception of a few services and the expectation regarding the services.

These five gaps influence the total perception of the service quality—customer satisfaction, affecting the brand image. Further, few types of research done in the past point out the frailty in the present organisational structure and instead focus on the service quality being the driver of the organisation in hospitality. Dadwal (2017) made it an immersion-suggesting hotel to develop a service quality strategy for competitive advantage.

Accommodation is perceived to be the basics of the hospitality industry. Further, it determines the cities and countries' ability to attract more tourism, as, without the basic infrastructure, there is no point in promoting tourism. Therefore, the management of the hotel and hospitality industry in terms of service quality which in turn is responsible for the brand image, is crucial not only for the hospitality industry but also for the tourism industry, as they go hand in hand (Makanyeza & Chikazhe, 2017).

It is interesting to know that customers have well-defined service quality and specific attributes are more crucial than the other may they be the smallest or biggest. Like hygiene factors, how clean and disinfected is the who premises, the fragrance or the scents across, the availability of sanitisers may seem like a small thing in the 'to do list'; however, can be the factors which makes or breaks the brand image and lead the customer to rate the service quality as poor even though they had other good experiences in the hotel (Jones and Comfort, 2020). The presence may not mean improving the perceived quality of services; their absence may mean the ratings go downhill, but it is not the fact, vice versa. The service staff's skill and performance are critical determinants of service quality for many customers. For a service quality to become the satisfaction process incorporating the value-based ideal standards and experienced outcome through negative disconfirmation of determining satisfaction leaving the negative cognitive bias aside (Kim et al., 2021). SERVQUAL index

was used to evaluate the service quality of the hospitals, which focused on the expectations vs perception of the customer comparison. It was found that two extreme service quality results resulted from the customer's expectation of service quality rather than perception. This asserted that customer expectation impacts the brand's evaluation of service quality (Wang and Tseng, 2019).

With so many definitions of quality and many other possible interpretations in the service sector, quality is the topmost factor contributing to luring and retaining customers. The service quality model based on operational issues like staff training skills explains that matching customer expectations with staff skills increases job satisfaction. If service quality becomes the foundation of the marketing strategy, it will be easier to measure the performance, making SERVQUAL a crucial instrument. Eventually, service quality evaluation has become essential for researchers and hotel managers (Lee and Severt, 2017). The framework of the central quality service points out that the consumers not only consider their expectations but also consider the service provider's performance while evaluating the service quality. Another research was focused on the integration of marketing and operations for improvement in the quality of services setting while also discussing the improvements, responsibilities, and measurements of service quality. The advocacy of amalgamating the service quality improvement tool (QFD) and service quality evaluation (SERVQUAL) and therefore further suggesting the integration of system tools, concepts which an organisation can aim to achieve the best service quality (Haming et al., 2019).

Total quality management (TQM) helps in improving while reducing the cost. They have also strongly suggested that SERVQUAL be used to benchmark performance, which will help in improving the service quality. Brand image and its measurement are how the brand is perceived by the customer and therefore, after experiencing the services of the brand how loyal and trusting and reliable the brand comes out in the customers perceived expectation and final delivery, basis which whether they will stick to the brand or switch over is what makes for the brand image (Shafiq et al., 2019).

With ever-increasing competition in the hotel industry, hotels prioritise service quality more than ever to sustain in such a competitive world. To include that, hotels have figured out a competitive gap analysis through an analytical process. Such methods will help the hotel managers design viable service quality strategies to wade through the cutthroat competition

(Naumov, 2019). After analysing eight hundred incidents across service industries, a research conclusion points out that any positive incidents are majorly driven by the responsiveness, understanding of the customer, and communication with the customer. The absence of significant factors like assurance, reliability, responsiveness, competence, credibility contributes to the unsatisfied customer driving the adverse incidents (Naumov, 2019).

The two major dimensions that came out of the research were service staff vs service system and customer initiative vs staff initiative. The service system is attached to adverse incidents and service staff to positive incidents. Upon testing through various hospitality structures, it has been demonstrated that SERVQUAL as an assessment and evaluation tool consists of matching and managing customer expectation viz. a viz. the design of the service or product (Dube et al., 2021).

The service sector is hell-bent on providing the best service quality through various hit & trial methods and management techniques. It is given and known that brand image is directly linked to service quality, and therefore, the profits of the business are directly associated with the service quality (Kim et al., 2021). As in such sectors, the customer has a crucial role and directly impacts the service provider and the entire network of industry. This brings out the assessment of relation in the marketing of relationships. There is no difference when it comes to the manufacturing and service industries. Service has become an integral part of the products, making all businesses service-oriented focused on satisfying the customer's need (Wood, 2020).

It has inspired and motivated companies to add advanced technologies and decrease the orders for cheap materials imports. Each organisation bet in hotels in the hospitality or any other business is striving to gain the competitive advantage by providing superior value experience through excellent customer service, adding to the not so expensive rates low delivery cost (Shen and Tang, 2018). Customer service remains the crucial and top priority factor in acquiring the customer, retaining the customer, increasing the service quality, strengthening the brand image in such a competitive market. The four gaps were further assessed to determine the perception of service quality through the hotel managers in the hotel market. That study showed that the hotel industry's tourist perception of service quality was consistently lower than their expectations. However, the hotel manager overestimated their service delivery (Naumov, 2019). Therefore, concluding that Delivery Gap and

evaluation Gap are the significant contributors of service quality shortfall in the hospitality industry of the United Kingdom.

The service Quality in hospitality and tourism has been studied extensively still the debate is not yet resolved as to which measure. Therefore the tool has the most excellent validity and precision. The two main instruments, IPA- Importance Performance Analysis and SERVQUA, L, were out under the radar. The researchers agreed that SERVQUAL and SERVPERF (service Performance) is excellent tools for precise assessment. Taherdoost and Hassan (2020) assessed the four main methods of measuring customer service quality by analysing the data obtained through UK tour operators and the hospitality industry. It was shown that the four methods vary in ranking, yet the difference was not proved statistically. All the companies should broaden their productivity test from the typical company perspective to a newer customer perspective. This approach will help reconcile conflicts, and integratetween improved service quality and service productivity, further strengthening the brand's image (Oh and Kim, 2017). When a study was done on two different hospitality organisations with similar technology, techniques, and infrastructure, it was found out that one was more successful than the other from the service quality point of view. It also revealed that the successful organisation put more attention to the human aspect like improved management support, better communication, corrective measure implementation, and follow-ups in issues for quality (Namin, 2017).

When the gap model was compared with the performance model, it was seen that across the three hotel brands performance model was more successful and, therefore, superior to the gap model. It was also demonstrated that perceived service quality is the predecessor of customer satisfaction and not another way around. As much as tangible is important for product-based and service-based industries, responsiveness takes the lead in service-based or people-based industries. Meticulous study of service failure helps the brands to improve their service quality and therefore retain the customer (Spanaki et al., 2021).

Financial performance data, which the major significant raters released, pointed to the impact of Covid-19. Premier INN was seen to decline 70% in accommodation revenue by November 2020. IHG reported a decrease of 72% by November 2020. As per the National statistics office, the overseas footfalls declined to 96% by the second quarter of 2020 compared to the same period in 2019, while the domestic travellers and consumers opted for a staycation

during Covid restrictions (Spanaki et al., 2021). With the nation vaccinating the citizens and easing the travel restrictions, tourism is expected to benefit the hospitality industry and hotel market. But by far, the staycation will give the hospitality industry a certain respite amid the fears and the possibilities that of rest of the other countries may lag in their vaccination effort (Dube et al., 2021).

The building of theories in service quality has been started with the right intention. In a comparative study done by researchers, it was found and further highlighted that different discrete service quality constructs and has further shown that many other empirical studies have gaps in pointing out and reporting these constructs, and therefore advocating for rebuilding of such theories inclusive of these constructs on service quality management (Jones and Comfort, 2020). When traditional marketing was compared with service marketing, it was pointed out that since services do not have any tangible products, it is only a form of an interactive process. And unlike in the product business where consumption of goods happens in the service industry, it is replaced with consumption of the result or the outcome (Wood, 2020).

Service quality is highly dependent on physical appearance. The service quality delivery of a departmental store impacts consumer behaviour. Therefore, the physical appearance and the policy greatly influence the brand's overall perceived quality of service and the consumer's shopping behaviour, henceforth (Tan and Despotis, 2021). Any service-based business will have different performance requirements than those of product businesses. In the product business, the reliability of service is crucial, and therefore the reliability factor is satisfied by the delivery of the service to the customer on time and smoothly. Trust is essential in establishing long-term relationships between the customer and brand.

This trust determinant depends on empathy, politeness, personal touch, offer related promises like promptness, competence, and reliability (Wang and Tseng, 2019). These trust variables impact the relationship and the length of the relationship significantly. With the advent of technology, the usage has increased drastically within the past five to eight years in the service industry for precision. The implementation of such technology of automation, web and its effects need to be analysed. Currently, a business can deliver the service with no or little human interaction or encounter (Lai et al., 2018).

The environment thus created is virtual, which has reasoned and motivated the business to find different and discrete ways to deliver the services to the end customer. Re-evaluating the two existing theories on eliminating human encounter or interaction and automation of service quality, it was derived that the web acts as an intermediary between the brand and the customer and is, therefore, a direct link for the brand to their customers (Legrand et al., 2020). A company's ability to achieve excellence in service quality is depended on the attributes of service and the prioritisation of these attributes. It is significant for brands in the hotel market to use the quality improvement index and prioritise their service quality attributes for accurate and straightforward results (Qiu et al., 2020). For Example, SERVQUAL operates with a linear and symmetric relationship between gaps of quality of service and overall service quality (Shafiq et al., 2019). Further research and study with the nonlinear and asymmetric approach of the model shall develop and more advanced utility theory, which will focus on prioritisation for the attributes of service quality and the dimensions both. A study done on Singapore airline suggested that the four crucial elements for which are critical drivers of service and forms the skeletal framework of service marketing are: knowing the customer better and their needs better, meticulous study, and an eye for details, profits, and training – motivation session of employees in the intern in the continuum.

A study on the hotel industry's organisational culture and climate concluded that good corporate culture and environment integrates with the service quality and therefore affects the whole service quality initiative (Tan and Despotis, 2021). Organisational culture and the climate are directly linked to service quality, hotel performance, and brand image. If the Organizational culture and the environment are poor, the service quality is poor, the hotel performance dips, and the brand image goes for a toss (Canhoto and Wei, 2021). Suppose the Organizational culture and the climate are average. In that case, the service quality is moderate, and the hotel's performance is rated as average, which amounts to an intermediate brand image. However, suppose the Organizational culture and the climate are excellent. In that case, the service quality offered is of good quality, which pulls the hotel performance to the brim and makes the brand image positively stronger than ever (Ali et al., 2021).

The internal theory of marketing based on perceptual marketing states it clearly that the perceptions of the brand are the collective information a consumer gets through various outside channels, advertisements, brand awareness, their own experience, feedback, and reviews. Suppose this perception is positive and based upon the best experience, the customer

expectation increases while using the services for the second time (Wood, 2020). Now, if the interim strategy of the brand does not motivate the employees with enough incentives, salary, expeditions, and another one on one interaction and leadership theory absorbed by the higher management the front runner of the hotel industry which forms the granular and the basic foundation of the perception versus expectation are ruined for they may not be well-groomed, well trained, or smiling and promoted enough to resolve the issues for customer, instead be lost in their world of problems and stress-related to feeding mouths back at home, office politics (Haming et al., 2019). Therefore, running the forts interaction if he hotel as a brand with the customer.

This negative impact influences the expectations, and therefore, the positive perception is broken down to the reality of the expectation, which is damaging and not a smooth experience. This, in turn, may mean losing the customer forever. In this competitive world of the hospitality and hotel industry, customers do not give a second chance. They simply hop on to grab other opportunities offered by different hotels that are keen to bring them on board and will do whatever it takes (Hole et al., 2018). Therefore, they may never return. Now the number of such customers will increase by the day and word of mouth, therefore, sent across outside will be negative; these customers will ruin Google reviews and the online image because these are not just consumers of the services as stated earlier, these consumers have become prosumers, the one who consumes the product or service and creates-procreates it further by writing about their experiences, sending out feedbacks reviews so that the other peers do not get into the trap of the marketing gimmick and false promises (Kim et al., 2021). This may ruin the image of the hotel brand permanently, if not always, for the longest time. The brand to return to its glory will take forever, as it is said in the digital-web world, once you lose a customer, you will not just lose one customer but lose a brand name and brand image and further 'n' number of other potential customers (Wood, 2020).

The correlation between the excellent service and profits was studied where a holistic approach to figure the financial performance and excellent service delivery was done. The poor service reputed brand was also studied where the wealth, turnover, and number of employees were considered. It was concluded that better and good quality service is staff initiated and has produced far better profits for employees in terms of incentives and has given a better return on assets and equity for these brands than those with poor quality services. So far, SERVQUAL has been used for the measurement, neglecting the dimensions

of service quality (Haming et al., 2019). As per the European perspective, Service quality is three-dimensional, including image, functional and technical. The idea works as a filter for service quality perception. The crucial issue of service delivery has two essential and prominent factors: customer participation and customer expectation.

Services, as stated before, are interactive, and due to this interactive nature, the customer plays a central role by frequent participation in the co-follows and co-production of the service (Jones and Comfort, 2020). Now, while participating in the production, this customer also enters the process with certain expectations about the services they are to receive. A study on this founded principle showed that customers themselves contribute to the service failure because of their participatory role in the whole service delivery process and the impact or influence of the preconceived perception and expectation of the service level (Hole et al., 2018). Understanding customers' needs and choices can help the hotel managers to formulate a strategy and designs a better offering of services that will develop into operational success. The service quality definition should be based on and determined by customer demands. Quality stands for the integral unity of product features and service; therefore, it is appropriate to meet these bases upon consumers' demand and further conform to it. Unlike product business which is tangible and therefore can be offered as samples and or testing, services are not provided for pre-testing; it is a nontangible offer that cannot be touched, felt, or smelled before buying them (Kotera et al., 2020).

Therefore the potential consumer looks for some tangible evidence in feedback, reviews, references, and information that can provide confidence about the services. For example, in the hotel industry, a potential customer may look for exteriors of the hotel as soon as they arrive. They may meticulously study or observe the cleanliness of the public area lounges, washrooms, etc., of the hotel to get clues on the service quality offered by the hotel. Various research has stated that high-quality service ensures and builds loyal customers, creating a positive word of mouth. It works as a determinant for customer satisfaction, further influencing the repeat business from the same customer. It is stated that it takes around five to six times the effort or develop one customer compared to maintaining the existing one. Keeping the current customer as a brand loyalist is easy and taxing for human resources, finance, time, and efforts (Li et al., 2021). Therefore, the hotel brands that have increased the number of satisfied customers and guests experience higher customer loyalty and perform better financially than the rest of their competition. Such long-term success is dedicatedly

founded on customer or guest loyalty, repetition, retention, and sustenance, resulting in more significant revenue at present and in the future (Namin, 2017).

The instrument SERVQUAL serves the purpose of the hoteliers as per a few research. After the quantitative application of SERVQUAL, the result provides the hotel managers with some beneficial insights regarding the customer's perception and expectation. It also helps them objectively learn gaps in the quality dimensions (Oh and Kim, 2017). These researches have further stated that the usage of SERVQUAL provides insights into dimensions of service quality which is a crucial feature from the customers' perspective as more than often, these hotel managers are not aware of customers' expectations because most of the essential service dimensions necessary for the hotel managers are not crucial for the customer. The instrument, SERVQUAL, provides the hotel managers with a clear picture of the quality of service offered to the customers, viz. a viz. the expectations, need, and wishes of the customers or guests (Shafiq et al., 2019). Value has a crucial role in customer retention; therefore, providing value-added services has become a norm in today's competitive world. Value influences the customer's perception of service quality, as the service quality influences the customer's perception of value. The hotel's staff needs to know the exact attributes, which is the source of customer value (Taherdoost and Hassan, 2020).

Identifying that attribute for positioning the hotel helps the management allocate the resource accordingly. Various data analysis to establish the regression and correlation has uncovered untrusting facts. It was found that there is a direct influence of reliability and assurance on the functional value. These applicable values include customer belief via hotel security and transaction transparency (Vlachos, 2020). It was also found out that any tangible cues like good programs and well-dressed staff, modern updated equipment are strongly associated with the value. For any personalised service, a good understanding of the customer's needs, expectations, and perceptions satisfy the guest to a great extent, influencing the emotional value. It was also found that Responsiveness through either hi-tech gadget innovations affects the epistemic or conditional value (Tan et al., 2017). This connection between the service quality cues and the attributes forming the value system further facilitates the designing of the skeletal framework for device recovery sessions and programs. Also, it becomes the foundation for the management to make their services more competitive, better served as per the perception and expectation of the customer (Wang and Tseng, 2019).

It considers the hotel price and its star classification (one-star, two-star, three-star, four-star, five-star, seven-star etc.) as critical determinants of the brand image of hotels in the United Kingdom. It is found that most of them have negative feedback that pots the experience of the services owing to the customer's perception and their expectations. The price with the age of the infrastructure or brand has also hurt the service quality assessment (Ali et al., 2021). Now the guests of these hotels, especially those who pay higher for comfort and luxury, are immensely demanding. Any shortcomings, no matter how small it is in the services and facilities, consequentially bring negative ratings for the hotels because these guests come with certain expectations, which are relatively higher (Kim et al., 2021).

The four key determinants impacting the customer's expectations of hotel brands are the hotel star category promised services, price, and location. High cost or price for such services demands superior service quality levels, whereas the less expensive hotels relatively have lesser expectations and therefore less impact on the guest perception. The system of star category induces the quality indicators and norm levels, which primarily increases with the increase in star levels (Dube et al., 2021). The fourth and last determinant, location, significantly impact customers' expectations. If the hotel's location is exotic, customers' expectations automatically increase. Therefore, the analysis was done to associate customer expectations and customer perception about service quality. Many spa hotels have successfully used SERVQUAL and have confirmed that it is crucial to realise the goal through a service that aptly suits the customer's needs, wishes, and demands (Haming, 2019). To curtail the gap between the services offered, the services expected, and anticipated customers perception of the services delivered, each staff member should aim that each time they service the guest, they provide them with a positive experience.

The hotel management should also ensure that they make a standardised service quality system that is well defined and transparent at the same time. The management should ensure smoothness, precision, and promptness in the quality and social dimensions attributes (Vlachos, 2020). Quality dimensions include meeting the customer's requirements, timeliness and punctuality in serving the customer, and controlled smooth coordination, while the social extent includes promptly solving the customer's problems and queries positive and ever-smiling warm attitude, and providing individual attention to the customers (Tan and Despotis, 2021). For the longest, the need to understand the perception of international and domestic tourism in the hotel of the United Kingdom was neglected. However, after an extensive study,

it was found that there is no significant difference in all the dimensions of service quality for domestic and international tourists except the Value.

International tourists have reviewed the global chain positively much higher.

They receive service quality at par with global standards. In contrast, the domestic tourist does not consider that, and therefore they rate their home-grown brand much better than the international chains (Qiu et al., 2019). Data and research have confirmed that a satisfactory recovery in services can pull off the brand's positive image. It is also supposed that there is a close bond between the service quality offered and the customer's loyalty towards the hotel brand. It is a crucial predecessor of customer loyalty. Better service further helps in customer retention. Brand image is the customer perception of the brand and their services through the various channels they encounter the brand, like advertisements, experience, feedback, etc. The customers who receive personal attention and excellent service eventually become loyal to the brand and the hotel (Tan et al., 2017). The research was done to establish a link between the brand image, service quality, and customer loyalty shows that service quality directly impacts the hotel brand's image. However, service quality has no direct impact on customer loyalty (Tan et al., 2017).

Other attributes to service quality form the brand's image; they may directly impact customer loyalty. This only adds another angle to the fiercely competitive world of the hotel market and hospitality industry. Through a study done, it was found out that the most crucial factor and therefore the critical determinants of the service quality resulting in customer satisfaction and repeat visits are: housekeeping, quality, and performance of food and beverage, front office operations, and willing-smiling hotel staff (Dube et al., 2021). In terms of priority, if put against the customer's perception, the front office operation becomes the most noteworthy and significant determinant. The quick check-in checks out, curtailing the long waits and the well-behaved staff across the counter wins the brownie points (Vlachos, 2020). This is followed by the willing, smiling, well-behaved staff interaction, which increases the chance of the guest's revisit. And then the third key determinant was the housekeeping which not only includes the hygiene, cleanliness but also the quality of furniture, attractive interiors, and décor of the hotel and the hotel rooms, appealing and warm theme, temperature and music, and the last key determinant which is significant in deciding whether the customer may want to revisit or not is the food and beverage not just in the form of tasting but also how attractively they are served and put (Kim et al., 2021).

Furthermore, there is a need for continuous performance evaluation of these critical determinants for the hotels of the UK to be successful and maintain a good, positive, and strong brand image. A comparative study of many such service models by effective neural networks shows that Performance-Expectation Gap is the best way to evaluate the service quality. It outperforms the rest of the techniques and can be used for any industry (Hussain et al., 2021). Hotel guest expects high and improved service quality levels in all dimensions of technical, social, service, etc. however, they may give low scores in the tangibles, which are a great motivating and learning for the hotel manager s to improve in the physical attributes of the building, infrastructure, interiors, colour coordination, theme, staff appearance, etc. As stated before, there is a definite relationship between the service quality and the hotel's performance. Improved service quality has resulted in positive changes in hotel performance. Service delivery and better infrastructure result in a better brand image, resulting in increased revenue (Jones and Comfort, 2020). It has been seen that improving the service competency of employees and many services offered at the room to the guests resulted in an increase in the revenue from the room, which suggest that the hotel can aim at higher room revenue by continuously improving the tangibles of the hotels including the facilities and the ambience.

As stated before, there is a gap between customer expectation and perception viz. a viz. the service delivery (Hussain et al., 2021). Often, the customer expectation of the quality of service is not met by the management of the hotel, which in turn proves that assurance, reliability, and responsiveness are the essential dimensions. Therefore, the hotel management needs to re-work improving the service attitude. The hotels can satisfy real expectations, but if the intangibles are left untreated, the customer expectations are not met, resulting in bad reviews and, therefore, loss of the hotel's brand image (Vlachos, 2020). It becomes crucial for the service industry like hotels to continuously improve the quality of services as no set practice for long can sustain the hotel unless it doesn't change with the changing times or improve with the changing times and generations. The customer changes with each age, needs, expectations, and how they perceive the brand and the brand image changes. The value they consider essential differs from that of a previous generation or a generation two-decade older than the existing one (Wood, 2020). For hotels to understand their customer and keep changing their service quality, being in sync with the generation, a new set of customers and time will help any hotel sustain its brand image, improve it for better and sustain the profits.

Hotels need to meticulously observe the personal interactions between the staff and the guests. That plays a significant role in customer satisfaction, leading to better reviews and a strong hotel brand image. It is of prime significance for the hotels of The United Kingdom to be fully, dedicatedly and devoted to the continuous improvement of their services and the dimension gap of these services (Li et al., 2021). Hotel management also needs to make the staff realise the impotence of such attributes to serve better, contributing to the impression of service and brand image. To make a strong brand image and presence, hotels need to identify the customer's expectations and take the cues to better their services as per the customer demands, which will help them in increasing the hotel performance and further the brand image and the revenues to sustain and wade through the competitive world of hospitality.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in improving brand image. This research seeks to identify a metric to measure the effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving the brand images of hotels in the UK. The specific *research objectives* are:

- To determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in improving brand image.
- To identify a metric to measure the degree of effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK.

Research questions

- What is service quality and the critical elements of successful service quality strategies?
 - What is brand image, and how it is measured?
 - The issues the hotel industry is facing in terms of service quality
- What measure can the hospitality industry (hotels) implement a service quality strategy that demonstrably improves brand image?

The organisation of the study

This section gives a concise review of the research chapters. This research has been divided into six chapters. Chapter 1 is the introduction which introduces the topic ‘the key determinants of service quality strategies that improve the brand image of hotels in the United Kingdom’ and defines the essential terms related to the industry and the factors which determine the hospitality success and its brand image keep the UK market in mind. The background of the hospitality and hotel market of the United Kingdom in which the needs RevPAR, occupancy, and revenues have been compared follows the introduction from the past through various graphs for analysis. It gives an in-depth knowledge through multiple data representation and graphs idea of how the hospitality industry of the United Kingdom has been moving since the past decade and the kind of investments it has grabbed for itself. The background gives the firm ground on the industry; this is then followed by the rationale in which in-depth knowledge through graphical data representation has been shown of the industry's current status in 2020 and 2021. It also has a stark analysis of the United

Kingdom's hospitality industry from 2008 till 2021 and the impact of BREXIT and COVID-19 on the hospitality industry of the United Kingdom. This provides the rationale of the study and the research and makes the foundation to determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in improving the brand image. This also helps identify the effectiveness of different services quality services, which will help strengthen the UK's hotel's Brand image.

Chapter 2 covers the Literature review through various relevant theories and relevant literature and an overview of the research context of the study. Chapter 3 is the methodology, explaining the methods used to analyse the data and the sector. The qualitative and the quantitative approach has been used to put forth a precise conclusion and recommendation further post the analysis. Chapter 4 entails the Data presentation, which compares the quantitative data viz. a viz. the UK hospitality industry and hotel market. It identifies the findings of the quantitative research. Chapter 5 includes the discussion and analysis of the data collected in questionnaires quantitative research methodology. Basis this analysis and discussion, the Conclusion is drawn in Chapter 6. Recommendations are given henceforth for the UK industry to take a cue from and apply to pick them up from the Brexit and COVID-19 impact.

2. Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 The hospitality industry in the United Kingdom

The hospitality industry is diverse, and this is due to the classification within the industry, ownership, innovation, the grading system, service provided, leisure facilities as well as future trends. The hospitality industry in the United Kingdom is exemplified on a large scale by the state's hotels, restaurants, pubs, and leisure companies and produces about 4% of the United Kingdom GDP (Qiu et al., 2019). It's one of the most massive industries globally and is continuously exposed to rapid growth. In the United Kingdom, there are over 46,000 hotels and guest houses, and the hostel industry constitutes an important sector of the economy, constituting a yearly turnover of about 40 billion pounds. This industry employs about 1.6 million people and comprises around 127,000 properties. This industry is ranked the third-largest sector that creates employment (Dube et al., 2021). It includes various commercial industries such as fast food outlets, hotels, restaurants, motels, clubs, and takeaways. It also forms part of the welfare sector, including residence halls, educational institutions, nursing homes, hospitals, and prisons. Within the two factors that compose the hospitality industry, accommodation and sustenance, housing is one of the most critical sectors, which is the reason behind the continuous innovation realised in the hotel industry (Wang and Tseng, 2019).

Hospitality is a vast industry that comprises a spectrum of spheres and businesses around hotels, restaurants, travel and tourism, sports and leisure, and gaming. The industry can be defined in various ways. It can be determined using the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC), founded in the United Kingdom in 1948 (Qiu et al., 2019). This way of classification defined the industry under the 1968 classification. It stated that the hospitality industry is a combination of various establishments, both licensed and unlicensed, that serve the purpose of selling and providing meals, drinks, light refreshments, intoxicating beverages, and accommodation (Kim et al., 2021). In recent times the industry has been looked at as an industry that is responsible for the provision of food and accommodation to the guest; it is said to be a home away from home and strives to provide the customer with the best comfort and satisfaction in most areas of their lives when they are out of their homes. Two distinct

services constitute the hospitality industry, and they're; the supply of food and beverages to those eating away from home, and also catering to those who don't prepare their meals as well as the collection of overnight accommodation for those that are away from homes (Ali et al., 2021).

The hospitality industry is the kind that largely relies on economic sentiment and customer confidence. Continuously, the industry is faced with increasing pressure in terms of quality, value, and innovation; it is faced with continuous changes when coming to what the industry provides and how it is provided. The industry is continuously battling the need to supply skilled personnel to deliver the best possible service (Al-Ababneh, 2017). Consumer satisfaction is what the industry thrives on, making the customer the primary determinant of the businesses, the very same customer who relies on other sectors and measures for income. And with the delicacy of European and United Kingdom economies combined with the non-indulgent actions of the Government, the customers are left under tremendous pressure (Rather et al., 2019). And this makes the value of brand strengthening and the development of effective distribution channels more heard of and more essential than ever before. Digitalisation has led to an increase in the industry's digital engagement with the consumer, who has recently shown a level of interest in more personalised interactions with brands that have prioritised social media engagement and mobile technology on a multi-channel basis (Koc, 2020).

2.1.1 Organisational structure

The organisational structure is the conventional system that details required job relationships that align the employees to favour them in archiving the company's goal. It's referred to as the interaction between the people and various segments of an organisation—organisational structure details certain activities, including task allocation, coordination, and supervision directed towards achieving goals. Types of organisational structures include pre-bureaucratic, bureaucratic, post-bureaucratic, functional, divisional, flat, tall, and matrix structures (Palacios et al., 2021). Various organisations settle on multiple systems; some have balanced designs while others are tall. Tall organisational structures are found within large organisations such as hotels, which are comprised of various levels of employees, from managers to the workers whilst the flat organisational structure are associated with small-

scale organisations that don't have multiple levels of staff, for example, in a restaurant owner, can be a manager, and a cook as well (Mo et al., 2021). Various types of ownership and structures are found within the accommodation sector. There are two trendy types of ownership in the hospitality industry: franchised and sole right. In the franchise system of ownership, one must pay the franchisor a particular amount of money to operate a business. Within this type of ownership, one can cut marketing and promotion expenses. In this ownership system, the suffering from the business fluctuations is buffered as one is a part of a chain (Lee and Severt, 2017).

Sole ownership indicates starting up a hotel and maintaining it without receiving financial aid from outside sources except for loans. The primary benefit of this type of ownership is that the owner gets all the profits and can structure the business however they want. The downside is that the owner has to bear the input expenses and losses without fully supporting the hotel chains (Kasiri et al., 2017).

2.1.2 Hospitality market, Trends, and investment

The hospitality market in the United Kingdom is sectioned into type (chain and independent hotels) and segment (service apartments, budget and economy hotels, mid and upper-scale hotels, and luxury hotels). The industry has become kinetic regarding investment volumes recorded recently, considering the level of uncertainty brought upon by Brexit. In 2018 the sector realised positive fundamental performance values (Hole et al., 2018). The overall key performance realised in London city was fractionally eminent compared to the overall performance recognised by the entire state. In 2018, the average room rate (ARR) for the United Kingdom was about GBP 87 whilst the average room rate for London was about GBP 150 (Floracic, 2020). During the same year, the occupancy rate (OR) was 78.8% for the United Kingdom and 84% for the city of London. London's revenue per available room (RevPAR) was settled at GBP 124. At the same time, the RevPAR for the United Kingdom was fixed at GBP 67.5, making London the most significant contributor to the entire industry. With the ever-increasing number of travellers to the United Kingdom, there's an increase in the demand for hotels, especially in London city (Floracic, 2020).

The hospitality industry is very dependent on current and future trends, thus continuously embracing change and striving to remain sustainable. Various sectors within this industry experience multiple sensations and are impacted by these trends differently. There are several trends in the accommodation sector. Recently, people have become more mindful of what they put into their bodies; they are now conscious about the kind of food and drinks they take, resulting in a shift towards healthy and organic food and beverages (Makanyeza & Chikazhe, 2017). Digitalisation is also one of the current trends; technology is taking up space and becoming a leader in many industries. Innovation has brought new technological inventions that have improved life and fastened service delivery. Globalisation has created a space for businesses to constantly see the need to broaden their spheres continuously and take up space in the global market (Lai et al., 2018). It has come with the trend of establishing branches in various states. The other direction, with a significant impact, is consumer spending. The higher people earn, the higher the spend, so any aspect detrimental to consumer incomes becomes harmful to the industry. Booking for reservations on the websites is also a current trend that contributes positively to this industry (Haming et al., 2019).

In the United Kingdom, hospitality has continued to expand over the years. The hotel sector has been flourishing annually as tourists continuously go into the United Kingdom, primarily London, in large numbers. The sum of money spent by overseas visitors during their visits to the United Kingdom went up by 15.9% during July of 2010 to 1.96 billion pounds compared to 1.69 billion pounds during the same month of 2009. An increase in investments within the industry was experienced in 2018 (Jones and Comfort, 2020). The industry is comprised of various sectors one can invest in. Investors have the option of investing in multiple types of chain hotels, boutique hotels, business and conference hotels, budget hotels, motels, and lodges, among others. Some investors can opt for investing in property within the hotel industry, and some can build up hotel businesses. Investing in chain hotels and well-established hotels gives one the benefit of saving time and cutting the costs required for promotions and marketing (Hussain et al., 2021). Trending in recent times are the budget hotels associated with low disposable income. People are interested in spending less for more. Apart from starting up a business and being a sole owner, investors can purchase the franchising license or get involved in management contracting. Even though the uncertainty surrounding Brexit has negatively affected the investment sphere, the increasing demand has supported the country in drawing in investors (Hole et al., 2018).

2.1.3 The impact of Brexit on the industry

Brexit is an abbreviation of two words, Britain and exit, and it refers to the withdrawal process of the United Kingdom from the European Union (EU). The government of the United Kingdom's proposal for its post-Brexit immigration system poses several issues to the industry, which were initially catered for by EU nationals. Brexit has brought a flock of legislation around recruiting workers from the European Union, visa requirements and the right to work status, and the need to become an approved employer-sponsor (French, 2018). The primary challenges posed by the immigration system will have a detrimental effect on the hotel industry as these challenges are set to increase skill shortages. Many roles may not cater to the new skills threshold criteria. The other increase will be in costs, as the new immigration system will burden immigration compliance with extra administrative work, resulting in more time-consuming and complicated procedures. Businesses will have to familiarise themselves with the cost implications of this system, which includes costs involved in the intended extra compliance required in motoring requirements, the prices of up-skilling staff and automation, and visa costs (Filimonau & Mika, 2019).

The challenges brought upon by the new immigration system include the need for the employers to have a Sponsor Licence to employ EU residents; this system applies to both EU and non-EU nationals equally. The other challenge is that the minimum salary threshold is set to use about 25,000 pounds. Immigration fees are also set to apply to both EU and non-EU nationals, whereby a five-year visa will require an upfront fee of around 8,500 pounds per employee (Dube et al., 2021). The other issue is that employers already possessing a Sponsor License will have to review whether or not their current procedures can cater to higher volumes. In this system, employees will not be able to sponsor lower skill roles; thus, a review will have to be performed to evaluate the parts that might no longer be eligible for non-UK workers (Kim et al., 2021).

For the United Kingdom hotel industry to survive the uncertainty surrounding Brexit, they will have to look into which roles under the new system will still be eligible for sponsorship of EU workers. They will have to intensify automation throughout the industry, consider

what is appropriate for the business, its impact on consumer experience, and understand the changes coming with this system and their effects (French, 2018). An assessment on who needs to apply for Sponsor Licence will have to be undertaken and the associated procedures. An upgrade on the current HR policies is also required. The industry also needs to train internal teams on the new system requirements, prioritise up-skilling the existing staff, and determine which steps are to be taken in accommodating broader-reaching compliance requirements within the new immigration system (Hole et al., 2018).

2.1.4 The impact of Covid-19 on the industry

Covid-19 has had an enormous impact on the hospitality industry as a whole. The food and accommodation sector has suffered the most due to the pandemic. The restrictions and regulations put in place to curb the spread of the virus have resulted in the temporary closure of businesses within various industry sectors. This restriction was so impactful to the point of rendering most companies obsolete. The pressure from Covid-19 is still felt even after loosening certain restrictions (Dube et al., 2021). The number of employees working was also reduced, which led to an overall reduction in businesses' productivity, leaving most companies vulnerable. Lockdowns had become a new standard, impacting consumer behaviour; it also negatively affected their income, affecting their spending habits. Many people were retrenched, which widened the skill gap. Hospitality comprises many non-essential sectors, which were shifted to the backseat as important sectors and workers were prioritised. The restriction of movement also meant that people would no longer travel and explore various places, which led to the closure of hotels, recreational areas, restaurants, and others (Ali et al., 2021).

The hospitality industry's economic output decreased by 90% in April 2020 compared to February 2020. The easing of restriction and the 'Eat out to Help Out' campaign boosted the industry, leading to some recovery in the summer of 2020. A decline was experienced again as a result of the tightening of restrictions. The ONS reported in early March of 2021 that 43% of the businesses were trading as compared to 74% across all industries. It was indicated that 55% of hospitality businesses had been temporarily put to a standstill, compared to only 24% of all sectors (Kim et al., 2021). From the onset of 2020 (January to March) to July 2020, there was a decline in the number of workers within the sector of 6% (147,000). There was

then a peak realised in the number of jobs on furlough under the CJRS within the food and accommodation sector on the 10th of April 2020. A decline in these jobs was then realised from April to October. However, as a result of two separate national lockdowns since October, 56% of eligible jobs in the food and accommodation were laid-off under the CJRS in January compared to 16% in all industries (Vlachos, 2020).

2.2 Issues of the hospitality industry in terms of service quality

2.2.1 Service quality in hospitality

Service quality has become an important area of attention during the past few decades. It has a significant positive impact on the return on investment, customer satisfaction and loyalty, lower costs, higher profitability, and business performance. It is an essential dimension of the competitiveness of a business. Service quality results from a judgment value that considers customer expectations and perspectives. Service quality remains one of the most critical components in this vast industry (Oh and Kim, 2017). As noted, hospitality is one industry that depends on customer satisfaction and thrives on customer confidence and loyalty. Hospitality isn't only concerned about attracting customers; it is also about keeping them. Thus very important that the service provided be held at best possible level (Lee and Cheng, 2018). Service quality is essential for attaining durable competitive merit in highly rivalrous markets. It is the determinant of many aspects in the business that determine its success rate, such as customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, brand image, the competitiveness of the industry, and surviving specific challenges.

Many people perceive service quality differently; thus essential to note various aspects of service quality equally (Wood, 2020). It can be defined as the extent to which the service satisfies the customer's expectations or needs. It can also be defined as the gross impression of customers regarding the excellence and weakness of service, which is due to the earlier definition. Parasuraman described service quality as the global judgment or attitude relating to the overall excellence or superiority of the service (Vlachos, 2020). It can also be referred to as assessing how well a delivered service conforms to the client's expectations. In recent times service quality is defined as what the customer gets out and is willing to pay for. Service quality is comprised of three components: physical facilities, staff, and materials, and

is segmented into two aspects: functional quality as well as technical quality (Tan et al., 2017). It has also been argued that service quality is comprised of five components instead of just three, those being: assurance, reliability, empathy, tangibility as well as responsiveness (Tan et al., 2017).

The functional quality of service quality is implicated in how the service is being rendered, whilst the technical quality is concerned with what kind of service is being generated. The customer sees the service being developed as the outcome. Service quality delivery, measuring, and defining in this industry is further complicated and identified by other essential dimensions such as imprecise standards and fluctuating demands (Spanaki et al., 2021). An example would be given as firms in this industry having constituted policies, procedures, and rules to regulate the standardisation of the product. Many aspects of service quality do not lend themselves to standards. Many factors in service quality within this industry are not standardised as many aspects such as friendliness, helpfulness, and politeness are the kind that is likely to be interpreted differently depending on the customer and the service delivered. Services within this industry are generally explained in intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability, and perishability (Rather et al., 2019).

There are several instruments involved in measuring service quality, and these measures vary in various sectors of the industry. As per Haming et al. (2019), the SERVQUAL scale developed by Parasuraman in 1985 is one of the most known instruments utilised to a great degree; the instrument was later refined in 1991. The SERVQUAL is based on a model that suggests that customers evaluate service quality in five defined attributes, namely: reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy as well as tangibles. The scale also proposes that service quality varies depending on the customer's expectations and perceptions of service quality. Apart from SERVQUAL, there are other widely known instruments on service quality: SERVPERE, INTERSERVQUAL, and INSQPLUS (Chaturvedi, 2017). Many instruments are intended to evaluate service quality developed within the tourism sector: HOLSERV, DINESERV, CASERV, and LODGSERV. Instruments such as DINESERV are the ones widely used in restaurants. Instruments utilised in the accommodation sector include LODGSERV and HOLSERV, whilst CASERV is used in the casino sector. Employee perception of service quality is also measured, and the instrument involved in this are INTERSERVQUAL and INTQUAL (French, 2018). As a result of certain service-specificities within the hospitality industry such as storage, inseparability, and impalpability,

a specific instrument known as SERVQUAL (services and quality) was introduced to measure service quality became the most popular scale of measurement. This scale has various features for evaluating customer perspectives and expectations of service quality within the industry (Conhoto and Wei, 2021).

Components of service quality

Tangibles – this attributes to the physical facilities, equipment, and employees’ appearance. This is concerned with the material and authentic appearance, which attracts customers. The physical feel of a company is an essential aspect of a business as people can anticipate the kind of service they will receive based on the appearance of a business. Equipment plays a vital role in all hospitality sectors in assuring that the expected service can be rendered. User-friendly technology, well-represented and proficient employees, and properly functioning facilities are all essential for the desired operation of the business (Naumov, 2019).

Responsiveness – the willingness to assist a customer and provide prompt service continuously. This is concerned with the desire to render a service and respond to the customer’s needs. Business needs to be receptive to moving the customers’ needs and preparing essential programs for the business. Responsiveness emphasises attentiveness and willingness to deal with consumer needs, complaints, or suggestions (Koc, 2020).

Reliability – this is the ability to render a service accurately and dependably. Service that is adequately rendered can enhance the perceived quality of the customer experiences. The business should provide the kind of service they sell to the customer through advertising; failing to do so shows that the industry is unreliable, and customer confidence is lost (Chaturvedi, 2017).

Assurance – This is the ability of the employees to attain customer confidence and trust. The rating of a particular service is usually determined by how the customers perceive the rendered service according to their expectations. Quality assurance relates to customer service, and poor service delivered leads to a lack of fulfilment and dissatisfaction. Best quality guarantees customer loyalty and retention (French, 2018).

Empathy – This is the extent to which individualised caring service is provided. It may be a challenge for businesses to surpass customer needs sometimes. For example, many employee deficiencies in hotels and the requirement for the best occasion, facilitating and service have increased, extending the staff-customer proportion (Qiu et al., 2019).

2.2.2 Service quality issues

Offering the best possible service depends on many factors; service quality is also dynamic and affects many aspects. It is hugely impacted by trends and is not static or formulated; it is vulnerable to change and perceptions (Oh and Kim, 2017). Below are some of the issues related to service quality within the hospitality industry.

Expectations – the entire purpose behind this industry is to meet customer expectations and keep them happy. This industry continuously seeks to close the gap between expectations and the service rendered. The industry is faced with various problems and expectations each day. And people's expectations change continuously due to their perceptions, standards, and trends. Their expectations vary a lot from one customer to another. Age is a determinant in determining the type of customers to request a service from a business, and it also influences their expectations (Vlachos, 2020). Within this industry, millennials are the fastest-growing segment and are the ones who live the fast-paced lifestyle, thus continuously expecting the fastest possible service. This indicates that all the practical and time-saving solutions pave the way to success.

In most cases, especially within this industry, time is essential for crafting the best possible service. Social media has also raised people's expectations regarding the kind of service they deserve based on the service quality and the type of service others received. When travelling or going to a particular restaurant, most people start by visiting review pages to get the feel of the kind of service offered. This plays a massive role in whether they will go or opt for another place (Ali et al., 2021).

Innovation and technological changes – digitalisation has brought about a lot of more tech-savvy customers, and innovative technology has become an essential issue within the industry. The skills required to operate the technology involved in service delivery and maintenance are of utmost importance (Al-Ababneh, 2017). Technology has primarily

changed the space of service delivery and quality. Nowadays, people partake in electronic check-ins through mobile phones or Apple watches. Identification technologies have also emerged, providing the customer with the relevant information regarding their check-in and room numbers which saves time and errors in administrative work. Contactless service, online ordering, and payment via online platforms are the new normal, and the technologies involved in making these possible say a lot about the business and are in most cases the sole determinant of the kind of service quality realised (Hole et al., 2018). Technology plays a significant role in influencing the type of service offered and delivered. Implementing technologies within this industry also comes at a cost and maintenance, directly impacting the service. Now always been an issue for this industry to combine human and technological forces with meeting customers' expectations. And complications in the technical systems, even if for a short period, can have dire consequences on the quality of service (Kotera et al., 2020).

The skilled labour shortage is one of the significant issues in the quality of service rendered and the industry. Success in this industry requires talent, knowledge, and people skills. That is why the sector prioritises up-skilling the employees to deliver the best service continuously. Unskilled personnel leads to poor service quality (Kasiri et al., 2017). This industry constantly grows and fails to meet the increasing demand for skilled employees. The best thing for this industry is to invest in training; improved training programs, hospitality industry certificates, online hospitality courses, and apprenticeships can help in providing more skilled personnel. Leadership is also an essential aspect as it ascertains proper management. Properly qualified personnel will ensure the required service quality (Wood, 2020).

Health, wellness, and hygiene – people are not only interested in having a good time, but they are also concerned about eating the correct type of food as some may be suffering from certain diseases or taking medications. Some are interested in leading a healthy lifestyle and as per Kotera et al. (2020), considering all of these aspects plus others makes service quality susceptible. One has to look at when food is stored and prepared, which impacts the food quality. The kind of procedure and techniques involved in the preparations of food also affect the food did. All of this adds to the quality of service rendered. The hospitality industry thrives on the presence of people, and it may be challenging to keep the space they occupy clean and hygienic (Legrand et al., 2020).

Pricing and security – people are interested in paying more for less. This can be detrimental to the quality of service as one needs the best material, equipment, and personnel to deliver the best service that doesn't come cheap. One cannot have a high input cost to generate a small number of profits. The other issue is security, as people need to be protected when within certain premises and their belongings. Many people suffer from ailments they are unaware of, like specific allergies that certain foods may trigger; assisting in situations improves service quality (Mo et al., 2021).

Quality systems not being followed – even when a business establishes quality systems, and sets out regulations and instructions to be followed, is it trendy for employees not to follow these instructions. The failure to follow the law and consider quality systems is due to the lack of qualification. This is related to the employees who didn't get complete information, and their training is just a formality, this kind of employees do not know the standards and learn by trial and error. The other reason is the lack of motivation which is very popular among employees (Wong and Yang, 2020).

Failure to conduct quality measurement accurately – evaluating a business is essential to identify the strategies that work best and those that don't. In the hotel business, the five gap model, critical incident technique, and perceived quality model are used to measure the quality of service accurately. Factual analysis of service quality can be attained through external expertise. Tangibility and increasing customer demands continuously improve issues faced by a business. To eradicate these issues, one must optimise customer satisfaction by curbing out factors detrimental to service quality. One can achieve this by gathering information via surveys, mystery shopping services, and performing field research (Zhang, 2017).

Reputation management and competition – companies strive to be the best out there, which isn't easy, so they keep on manipulating and trying to change the quality of service they provide, which may confuse customers as some don't like change. Many businesses also offer the same service within this industry, increasing competition (Assaker et al., 2020). This leaves the business challenged to do whatever it takes to provide the best quality and remain on top. This means that companies can now try and imitate each other and lose authenticity, which may negatively affect the service quality (Lee and Cheng, 2018).

Interactions between the customers and the employee remain the most important aspect of hospitality and the most problematic. The “The customer is always right” concept does not work in many instances when the customer clashes with the employees. Proper communication is always crucial, but this does not work in times of conflict. In some cases, the customer may have overly high expectations that the employees cannot meet, which then creates service problems—making it very essential to have good people skills, listening skills, and management skills (Hole et al., 2018).

Personalisation of customer experience – customers now expect to be recognised as individuals rather than as a group; they demand a greater degree of personalisation. They make it difficult for the business to translate insight and data into actions. Customer information regarding their buying habits and previous purchases and payments make it possible for the company to tailor the expected service quality. This shows that hospitality businesses need to continuously find unique ways to personalise a particular person’s experience (Assaker et al., 2020).

2.3 Theories about the importance of service quality in the hospitality industry

Within the hospitality industry, diversity, change, and innovation are prominent role players, competition is culture, and the requirement of the highest possible standards is always at a peak. The importance of service quality within the industry gained some concern through the past years. And superb service quality has been accepted as a medium of competitiveness and supremacy in terms of service. Customers within various sectors of this industry expect high levels of quality to be maintained in every aspect of service delivery (Altinay and Taheri, 2019). The failure to maintain quality can taint the name of the business-like customer satisfaction, and a good reputation is critical in this industry. Total quality management needs to be advanced in every aspect of service delivery within the industry. And for this to happen, businesses need to incorporate their principles into their corporate strategy to ensure high-quality service delivery and customer satisfaction.

The adoption of product/service design and modern technology is required to meet and maintain the minimum quality standards (Rather et al., 2019). This industry is very dependent on high calibre personnel; thus, employee role in service quality is significant. For businesses

to maintain their reputation and remain competitive, employees must play their part. To maintain high quality, many businesses within this industry have introduced measurement standards that are evaluated continuously. Businesses that can deliver high service quality can escape the commodification of the hospitality industry and stand out from others. This level of differentiation ascertains a competitive advantage (Chaturvedi, 2017).

Service quality is concerned with delivering constructively superior service related to customer expectations. The kind of service provided with willingness, exceptional attitude, behaviour, and effectiveness. It is all about service provision that exceeds what the customer expects. The key benefits of delivering advanced service quality include retaining customers, increasing referrals, avoiding price competition, retaining good employees, and reducing prices (French, 2018). There has been a significant revolution in marketing in the industry. Marketing is no longer interested in just making sales, and it is now interested in making repeated sales and retaining customers. The level of customer retention shows the potentiality of a business in gaining loyal customers. Satisfied customers are the ones that get the word across; they are not only essential in becoming loyal customers but also in referring new customers (Lai et al., 2018). High-quality serving businesses don't suffer from price competition as people are always willing to spend considerable money on high quality. Serving advanced quality makes the business stand out, and the better the quality, the more people are willing to pay, and the company is separated from the masses. Offering good service quality awards the business a good reputation, which helps attract customers and retain employees (Mo et al., 2021).

Service quality is an essential element of the customer's perceptions and a significant element in the customer's evaluation. Quality plays a vital role in customer satisfaction in an industry where services are offered physical and non-physical products. Customers judge the service they receive on their perception of the technical outcome and how the work was delivered (Khan and Hefny, 2019). For example, a customer in a restaurant will judge the quality of service based on their perception of the meals associated with the technical outcome quality and how the dinner was served, which is related to the process quality. Customers base their service quality assessment on five dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, tangibles, empathy, and assurance (Ali et al., 2021). These are the exact dimensions representing how consumers organise information regarding service quality in their minds.

Systematic quality management is what improves the general health of a business. The benefits are highly lucrative and are essential in boosting the brand value of a business. Customers can only be satisfied when they are offered the best possible quality of service. This is why high service quality is required to gain customers' loyalty; in many businesses, happy customers are satisfied. And with intensified satisfaction comes intensified customer loyalty (Oh and Kim, 2017). In the hotel industry, the quality of service directly impacts the customer's experience. With the help of service quality management, the hotel manager can determine the level of customer loyalty to their brand. High service quality is what provides a happier environment. Even though a business's physical appearance is essential, especially in this industry, in determining customer satisfaction, it is not necessary to invest too much time and effort in erecting over-the-top designs (Koc, 2019).

Service quality management argues that incorporating too flashy appearances makes the customers feel alienated as they prefer simple, personalised architecture that provides them with a homely feel. Security is also of utmost importance within this industry as people leave their homes to visit various places (Namin, 2017). During these visits, they need to be protected and their belongings; they also need to eat safe food, another service quality factor. Providing good service quality depends on security; providing security throughout all the service delivery processes is essential and is what some customers base their perception of service quality on. Service quality is necessary when coming to brand value. Every business, regardless of the sector, thrives on brand value. Whether it is the market share or customer experience, maintaining maximum brand value is essential for a business, and service quality management assists in creating and preserving the value of a company (Palacios, 2021).

Service quality management remains a crucial element in sustaining competitive advantage and customer confidence in the brand in this overly competitive field. Managing service quality is seen as the life-giving force of all operations within this industry. In every element of service quality, technical and functional qualities should be well-kept to improve assurance, reliability, empathy, tangibility, reliability, and responsiveness. Since the well-being of a business, its customer satisfaction, and its competitiveness rely on the quality of service, service quality management becomes an essential issue in the hospitality industry (Lai et al., 2018).

2.3.1 The unified service theory

Figure 2.1 Unified service theory (Baker, 2017)

This theory outlines services from nonservices processes and acts as a critical unifying principle by identifying and revealing key commonalities across seemingly separate service businesses. The unified service theory determines principles common to a wide range of services and gives a unifying ground for different service operations theories and models. This includes traditional service characteristics and the customer contact theory, operational outcomes relating to capacity and demand management, service strategy, service quality, and others (Baker, 2017). These are explained using the unified service theory. The unified service theory has been used in the curriculum and provides a common reference point for service management researchers to anchor future testing and building ideas. The understructure of the unified service theory is that customers are involved in the production of the service as much as the providers. They supply inputs, and for this reason, issues of quality and improvement must impact and be impacted by the customer in their different roles (Chivandi et al., 2019).

2.3.2 Unified service theory and service quality

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Varying from manufacturing, the customer's inputs are key when value is created in service business processes. The expected output becomes questionable and affects customer perceived quality when these inputs are incomplete, defective, and non-conforming. The service process effectiveness, customer satisfaction, and job design are all affected when the customer provides unreliable inputs. Quality of service is also impacted when the customers refuse to cooperate with quality and productivity choose not to accept technological introductions and process improvements (Chaturvedi, 2017). This occurs due to service providers trying to render quality service that conforms to the set standards and the customer distracting the improvement process by supplying unreliable inputs. The customer's perception of service quality is essential for the service provider. It is about the interactions responsible for the change of perception of the customer and that impact the service process. The balance is provided between the culture and structure of a business and the retention of the customer. Perceived service quality has an advantage of intensified reliability by the customer, cost reduction, and improves the quality and production of a business and thus its profitability. This model provides the base for investigating the context in hospitality within the United Kingdom (Kasiri et al., 2017).

2.3.3 Behavioral theory

This theory emphasises the importance of the human element in increasing productivity. Following the behavioural study, a positive correlation exists between the workforce that has been improved and the performance of employees. Elton Mayo conducted research that studied the impact of workplace lighting on productivity, which revealed no correlation, as productivity increased the same way in both dim and lit rooms. The second stage of the research had employees without any supervision, and a result of this was that employees were able to better interact with one another. They had better performance both in an individual and group setting. Behavioural studies led to the emergence of modern human resource management practices that increased employee treatment (Maslaksi and Sesen, 2019).

2.3.4 Classical approach

The classical approach, also referred to as scientific management, focuses on online supervision instead of the overall organisation. The theory seeks to locate one unique way of

performing a task. Managers are applying the classical approach work towards finding ways of performing tasks that are more efficient than others. Within this approach, efficiency is as seen a way of doing things right. This theory is not concerned with effectiveness being seen as a process that improves the quality of service (Namin, 2017).

2.3.5 Management science

This is different from the scientific method; this is interested in applying the scientific method and mathematics in the construction and testing of models required in improving performance. The steps included are observation, development, hypothesis testing, and writing conclusions. Not like the scientific method, management science puts focus on effectiveness. Managers put action research to use, which is associated with the informal collection of information, the development of alternative solutions, intervention strategies, implementing changes and evaluating the effects on the performance of a business (Ntounis et al., 2021).

2.3.6 Contingency approach

The contingency approach emphasises the influence of situational circumstances on the performance and organisation. The decision taken by management is based on the current situational variables such as leaders, environment, and followers (Naumov, 2019).

2.3.7 Systems management

According to systems management, a business is a microcosm within an independent microcosm. A decision in the industry can only be made after finding out its effects on the bigger picture (Oh and Kim, 2017).

2.3.8 Prospect theory

Figure 2.2 Prospect Theory (Naumov, 2019)

The prospect theory is a descriptive theory whereby an individual's alternatives are limited to a series of prospects evaluated independently of a particular value function. The prospect theory and the value function explain the non-linear and symmetric relationships. The value function of the prospect theory comprises three characteristics: reference point dependency, loss aversion (the process of steeper for losses than for gains), and diminishing sensitivity (concave for increases and convex for losses). The expectations of the service quality construct the reference point. The aversion that is integrated into the prospect theory proposes to loom larger than gains (Naumov, 2019). When coming to the satisfaction context, a negative deviation from the reference point, expectations should carry more weight in the gross satisfaction judgment than the equal amounts of positive attribute performance. The diminishing sensitivity within the context indicates that, at high (low) levels of service quality, the positive (negative) version of a particular item should not impact satisfaction as hugely as it does on the lower levels of happiness. This very development is the same as the diminishing returns. A two-step approach was established to understand whether a relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction can be described by utilising the prospect theory. The first step of this approach is determining whether a non-linear relationship exists (Kim et al., 2021).

2.3.9 Service quality theory

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Figure 2.3 Service Quality Theory

As per Maslakci and Sesen (2019) and Chivandi et al. (2019);

The service theory entails knowing what is considered permanent and regular in-service production.

Service customer theory identifies the customers' needs and strives to exceed them.

Service quality – is the comparison of perceived performance expectations of a service with perceived performance, which gives rise to the equation $\text{service quality} = \text{perceived performance} - \text{perceived expectations}$.

Service quality theory states that the client will judge that quality is low if the performance doesn't meet their expectations and increases when expectations are met.

2.3.10 Balance theory

The balance theory is applied to determine how service provides, and customer interrelationships influence the quality of service. Propositions are rendered regarding how and why both positive and negative relationships among parties are developed and the consequences on quality, the efficient outcome, and withdrawal behaviour. Examining the service triangle within a framework like this can considerably enhance the understanding of service quality delivery and lead future research efforts in the continuous improvement domain (Qiu et al., 2019).

2.3.11 SERVQUAL theory

Figure 2.4 SERVQUAL Theory (Haming et al., 2019)

As per Haming et al. (2019), this is a multi-scale created to assess customer perceptions of service quality in various industries. The SERVQUAL scale decomposes the notion of service quality into five components discussed as follows:

Tangibles – this is associated with physical aspects of the business; this includes equipment, staff appearance, and the physical element of the entire industry.

Reliability is concerned with the willingness and ability to render services accurately and dependably.

Responsiveness is all about the willingness one shows in the service delivery and handling of customer issues.

Assurance – This is the dimension that deals with the ability of the staff to inspire confidence as well as trust

Empathy is about the extent to which individualised caring service is rendered.

The SERVQUAL represents the quality of service as the discrepancy between the expectation of a customer and the perception of the quality of service they received, requiring customers to answer several questions about the service they received based on their perceptions and expectations. The utilisation of perceived versus the actual service received makes the SERVQUAL measure an attitude measure related to but not the same as satisfaction (Shafiq et al., 2019).

2.4 Models and frameworks about service quality

Services and high-quality products can meet or exceed the customer's expectations, which results in customer satisfaction. Quality comprises the expected benefit or development being realised. A customer does a mental calculation before purchasing a product or service; this calculation is based on the worth of the product or service they are interested in and the amount of money they are about to pay for it. This will determine the customer's likeliness to continue with the purchase, which will impact their perceived value (Salem et al., 2019). Quality is a function of the customer's perspective on quality which varies significantly among customers. Marketing has an enormous impact on how the customer views quality. Marketing is responsible for crafting positive anticipation about purchasing a particular product in a customer's mind. Should the customer not realise that anticipation, their expectations are not met, the customer is not satisfied, and therefore the quality has not been recognised in the customer's eyes (Kuhzady & Ghasemi, 2019). Quality focuses on the standards or specifications that a specific service provider promises.

Service quality dwells on the outcome of the activities and resources shaped to offer service against the customer's expectations. Service quality is a product of the excellence of product and service delivery, the value, conformance to specifications, and the meeting and exceeding customer expectations. Based on the gaps model, service quality recognises that expectations are subjective and neither predictable nor static. The confirmation theory influences this service quality model, which compares a product or service performance and a customer's expectations (Ahmad et al., 2019).

Quality is the most critical factor of service delivery within this industry. Products and services must be crafted with the customer in mind as it is the essential factor for them and the basis for their opinion, leading to archiving service quality. The quality of service influences the customer profile for the service product and the demand of the service (Salem et al., 2019). Service quality's impact on the profits and financial indicators of the business's performance is essential in service marketing. Service quality is seen as a strategic force and a fundamental problem of service marketing management. Since it affects the continuous improvement of service performance through increasing the market share and profit development, it must also be noted that service quality is a substantial source of sustainable competitive advantage (Ahmad et al., 2019). Businesses that build their brands based on high

service quality have a good reputation and are likely to retain loyal customers and have great brand value.

Cosmopolitan models of service quality and their limitations have been studied for many. The specific understanding of which dimensions of quality customers regard as necessary in the evaluation process is easier said than done (Wood, 2020). Setting quality standards solely based on the misguided assumption of the customer is not sufficient. Various measurement criteria are required for multiple concepts such as customer expectations and loyalty, customer perceptions, and customer satisfaction. The assessment of these concepts requires various scales of measurement, the scope of opinions, and behaviour and attitudes (Kuhzady & Ghasemi, 2019).

Quality of service can be separated into two segments: tangible product orientation and intangible service delivery. The most crucial segment of the ethereal service delivery as most tangible hospitality products is becoming. The actual product orientation focuses on the development itself based on two perspectives. The first perspective is the product/service features, which are concerned with features responsible for the customer's satisfaction. Companies are always set on expanding and developing additional features to satisfy the customer (Agwa et al., 2017). This approach poses additional costs on the company's exiting input costs. Additional customer expenditure on these other features may cater to these costs. Customer expectations are formed by the company's image, word-of-mouth, marketing, and price levels. A guest staying at a hotel will have different expectations from staying in a motel. Product features are related to customer expectations (Sánchez-Pérez et al., 2020). The second segment is freedom from deficiencies, which is highly concerned with the service's functionality. This segment is comprised of the tangible service delivery orientation, which focuses on the process of service delivery which involves the two essential components and is the technical quality which is related to the means of service delivery, and functional quality related to how a service is rendered (Kadir and Jamaludin, 2019). The technical quality includes the systems and infrastructure required for service delivery, such as computerised systems, machines, and technical solutions.

The customer is continuously exposed to many interactions with the service provider in the hospitality industry—a successful meeting results from the functional areas set to provide the best experience for the customer. The technical quality must be sufficient and put in place to

make sure that customer satisfaction is achieved. The functional quality involves employee behaviour, attitudes, service-mindedness, appearance, internal relations, accessibility, and customer contacts. Service quality models help people understand the complexity entailed in service quality. Below are several models and frameworks of service quality (Ali et al., 2021).

2.4.1 Perceived service quality model

This model was introduced by Christian Gronroos of the Swedish School of Economics in 1982. Cristian has proposed that studies related to service quality and subsequent model development have been primarily based on what the customer regards as quality from the very beginning. This indicates that service quality emerges from the marketing concept that focuses on the customer. What is considered necessary here is what the customer perceives as quality and not what the service provider sees as quality (Agwa et al., 2017). Customer purchasing behaviours have greatly influenced many services quality models. After the purchase, the impression that the customer's perceptions are the function of their expectations, laying on the foundation of the confirmation/disconfirmation concept of service quality (Wood, 2020). According to the perceived service quality model, service quality perceived by the customer roots from the expectations and experiences of the customer. If the expected quality exceeds their standard, the total perceived quality becomes positive. If the perceived quality does not meet the low expectations, then the perceived quality is negative (Ahmad et al., 2019).

2.4.2 SERVQUAL/ Five-gap model of service quality

This is a model of measurement that is crafted from the pioneering work of Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry. This model is concerned with how a customer differentiates service quality by comparing the expected service and the perceived (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1994). This comparison comes up in three forms: met expectations, unmet expectations, and exceeded expectations. The quality of service is expected to be satisfied

when the customer's expectations are met. It is poor when customer expectations are not met and surplus when the expectations are exceeded (Haming et al., 2019). The model's key fundamental building block compares expected and perceived service. During the comparison process between the customer's desired service and the perceived service, it is essential to seek insight into the type of measurers utilised in the scheduled service, which becomes the basis of the comparison. The customers use five principal dimensions to judge the service quality: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. The SERVQUAL instrument also uses these dimensions to obtain customer expectations and perceptions (Wood, 2020). The assurance dimension includes the employees' competence, knowledge, courtesy, and ability to deliver the expected service.

The competency of the employees refers to the skills, knowledge, and willingness they possess required in service delivery. And courtesy is about the friendliness, respect, honesty, politeness, and trustworthiness they portray during service delivery. Tangible's dimension is concerned with the appearance and physical properties of the service (Qiu et al., 2020). A business's physical attributes, equipment and material, and how the employees look to promote the quality of service. Responsiveness is associated with the willingness the personnel shows when rendering a service. The reliability dimension is concerned with the ability of the service provider to keep the promises they made regarding the quality of service they render. It is about being dependent, accurate, and trustworthy in delivering service. And the last dimension, empathy, is about the level of attention a service provider gives to the customer. The kind of attention given to the customer should be the one that is characterised by individuality; it should show care, approachability as well as the availability of service providers during service delivery (Rather et al., 2019).

Figure 2.5: Five-gap model

This is another popular model of service quality; it proposes that understanding the customer’s expectations is possibly the essential step in service quality. They are making it very important that a company knows the customer’s expectations to craft the service quality. This is a marketing concept, and the consultative selling approach extension first learns through asking questions regarding the needs and wants of the customer, and secondly through providing the service or product benefits responsible for satisfying the customer needs and wants (Qiu et al., 2019). As per Njau et al. (2017) and Nazari et al. (2020), this model comprises five gaps discussed below.

Gap 1: Consumer expectations VS management perceptions – many service providers within this industry often fail to understand the customer’s expectation of the service delivered. This

also includes which features of the service provided are responsible for providing high-quality products and services (atkinson). Gap 1 of this model happens when the breakdown of understanding takes place. An example would be in a hotel when the manager develops a system that ensures that no guest waits for more than 15 minutes to check-in. Gap 1 would exist if a guest complains after 10 minutes. In most instances, hospitality businesses survey customers to understand their expectations, the expectations that are constantly changing. If the service and products delivered don't step up to these changes, then the gap 1 broadens. The constant evolution of customer expectations requires that one continuously be aware and remain apprised through ongoing research. Formal and informal research is the source of utmost impotence in understanding the customer's constantly changing expectations. The other vital source of the continuously evolving customer expectations is the Salesforce(Kang, Jame and Alexandris, 2002).

Gap 2: management perception VS service quality specification – when the hospitality service providers are aware of the customer expectation but cannot cater to those expectations by crafting the service delivery according to these expectations, then gap 2 occurs. The reasons behind gap 2 are inefficient commitment to service quality, inadequate task standardisation, the failure to set goals, and the lack of the perception of the feasibility of addressing customer expectations(Lehtinen). This industry is often short-term-oriented due to the short-term profits and industry's unwillingness to invest in human resources and technology, resulting in quality problems.

Gap 3: Service quality specifications VS service delivery – when the hospitality managers have understood what the customer expects and have put measures in place to meet the customer expectations and have also developed systems and specifications to deliver the desired service, but the employees are not willing to offer, then gap three is experienced perceived (Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry, 1990). Reasons behind gap 3 include the failure to lead employees properly, no proper selection and training of employees, a healthy working environment isn't granted, and the employees are not given the required facilities for service delivery.

Gap 4: Service delivery VS external communications – when the management makes promises in its external communications and fails to deliver, then gap 4 takes place. External contacts include but are not limited to public relations, advertising, pricing messages, and

personal selling. It is essential to ensure that marketers ensure that operations can deliver the promises made by the marketing sector (Kang, 2006). General Managers must have sufficient knowledge of operational processes, and the marketing process as these must work together to meet customer expectations.

Gap 5: Expected service VS perceived service – gap 5 depends on the other gaps. The key to achieving service quality lies in exceeding the customer expectations, and the high or low-quality service judgment depends on how consumers perceive the performance regarding what they expected.

2.4.3 Critical incident model

Patterson, Walker, and Lovelock describe the critical incident as a technique designed to evoke details about services that peculiarly satisfy or dissatisfy the customer. The information can be collected via in-house comment cards or one-on-one interviews in the hotel industry. The data collected through the stated mediums is responsible for identifying common problems. This differs from other information collection methods as customers are not forced to answer pre-determined issues. Customers are provided with an opportunity to share memorable incidents of the service they received. This model identifies the service's specific dimensions that impact the customer and can also be utilised to restructure the service delivery system around the customer's perceived quality attributes (Philpot et al., 2021).

2.4.4 Grönroos model

Figure 2.6 Gronroos Model (1984)

This model identifies three dimensions of service quality: technical, functional, and image quality. Technical quality is associated with the customer's interaction with a business. The customer regards as essential in evaluating the quality of service (Grönroos, 1984). The functional quality concerns how the customer gets the technical results, including communication, competence, staff, and others. And the last dimension, image, builds up through technical and functional quality perfection. The Grönroos model of service quality is an efficient tool of measurement that can be used to assess service quality (Khader and Madhavi, 2017).

2.4.5-Dimensional model

This is a service quality model in which the quality of service is formulated from the perceived quality and satisfaction. The dimension of this model includes the designed quality, product quality, delivery quality, and sound quality (Naomov, 2019).

2.4.6 SERVPERV model

This is a performance-only model and an alternative to the SERVQUAL model of Cronin and Taylor. It is an instrument that measures the experiences only, and it is not concerned with finding out about the customer expectations. And therefore, this model only utilises the perceptions segment of the SERVQUAL Scholefield(Aga, 2007). The model argues that the quality of service is better anticipated by the actual service the customer receives, and not the difference between what the customer perceives as quality and what they expect, as suggested by Parasuraman. The SERVPERF model measures the quality of service as an attitude and not as satisfying. However, the model agrees that perceived service quality leads to satisfaction but further connects satisfaction with further purchase indentation (Maslakci and Sesen, 2019).

2.5 Brand image building in the hospitality industry

Brand image is a dynamic mental picture of how people perceive a particular brand. Customers have a view about a brand, and a set of perceptions, thoughts, and beliefs held about a specific brand. Brand image can be defined as a unique bundle of affiliations existing in the minds of the targeted or as an aggregate of beliefs, ideas, and perspectives that people have about a brand, which develops over time. It is concerned with a company's character and indicates the customer's perception of a particular product. It is about positioning certain brands within the market (Namin, 2017). Besides providing a mental picture of a brand, brand image also transmits emotional value. It is associated with the assemblage of observations and contact by people outside. Brand image underlines the mission and vision of a business. It is concerned with putting measures in place that will positively reflect the customer's mind. Customers are attracted to a particular brand due to their efforts and their expectations(Gabbie and O'Neill, 1997). People turn to form associations about a brand based on subjective perceptions of the association bundle that they have, and thus an image is formed. There are three main elements of brand image, namely: a unique logo, responsible for framing the image of the company, a slogan, which briefly describes what the company is all about, as well as a brand identifier backing up the fundamental values (Li et al., 2021).

Branding image is concerned with customers buying a product from a particular brand and selling the idea behind that product. Three essential elements that build a brand are positivity, uniqueness, and the act of being instant. Brand images are fortified by the correct use of advertising, packaging, intensified publicity, and others. It ensures that the expression and development of the product's character are carried out incomparably, without imitating others (Lee et al., 2018). A brand's image comprises different associations within a customer's mind, attributes and benefits and attributes. The customer's functional and mental connections formulate the brand attribute. These can be either precise or abstract. Help make up the rationale behind the decision to buy, and they are segmented into three types; being, functional benefits, associated with the quality of the brand compared to others, emotional benefits, associated with how one feels about the purchase; and lastly, the rationale beliefs related to why one and the customer's general appraisal of the brand makes up the brand attributes (Kim et al., 2021).

Brand image is continuously crafted based on the product's quality, appeal, ease of use, popularity, functionality, and general value. An image of a brand forms up the content behind a brand, and it is comprised of the objective and mental feedback of a customer after the product purchase (Lewis and Mitchell, 1990). Being able to exceed the customer's expectations indicates a positive brand image. A positive brand image intensifies the goodwill and overall value of a business. Brands are usually perceived differently by different people, making it difficult to craft a suitable brand. Companies strive to build strong brand images as it doesn't only help in satisfying the company's motives but also increases traffic into the business, thus increasing profits. Brand image makes it easy to introduce new products into the same brand, boosts customer confidence and loyalty, and creates professional relationships between the customer and the brand (Joseph Sirgy, 2019).

2.5.1 Brand image building

This is the process of yielding awareness and promotion of the service concerned with the company through advertising campaigns, sponsorships, strategies, and tactics. It is raising brand equity through promotional methods and advertising. It's an essential element of a business as it's the visual voice of a business. Strategies of brand building not only spread the word about the existence of a company but also attract people into the business and provide

value for them in a manner that offers a level of experience for them (Martínez & Nishiyama, 2019). Companies spend a considerable amount of time, effort, and capital building a brand. They work on the appearance of a brand, the emotional value behind it, and the positioning of the brand. All of these directly impact the overall success of a brand. It is essential to maintain a generally good reputation as the brand is formed out of its interactions and experience. That is why people quickly develop a mental knowledge of a brand based on what they read or hear in the media (Mo et al., 2021).

There are three segments to brand building, and they are discussed as follows.

Brand product – this is associated with the physical appearance of a product. Brand building ensures that a good quality product is sold to the customer, making sure that the brand of the product is visible and the packaging is appealing, is of good quality, and indicates the warranty. These are crucial in brand image building (Namin, 2017).

Service brand – this is associated with non-tangible services. This is when a customer walks into a restaurant. Their experience is solely based on their reception in the restaurant, the quality of the meal being served, the arena, and their interaction with the employees. In this case, brand image building becomes dependent on the customer's level of satisfaction with the service they received (Oh and Kim, 2017).

A retail brand is concerned with combining the service and the product. This indicates the products that are purchased through a service. Thus, a business must offer the best possible service and good quality products (Nadiri and Tümer, 2009). In a case like this brand, image building relies mainly on the service rendered and purchased product. This is seen when a customer orders a takeaway from a restaurant or a fast-food outlet.

Brand image building is perpetual and without a definite way of engagement (Martinez and Nishiyama, 2019). Innovation, creativity, constant monitoring, correct value positioning, and providing a good customer experience are all required during brand image building. It varies throughout various sectors of the hospitality industry. Even though brand image building isn't static and formulated, there are essential steps that must be taken into consideration, and they are:

Brand description – the initial stage in brand image building includes a thorough and precise brand description. This involves describing a product or service through logos, product description, packaging, etc. This develops a brand's equity and lays a foundation for a customer's perception (Hardjono and San, 2017).

Brand positioning and differentiation – after a product or service has been developed, it is essential that it is fortified against the competition through unique value-adding and positioning it in a manner that will easily attract prospects. These are essential in positive brand image building (French, 2018).

Brand promotion – Businesses use the right kind of communication and efficient media channels to assist in creating awareness of the brand and attracting prospects. Media such as TV, radio, print advertising, social media, billboards, and online advertising can be used to put the word out. This is where businesses put much money as it is essential for indicating the effectiveness of the brand image (Hardjono and San, 2017).

Brand personalisation – customer interactions and connections to the brand are required, and adding a personal touch is of utmost importance. This can be achieved through innovation and customisation, which leaves a strong impression and perception about the brand in the customer's mind (French, 2018).

Brand evaluation – continuous evaluation, monitoring, and reviewing the service and products are essential in increasing the functionality, intensifying the strength and reliability of the brand, and keeping it relevant and well-maintained. It is also vital in maintaining a good reputation which will enhance customer loyalty and confidence (Kim et al., 2021).

In various sectors within this industry brand, image-building strategies are adopted accordingly, which is essential in developing and differentiating brand value and forming the correct impressions for the business. Branding image-building strategies and manner determines whether a brand is likely to grow, remain stagnant, or parish field (Ball, Simões Coelho and Machás, 2004). Therefore, it is essential to bring new insights and continuously try new and different strategies or activities to ensure improvement and identify strategies that do not work. Customers play a crucial role in building a brand, indicating that the process, practices, and procedures undertaken in brand image building should be undertaken

with the customer in mind. Time and consistency are required in crafting a strong, unique, and competitive brand. Thus brand image building is a constitutional part of the development of a business and comprises different strategies and tactics that change over time (Kasiri et al., 2017).

Running a business in the hospitality sector can be a big challenge due to the intensified level of competition and imitation. Thus very essential that a brand stands out from the masses. Due to technological innovation, the entire world becomes a target market which is very beneficial to this industry. For this industry to take advantage of this, business brands need to grab attention and take up space in the digital world (Bailey and Ball, 2006). Brand image building builds credibility, increasing the chances of people choosing a particular brand over the other. It is essential to create a brand identity during brand image building in this industry. A brand identity is a tangible identification and representation of the company's name and general appearance (Koc, 2020). It relates to brand image but varies from it because it is the intangible reflection of the outward personality, character, and authenticity. To build a strong brand identity, one needs to develop and follow strict brand guidelines. The brand guidelines vary depending on the business and should be followed by its marketing partners.

The brand guide covers topography, logo lockups, logo safe space and usage, colour palette within the hotel business. One must also create a unified web experience; with innovation and digitalisation, the online area grows (Hardjono and Sand, 2017). Contactless servicing is rapidly increasing, and validation is given according to online presence. In the hospitality industry, it is essential to have a website detailing a business and the experiences of the customer's experiences. Elements that can be used include landing pages, Ad creative, social media content, and OTAs. To create a strong brand identity, one needs to optimise their OTA (online travel agency) listings within the hotel business. And the elements essential here can include photography, nearby points of interest, amenities, FAQs, company descriptions, and room options. People associate themselves with credible brands and have a good reputation over those that don't (Qiu et al., 2020).

For example, building a strong brand image within the hotel sector can help achieve the following.

Open up new revenue channels – in today’s world, people hardly have time to or any interest in thinking about a particular brand. They are too busy engraved in their fast-paced lives and are only interested in brands that quickly grab their attention. Thus, very important to have appealing brands and guides prospects clearly and concisely. Brand image building creates a face for your company, a face that carries the potential of engaging the audience, making their experience delightful, and eventually earning their loyalty (Bravo, Fraj-Andrés and Salinas, 2007). A face that portrays all the authenticity, strength, and functionality of the business. And the hotel business needs that face that will carry its credibility—the more substantial the brand, the stronger the customer loyalty. Strong brands turn prospects and guests into ambassadors (Salem et al., 2019).

Draw in the power of emotions – giving prospects a real and substantial reason to feel strongly about a particular brand over the other and maintaining that state as well as exceeding that state turns prospects into life-long customers. Research has revealed that behind a purchase lies emotion and not logic in most cases (Jones and Comfort, 2020).

Builds trust – the company’s experiences extend beyond the premises of a hotel or any business and are part of continuous communications reading the business. A profound social media presence will be necessary for covering the bases(Hutchinson, Raman and Mantrala, 1994). The brand communications will have to remain consistent to ensure continuous engagement. The contacts also need to be personalised and caring to create a stronger bond between the customer and the brand. In the hospitality industry, enhancing brand loyalty can vary between securing customer approval and losing it, which indicates how crucial it is for a business to build brand strategies toward this end goal (Tan and Despotis, 2021).

Draw in the power of storytelling – people are interested in engaging stories and are designated for levels. Creating a brand story for a hotel with historical touch details the mission, values, dedication, and other essential elements of the business can lead to stronger customer engagement(Ladhari, 2008). Brand stories improve the brand’s understanding, receptivity, and trust. Compared to facts and statistics, stories create a mental picture that is insightful and engaging. An appropriately crafted brand story ensures that customers will

more likely form connections with the business, leading to a relationship (Hardjono and San, 2017).

Brand advocate creation – word of mouth is still compelling even today; people are like to try new restaurants, hotels, and visit places just because someone was talking about their experience there. People are now quick to visit review pages to check the service being served at a particular place. Companies should provide platforms for communications to take place. They also need to invest in a compelling and clear brand experience as it will enhance the impact the satisfied customer has, which will, in turn, earn the company positive reviews and deliver a great return on investment (Sánchez-Pérez et al., 2020).

When building a brand image, the company must remain consistent. The company will have to be clear with what it is about and what it represents and always live by it. The brand image needs to represent all that is associated with the business. The business needs to always strive for a better brand image by always going beyond. A brand also needs to be authentic; in this industry, competition is high, which often kills authenticity (Lee and Severt, 2017). A product or service is always one way or another similar to another. Being authentic helps differentiate a brand from the others; it makes it unique and provides a new and enticing experience. Businesses must be social when creating a brand image. Social media is an exciting platform that increases customer interactions and the brand's popularity. Another keystone in building a brand image is always to stay focused. This will help find a niche, define the brand, and find the best possible ways to cater to the customer. One needs to work hard in finding strategies to differentiate their brand (Mo et al., 2021).

2.6 Brand image improvement in the hospitality industry

In this ever-evolving and dynamic digital age, competition within the industry and the enhancement of technological inventions continue to diversify. Businesses continuously introduce new products and services (Lee and Cheng, 2018). This level of competition has come as an advantage to the customer. It awards them the freedom of choice between vast amounts of alternatives; thus, the selection of products and services becomes broader. The brand image then comes in to help the customer select which product or service works best for them as customers turn to consider a group of alternatives, then creates a mental

framework based on the relationship or prior interactions linked to the brands regarding the functionality of products and services associated with the brand (Ahmad et al., 2019). The collective synchronisation of a brand image, consideration of a brand over others, purchasing from the brand, and brand loyalty, directly and indirectly, impact brand image and awareness. Research has proved that the first role of brand image within the hospitality industry is anticipating customer satisfaction. Investing in proper brand image building can increase customer loyalty (Kamakura and Russell, 1993). Brand image is one tool that vastly improves the performance of a business. It is also an indirect tool that significantly impacts the modification of the customer's purchasing behaviour. It has been indicated that brand knowledge, brand advertising, and brand relationship have a considerable impact on customer retention (Li et al., 2021).

Brand awareness, as well as brand image, play a role in determining brand knowledge. Brand awareness is concerned with the willingness of a customer to purchase a product or request a service associated with a particular brand and to what extent a specific brand has left an impression in a customer's mind. Brand image and brand awareness are directly related. Without brand image, brand awareness can be moulded according to the customer, which influences the company's reputation. Brand experience has an indirect and direct impact on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction in brand personality associations (Kenyon et al., 2020). A couple of dimensions were constructed by Brakus responsible for checking the brand experience scale (affective, behavioural, and intellectual. Brand experiences are conceptualised as something subjective, and they are also largely dependent on the customer's integral responses.

These responses are components of the customer's feelings, sensations, and behaviour, which the customer has towards the brand as a result of its design and identity while also considering its packaging, environment, and communication (Wood, 2020). Brand experience has also been proven to be a more effective measure of customer satisfaction than brand personality. And this is because brand experience shows a more robust prediction of actual buying behaviour. Brand experience indicates the evaluation between the brand strategy and customer experience, whereas brand familiarity relies on customers' previous experience and knowledge of a brand (Uyasal et al., 2018).

Brand trust becomes a more significant experience of brand loyalty. Brand trust is crucial when achieving brand loyalty, and it leads to the creation of trade association which is valued enormously. Various methods are included in measuring brand loyalty. Brand loyalty can also be measured by measuring purchase intention and commendation. Brand equity has shown to have types of brand strength that are primarily focused on (Khader and Madhavi, 2017). Brand loyalty is one imperially captured through such actions as the proposal, partially, and customer intention of buying. And the second factor is the customer's willingness to pay a specific price for a particular product. Brand loyalty is prejudiced by the behaviour itself and the practical action of the entity. The prospect of the product prejudices customer retention. A positive relationship exists among quality commitments, trust, satisfaction, customer retention, and the future use of a product (Hole et al., 2018). It has also been stated that there is a concrete relation flanked by the worth of a product or service and customer retention. Customer satisfaction attracts a lot of loyal customers. And it is the judgment of the state of happiness and the level of satisfaction by the customer. There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Businesses have to optimise their focus on a comprehensive approach to relationship marketing, which entails customer satisfaction. This will result in the retention of existing customers and the development of a positive and powerful word of mouth (Dadwal, 2017). Research has shown that customer satisfaction plays a significant role in both customers and businesses in intensifying and maintaining long-lasting beneficial relationships. Furthermore, customer satisfaction results in ever-lasting profitable interactions with the brand. Customer satisfaction is also implicated in the extension of affirmative word of mouth marketing responsible for building good brand repute and gives considerable value to the brand (Chaturvedi, 2017). It has been studied that customer satisfaction and brand loyalty both have a relationship that is constructive with each other, and that the perception of a customer is dependent on the company's profitability as well as the company's share within the market, which is helpful in the ongoing improvements within the company. It has been indicated that customer loyalty can be intensified through customer satisfaction, company repute, and trust. Providing the customer with premium quality products and services helps them develop customer loyalty and increases the general reputation; it is also essential for achieving customer satisfaction. It is necessary to note that the level of satisfaction is different between customers as they both have varying needs (Altinay & Taheri, 2019). It is the internal feeling of every individual which may range from satisfaction to dissatisfaction, resulting from the

assessment of services rendered to an individual in context to the customer's predictions by a business.

The essential aspect of customer satisfaction is accepting the disconfirmation theory, divided into two segments (positive and negative disconfirmation). Positive disconfirmation is when the level of service or product is better than anticipated and negative disconfirmation is when the product or service rendered is lower than expected (Agwa et al., 2017).

Brand awareness, brand experience, brand loyalty, customer retention, and satisfaction, as discussed above, are all essential and are related in one way or another and are all considered during brand image improvement processes within hospitality. They all play a crucial role in brand image building and the improvement of the overall functioning of a business. Brand image is an essential element necessary for both well-established businesses and start-ups. This is the era of transformation where digitalisation is rapidly changing every aspect of life; thus, it is of utmost importance to consider innovation, technology, and the digital market when improving a company's brand image (Al-Ababneh, 2017).

In today's extensively competitive market, businesses within the hospitality industry face many challenges due to the intensely sophisticated demands of the customer. The difference in brand image is what makes certain companies remain on top. Many businesses utilise the internet as a sales and marketing tool to promote their services and products and communicate with customers. A customer's perception about a particular brand is not only crafted by the offline marketing platforms such as newsletters and magazines but by various online platforms as well, such as websites, third party websites, and social media (Facebook, Twitter, etc.) (Canhoto and Wei, 2021).

These online marketing tools used by the business within various sectors of the industry provide brand-related messages information regarding the company and assist in spreading the word and reinforcing the brand image and brand personalities (Hutchinson, Raman and Mantrala, 1994). This makes it essential to understand the importance of online presence, using the correct online marketing mediums, and managing and enhancing these tools to improve the company's brand image (Floracic, 2020). The previous experiences of a customer and market communication are essential elements that formulate the brand image in the offline context. A brand image represents a universal concept, whether online or offline.

This indicates that online and offline brand images are the same. Therefore, businesses should present the same brand identity in both online and offline contexts, and the customer's perception of the brand, whether online or offline, should be the same (Joseph Sirgy, 2019).

Strategies for the enhancement of an online brand image includes increasing the strength, favorability, and uniqueness of the website attributes, providing consistent messages and vision across the necessary channels, ensuring matching brand identity and brand image, being transparent, and continuing to improve and maintain the quality of services and products being served, developing good relationships with online travel agents as well as considering customer reviews as a voice and an opportunity to improve the products and services (Kasiri et al., 2017). The online brand should be able to connect with the target market. A brand image's implications in the hospitality space's online arena are essential as customers' perceptions are impacted by offline materials and online communications (Lai et al., 2018).

To thrive in the online space and remain sustainable, one must commit more time to purposeful social media marketing. Countless social media platforms award companies an opportunity to interact with potential customers continuously instantly (Li et al., 2021). And yet many businesses miss the chance of interacting with prospects because they are not in the online space or cannot use social media marketing effectively. Taking up space online is essential as the digital space continues to expand. When taking part in social media marketing, companies should define their target market, determine the end goals, identify their brand voice, and remain consistent. The other thing is to constantly update the website and be available for online interactions (Nazari et al., 2020).

Service quality is one of the essential role players in improving brand image. People are not only interested in affordable products and fast service, but they also put much value on the quality of the product and service being rendered (Kandampully and Suhartanto, 2000). Cooperating personnel who believe in the brand and respect it will do a great job communicating it and representing it. It is essential to pin the right people in place to represent the brand well and craft the best possible service (Salem et al., 2019). Excellent or exceptional service quality will build up the value of the brand. Once customers see value in a brand, they will be more likely to interact with it. The brand's value will communicate the functionality of the service being rendered. Good quality service and products lead to

customer satisfaction and retain customers. This shows that it is essential to invest in the quality of the service and products as they speak for the brand more than anything else. Following the right service quality improvement strategies will help improve the company's brand image (Qiu et al., 2020).

One other way of improving brand image within this industry is through investing in visual assets. This is associated with hiring a professional graphic designer to develop the ideal logo and brand media suite, which may include elements such as brand colour palette, acceptable fonts, letterhead, headers, and thumbnails formatted for social media (Shafiq et al., 2019). One also needs to focus on building brand values to improve brand image. All the people involved in the company are the company's brand ambassadors. They should all live and breathe the brand image not only for the owner of the company but also for its reputation. The company's brand image should always be represented positively. Employing the correct type of people and communicating the vision and mission of the company and the customer's expectations as related to their experience is of utmost importance (Tan and Despotis, 2021).

Investing in brand consistency is critical in brand image improvement. Brand guidelines are essential in attaining consistency. Lack of consistency results in the brand being overly misused and misinterpreted in the vast mediums that exist in today's world. Establishing the company's very own look across the marketing and social media platforms and remaining consistent with it ensures that the brand stands out, stays on top, and remains competitive in this overly competitive space (Wong and Yang, 2020). Consistency is crucial and has remained vital for ages in the business world. Providing brand extension experiences can be achieved by providing solutions differently. Brand image building differentiates between the offering of products and services within the marketplace. One needs to give a different experience to the customers within this industry. Combine essentials and non-essentials to offer the best possible experience for the customer. This can be associated with creating high-profile events which keep people engaged and talking (Zhang, 2017).

Personalisation and segmentation are also essential tools in improving a company's brand image. The one-size-fits-all concept does not work anymore. People are now interested in brands they can relate to, brands that consider the individual, and ones that feel like they have been crafted with the individual in mind. It is not advisable to be everything to everyone as this will only back the company. It is essential to know what the brand is all about (Nguyen et

al., 2018). Effective personalisation and segmentation are required for crafting the brand to the audience's characteristics. Search engine marketing (SEM) also plays a significant role in improving a brand image. The ease of locating a specific page on the internet provides the best experience. Many people go online to search for products and services. No one has the time to struggle with locating a specific site on the internet. They would instead opt for more user-friendly, which is how most companies lose potential customers. Investing time, effort, and resources in search engine marketing can improve the image of a brand (Lugosi & Jameson, 2017).

Buyer personas and journeys also have a role in brand image improvement. Having relevant information about buyer persona awards a company an opportunity to improve its brand image based on what it considers valuable and exciting to the customer. Analytics also play a significant role as inbound marketing is data-driven and awards one an opportunity to build a brand predictively by monitoring brand image metrics such as social media engagement website visits, email performance, search engine presence, inbound links, and many others. Monitoring a brand through analytics allows one to detect what works and doesn't. Investing in the correct type of technology improves the quality of the product and service being rendered; it also increases the accuracy, efficiency, and speed at which a service is being generated, which improves customer satisfaction and thus brand image (Zhang, 2017).

2.7 Service quality strategies to improve brand image

Since service quality has come out to indicate that it has a considerable positive impact on customer satisfaction, the improvement and maintenance of service quality have become primal essentiality for many. Increased customer loyalty will be realised if customers have a lot of positive comments to share about the quality of service, which then improves the overall performance of a business (Baker, 2017). And as a result, many researchers have worked hard to identify and explore service quality indices and how to enhance and improve service quality. There are many dimensions developed to measure service quality but improving and archiving high quality service is more important than measuring it. Several critical service quality factors can be used as a base for internal operations planning and modification, representing a quality gap. These factors include service attitude and behaviour, which indicates that the service's attitude and behaviour have a considerable effect on the quality of service (Assaker et al., 2020). This is very critical as the attitude and behaviour of the service provider towards a customer shapes the first impression of the customer. Many people often judge the quality of the service they will get primarily based on the first impression. They are making it very important that the service provider is always on their best behaviour to maintain the service quality. A positive attitude leads to high service quality (French, 2018).

The other critical factor is the customer's emotions and perceptions; this concerns being conscious of the customer's emotional delivery and giving an immediate response. If this is not done, the customer can disrupt the service to show dissatisfaction. Many customers can reveal their emotions, perceptions, expectations, and discontent during service delivery, which can make service delivery a lot easier as the provider is able to can then quickly fix their errors (Kadir and Jamaludin, 2019). Commitment is also a critical factor as service quality can be significantly improved and enhanced through a certain level of commitment. Commitment directly impacts customer satisfaction, which in turn impacts service quality evaluation. Commitment is a factor that cannot be put aside as it significantly impacts service quality.

Customer relationships should also be valued regarding service quality; service providers are always trying to understand the customer demands in this competitive industry and delivering what the customer demands are of significant concern (Koc, 2019). The order of the customer is based on their perceptions and behavior. Providers must strive to understand and analyse customer perceptions and behavior to render high-quality service. Furthermore, it is essential to develop strong relationships between the customer and the brand. When solid and close relations have been established, businesses can observe and measure the customer's behaviour and perceptions. Through these observations, customer demands can easily be obtained. When the customers feel that their needs are met, they can positively evaluate the service quality. This indicates that one must build strong relations with the customer (Kenyon et al., 2020).

Another critical service quality success factor is service innovation; this is realised when businesses manipulate and modify the existing service model by looking into the customer demands. The creation of service quality has the immediate ability to meet the customer demands, even in the case of varying demands. Customer is likely to evaluate service quality positively when they learn that a particular brand is innovative in meeting their needs. In turn, it will retain and maintain its relationship with the business (Lee and Cheng, 2018). It has been revealed that there is a relationship between service innovation and the quality of service and that service creation has an influential impact on service quality. Cultural and cross-cultural awareness is also an essential factor of service quality improvement. People vary significantly regarding customs, backgrounds, values, and cultural diversity, directly impacting their preferences. So for the service provider to continuously satisfy the customer's needs, they need to consider their cultural differences (Mo et al., 2021). Customers turn to evaluate the service quality positively when their demands are met based on their values and cultural backgrounds. And for this reason, cultural and cross-cultural awareness is of utmost importance and positively impacts service quality. The experience quality is a factor that is essential to in-service quality as well.

Customer experience is crucial in this overly competitive industry, and what makes it even more critical is the ever-increasing and diversified demands of the customer (Martínez & Nishiyama, 2019). Researchers have revealed that offering the customers some pre-experience can fulfil the customer's needs and improve customer loyalty. Customer experience develops personal impressions and creates memories for the customers, increasing

the value of a brand. A positive experience impacts the customer's anticipated values and can determine whether the customer will give a high service quality evaluation. Experience quality has a significant positive impact on service quality and promotes the fortification of the competitive ability of businesses (Oh and Kim, 2017).

Knowledge of the industry is also considered as the hospitality industry in the United Kingdom is vast and diversified. The knowledge factor is concerned with the immediate response of the service renderer when the customer is being served. During service delivery, customers usually have queries, questions, and uncertainties, and handling these professionally with a positive attitude leaves a good impression on the customer. And the immediate and effective response is thus essential in-service quality (Nazari et al., 2020). And being able to provide this kind of response is mainly dependent on having advanced knowledge of this industry and the necessary people skills. Thus, training is of utmost importance within this industry. The level of knowledge required affects the quality of service positively. A relationship between advanced industry knowledge and service quality exists and is essential. Internal operations management of the service provider is another factor to be considered. It has been determined that internal operations management is critical for businesses as it provides a connection between a business's internal operations and the external customer (Ahmad et al., 2019).

Through planning and internal operations practices, a service model is usually developed. And the development of an effective service model is dependent on positive planning and preparations. Therefore, accentuating internal operations management and often practice positively impacts the quality of service delivered. This indicates that when managers work on improving the efficiency of internal operations, the gross service quality improves.

Communication is a primal element of service delivery in the hospitality industry (Salem et al., 2019). The role of communication during the delivery of a service is essential for identifying customer demands. Communication provides a space whereby the service provider can detect the customer demand and respond accordingly. For service providers to communicate effectively, they need to be great listeners. To provide the best possible service, service providers need to listen to the customers to identify critical service demands that are supposed to be met (Tan et al., 2017). When the customers' needs are effectively met, they will ease giving a high service quality evaluation. The inability of the service provider to

listen to the customer can lead to many problems such as misunderstandings, conflict, and crucial points being missed, thus leading to poor customer satisfaction. Service switching, gender differences, and customer experience management are other critical success factors for service quality (Shen and Tang, 2018).

As service quality has a significant impact on the brand image, and it's an element of primal importance, it is essential to take its improvement as a detriment of brand image improvement as the crucial success factors for service quality have been discussed. It is necessary to note that to improve service quality, one needs to identify the causes behind the customer's dissatisfaction. The crafted quality shapes the customer expectations, which will then pave the avenue for customer satisfaction, impacting the brand image (Chaturvedi, 2017). This shows that crafting the expected quality and going beyond it significantly improves the brand image. Therefore, several service quality strategies have been considered to enhance brand image. Below are quality improvement strategies that can be utilised to improve brand image.

One of the earliest approaches necessary to advance service quality was culture-based improvement based on the total quality movement. One of the most significant determinants of the positive and negative perception of the customer is based on the quality roots from the interaction between the customer and the service provider. The service provider's ability to detect the customer's concerns, communicate effectively, realise the issues they might have, and respond accordingly is critical in this industry (Agwa et al., 2017). The importance of service employees and culture has been established in earlier studies. Service culture can be improved through individualisation, employee selection, training, and investing in technology. The resourcefulness of the personnel and senior management commitment can enhance service culture. Businesses need to scrutinise variables that lead to poor service culture and errors. It has been indicated that to increase self-efficacy and job satisfaction and increase customer perceptions of service quality, managers should reduce employees' roles in conflict and ambiguity (Baker, 2017).

Design-based improvement – enhancing service quality through design is another relevant approach. There are three components of design-based improvement, and they are, linking strategy to the customers. Delivering high-quality service starts with understanding the target market (Kasiri et al., 2017). This form of understanding is what will derive the concept of the

service. Therefore, knowing the customer needs and crafting the service should improve the brand image.

The other approach of design-based improvement is linking the design to the perception. The customer's perception based on service quality varies a lot. And for this reason, businesses should put measures in place to detect what lies behind the customer perceptions and increase the development of relationships and interactions they have with the customer. The last approach to this is the direct manipulation of satisfaction through providing an inviting customer experience by crafting valuable service (Dadwal, 2017).

Failure-based improvement – with insufficient meaningful data to cater to statistical process control, some have opted for failure prevention, analysis, and recovery as the final theme within service quality improvement. It has been identified that most failures are not failures as they have been crafted into the system. As a service quality tool, a service guarantee is best viewed as a medium of generated data regarding critical service failures (Koc, 2019). The guarantee focuses on what the customer regards as important, provides the customers with an incentive to provide relevant information about service failures, and provides an easy and understandable measure of these failures. The essence of service recovery is the identification of the service errors that occur, correcting these failures, and putting the customer at ease. This will help retain the customer, detect service failures quickly, and eradicate them with ease (Lai et al., 2018).

Variation-based improvement – the variation-based approach is limited only to the subset of variables considered meaningful to the quality of service rendered, the kind of variable that can be measured. Simplifying the working processing, providing a healthy working environment, effective communication, training, and communication can boost the quality of service (Ahmad et al., 2019).

2.7.1 Other strategies

Others strategies include the following.

Achieving zero-defects and error-free service can be archived through management that gets the best out of people, control that strives for perfection. The one that will provide the best working environment requires error-free service. This direction will continuously review and evaluate the service quality to check what needs to be eradicated or improved (Wood, 2020).

Opening more channels for customer feedback – will increase the level of communication with customers. This will provide various platforms where customers can engage with the business and share what they like and don't like about the service. The level of interaction will give the service provider room to improve the service as they'll have immediate information on what works and what needs to be left behind (Qiu et al., 2019).

Providing a rich learning environment for the team – the employees should be put in an environment that exposes them to continuous learning and self-improvement. This will ensure that the employees are motivated and continuously develop their skills, interpersonal skills, people skills, time management skills, and others (Kim et al., 2021).

Internal communications – effective internal communications put the employees in a space that will allow for better employee interactions and promote better understanding between colleagues regarding their responsibilities. It also helps them deal with difficulties and misunderstandings in a conducive manner. This also advances the level of cooperation and coordination, which will, in turn, ensure the delivery of improved service quality, thus improving brand image. Businesses must also have recent technologies and equipment to simulate an actual work arena and train workers to provide the best service (Koc, 2019).

Product testing – the hospitality industry is an industry that people are constantly pouring into; it offers various activities that people can partake in. Being responsible for someone can be a challenge as many harmful things can erupt. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to test the products and the food offered within sectors of this industry before human consumption. And test the functionality of all the facilities to ensure proper working order. Testing a product ensures its safety and its functionality. Product testing is essential for brand image.

The other is testing a product in the marketplace before launching it, as this can provide customer feedback, and one can then act accordingly. One other helpful thing to prevent issues is to craft a service blueprint that will identify all the required activities for the final delivery of a service (Lai et al., 2018).

The empowerment of employees to deal with issues – training employees to deal with problems erupting from service delivery can have a positive impact on the brand image, as the customer will see that the business knows what it's doing and that it invests in people that not only gets the job done but gets the job done efficiently. This will eventually add value to the brand and increase customer interaction and satisfaction (Kuhzady & Ghasemi, 2019).

Practice active listening with the customer – learn what the customer wants or expects. People want to be heard; they want their opinions considered, especially when things are not going their way. Listening to the customer during this kind of situation will show the customer that the service provider is willing to rectify any hindrance and provide them with the service they deserve. Listening isn't about waiting to share your opinion. It is about taking into consideration the customer's concerns and acting accordingly (Lee and Severt, 2017).

2.8 Measuring degrees of the effectiveness of different service quality strategies

The prime step in improving service quality is starting to measure the quality of service as it can be hard to improve and monitor what has not been measured. The second essential step is to look for gaps existing between the customer perceptions of what quality is and the service provider's desired level of performance and take necessary measures to close these gaps. The final step in improving service quality is using the existing information and finding new information to ascertain that service quality is kept at a maximum (Haming et al., 2017). Two essential elements need to be considered when providing service of high quality, and these are the customer's expectations and how the customer perceives the performance. The perceived performance is responsible for ensuring the customer's satisfaction.

The customer is satisfied only when the perceived performance exceeds their expectations; the customer will not be satisfied if the perceived performance fails to meet their expectations.

As previously discussed, these customer expectations and the resulting performance can be analysed along five dimensions: responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and reliability. These dimensions are part of the RATER model, derived from the SERVQUAL framework of service quality (Haming et al., 2017). This model, as previously discussed, was developed in 1977 by Berry, Parasuraman, and Zethaml; this framework was the complete attempt at formulating systems that would measure service quality. This framework initially uses ten elements of service quality: competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, security, access, communication, responsiveness, tangibles, and knowing the customer. Seven of these were later collapsed into assurance, empathy, and empathy leading to the dimensions found in the RATER model (Naomov, 2019).

These dimensions are not entirely independent as the quality of facilities, considered under tangibles, may impact the level of the customer's confidence, considered under assurance. These dimensions are of equal importance. Their priority level may rely on the kind of service being provided and the kind of customers, their needs and their expectations. This drives some issues in the SERVQUAL service quality measurement instrument (Njau et al., 2017). However, the dimensions provide an essential qualitative model for improving and analysing service quality. Service quality is vital for business within various sectors of this industry. This is because of the nature of competition within this industry and because of an enormous number of players in the global market. And apart from utilising quality management techniques and following service quality improvement strategies, businesses need to monitor the service quality continuously. This often helps the management ascertain that the customer receives the quality that the company promised. Service quality can be monitored through several methods, such as conducting customer surveys, which help determine whether the customers are happy with the service and have any issues they'd like to be rectified (Haming et al., 2017).

Companies can also monitor customer feedback; the information retrieved from surveys and questioners should not be taken lightly as this information can improve. This is where the management can find issues detected on the service; these issues can then be corrected and prevented from occurring again. The customers' suggestions are also to be considered as they are what crafts the quality of service. However, the service provider can only adapt those attainable and applicable suggestions. Another method of monitoring service quality is reviewing service blueprints and problem-tracking systems (Koc, 2019).

It constantly involves blueprints and detecting the kind of problems occurring; this may require changes in monitoring processes and problem tracking systems. A service blueprint includes representing the process of service delivery, whereby the representation is in the form of pictures and diagrams detailing the steps to be taken during service delivery. Service blueprint gives relevant information on the individual steps and activities involved in service delivery. This allows the management to test service effectiveness before it can be rendered (Ahmad et al., 2019). The first step to be taken is to determine the extent to which a service meets the customer's expectations is the definition of a standard against which the performance of a service can be compared. The setting of specific goals may lead to the purpose of this standard. A qualitative standard is put in place to measure what has been considered difficult to measure. These standards include company-defined service delivery standards, customer-defined standards, and benchmarking (Taherdoost and Hassan, 2020).

Service that prioritises quality must have a focal point on four critical areas of importance to archive the desired quality. These four areas include service encounters, service design, service productivity, and the service provider's corporate culture. With the lack of necessary creativity of service provision systems, the exchange of service on the market cannot be archived since its functioning ensures efficient service delivery. During service design decision-making, the main issue lies in choosing between the service personnel and the type of technology required for service specified service delivery (Vlachos, 2020). And this is dependent on whether the service provider is interested in archiving maximum efficiency. The major understating of service quality lies in understanding that service quality is connected to benchmarks if the concerned service can be standardised. Many disagreements on the true nature of service quality are mainly on the relationship between customer satisfaction and the quality of service, and many factors usually impact happiness. Quality standards were initially developed in production and manufacturing (Baker, 2017).

The first reason was to improve product and service quality and conformance. The functional areas impact the business performance and customer satisfaction levels, which is why performance quality implies all marketing areas. Quality systems reinforce performance, with the focus being placed on procedures and processes. Thus, specific, quantifiable standards (benchmarks) are developed to maintain quality standards (Wong and Yang, 2020).

Measuring the quality of service can be an essential primal step in improving service quality as quality is the key to arching customer satisfaction. Service improving strategies such as culture-based, design-based, variable-based, and failure-based improvement, among others, have been put in place to render the best possible service. Improving these qualities of service depends on continuous monitoring and measuring their effectiveness (Usual et al., 2018). Companies must open all the systems involved and go through diverse information to get accurate results from these measurements. Service quality is not formulated, and it is structured on many variables that can directly or indirectly impact the quality of service and products (Tan et al., 2017). One needs to investigate many aspects when measuring the effectiveness of service quality strategies; these include various instruments and models. Taking the necessary step to measure and monitor service quality continuously can help identify areas of improvement, which will help service providers deliver the best quality they can. The correct data will reveal which aspects and service delivery processes need to be focused on. One also discovers what they are doing well to keep doing more of it. It is essential to know which aspects of service delivery are responsible for customer satisfaction. And knowing how to measure service quality and detect areas needing improvement is crucial in retaining loyal customers (Namin, 2017).

2.8.1 SERVQUAL instrument of measurement

SERVQUAL is a multi-dimensional research tool designated to capture a customer's expectations and perception of service quality. This measurement model has five dimensions responsible for representing service quality practices. Measuring the effectiveness of various service quality with this instrument involves the development of surveys that ask customers to rate the quality of service they received compared to what they initially expected. And as previously stated, these five dimensions include reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness (Haming et al., 2017).

Post-service ratings are another measurement method; this method is more like the SERVQUAL systems as it is also concerned with asking the customer to rate the service they received. Asking the customer relevant questions about the service they receive and asking them to order it is the easiest way of understanding what the customers want and what one can do to deliver it. Once a customer has received their service, the company can email them

to rate their service (Koc, 2019). Companies also provide easy-to-use platforms where customers can easily place their service. Social media monitoring is also vital in detecting what works and doesn't regarding service quality. Due to the rise of social media in marketing and business development, this method has become very popular (Naumov, 2019). Many people use social media as a space to vent about issues they might have with service quality. Many platforms on the social media space, such as business pages and review pages, can share topics, opinions, and suggestions about the quality of service they receive. Therefore, social media becomes the perfect place where companies can immediately judge their service (Tan et al., 2017).

Companies can easily implement tools such as Google Alerts and Mention to monitor what is being said about their service. Follow-up surveys can also be used in this regard. Follow-up surveys allow one to ask the customers questions regarding the service. Follow-up surveys are more resourceful than one-time surveys and service ratings to capture valuable customer insights. Many companies stop at sending emails that do not help on their own. The follow-up surveys allow the company to take on responses and act accordingly. They are also a lot more effective as they offer customers more time and freedom to respond and share their opinions (Nazari et al., 2020).

An in-app survey is another credible technique used in measuring the quality-of-service delivery. Here the customer can answer questions when they are on the business website. Customer effort score (CES) is a metric propped in the Harvard Business Review article. It is argued that many companies focus on trying to delight the customer to exceed their expectations. In most cases, customers are quick to drag a company for bad service than applaud them for good quality service (Lee and Severt, 2017). The costs of going beyond customer expectations are high; they indicate that the payoffs are marginal. Authors argue that instead of delighting the customers, companies must strive to make it effortless for the customers to correct their issues. And this is what was found to have the most significant impact on the customer experience and what they propose measuring. The question that should be asked is how much effort it took to have your question answered or queries resolved instead of asking how satisfied the customer is regarding the service they received. This is often accompanied by politeness from the customer and failing to tell the truth. The lower the score, the better (Ahmad et al., 2019). The customer effort score revealed that 96%

of the customer having high effort scores were less likely to be loyal customers in the future compared to only 9% of customers with low effort scores (Baker, 2017).

Documentation analysis is another method that involves listening or reading written or recorded service records. It is essential to pay attention to low service delivery commentary to rectify all the errors in the system. It is also necessary to pay attention to the positive comment to indicate the existing systems that work efficiently during service delivery. Another measurement method is the objective service metrics comprised of stats that deliver the objective of quantitative analysis of the service. The metrics are not sufficient for measuring quality by themselves, but they play a significant role in revealing which areas of service delivery need attention (Nguyen et al., 2018). These metrics include volume per channel, which is responsible for tracking the number of inquiries per channel; together with channels that cover efficiency and customer satisfaction; it allows one to decide which track to promote or leave behind. The other metric is the first response time, which tracks the customer's period to respond to their inquiry. This does not ensure that the problem has been solved, but it shows that the first step has been taken. The response time metric concerns the total time between responses (Lugosi & Jameson, 2017). People reaching out through emails expect a response within 24 hours. Those reaching out via social media expect a response within at least 60 minutes. Those who prefer to settle things via a phone call expect an immediate response. The other metric is the first contact resolution ratio; this is a result of dividing the number of issues that have been resolved through a single reaction by the number of those that required several answers. Replies per ticket is a metric that indicates how many replies to the service team needs to close a ticket.

Another metric is the backlog inflow/outflow, which shows the number of issues solved and the number of pending cases. Other metrics include the customer ratio success, handover per issue, instant service/queuing ratio, average queuing waiting time, and others (Priporas et al., 2017).

2.8.2 Customer retention rate

This is another measurement method calculated by subtracting the number of new customers from the total at the end of a specific period, then dividing that by the number of customers

retained by the total number of customers available at the beginning of a period. Figures close to 1 indicate high customer retention (Chivandi et al., 2019).

Customer satisfaction score (CSAT)

This is responsible for measuring the customer's feelings immediately after service; as with other methods, one can send a survey to the customer to get answers. Net promoter score (NPS) is the measure of the effectiveness of the quality of service; this gathers customer feedback through surveys. Like with customer satisfaction score as well as customer effort score, a business can collect customer feedback with several types of survey questions such as, "how likely are you to recommend our brand to another person" "high positive responses indicate that the customer was satisfied with the kind of service they received (Agwa et al., 2017).

2.8.3 Customer loyalty

The number of loyal customers is also a measure of service quality. High-quality service served professionally is what will retain the customer. The continuous supply of high-quality service and the adapting change in customer perception will lead to an increased number of loyal customers (Altinay and Taheri, 2019).

2.9 Summary and conceptual framework

Several service quality models were discussed in the previous section, including SERVQUAL, Critical incident, Grönroos, and Dimensional models. The five gap model has proven to be the most efficient as it assists the hotels in identifying and shedding light on the gaps in the services. Since the main concern is entirely subjective customer satisfaction, this model creates the relationship between the expectations and perceived benefits. The framework for such a model compares the customers' expectations and the perceived quality. The core is to understand the values and dimensions of the service to fulfil all the customers'

needs. There are five dimensions for SERVQUAL: reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness. Together they form the service quality for the customers.

Figure 2.7 Conceptual Framework

In conclusion to this chapter, the hospitality industry in the UK has been addressed with the demonstration of the hospitality industry history highlighting the organisational structure, hospitality market, trends, and investment. Hospitality is the third-largest industry in terms of employment creation, as it encompasses a variety of business sectors, including fast-food restaurants. It was critical to describe the level of pressure that the hospitality industry faces, as it is constantly striving to improve its customer service. The consumer is the foundation of this industry's success, and customer happiness is the industry's goal. The conventional system, referred to as the interaction between individuals and the company's various components, is the organisational structure. Long organisational structures, such as those found in hotels, are associated with large organisations with multiple levels of employees and managers for workers.

In contrast, flat organisational structures are associated with small organisations that do not have various employees. This chapter also focused on Theories about the importance of service quality in the hospitality industry. The theories of service quality's significance in the hospitality industry include the unified service theory and service quality plus the behavioural theory. It led to discuss the classical approach. The management science and contingency approach were also included with the systems management and the prospect theory and

service quality theory to lead to the balance theory and, finally, the SERVQUAL theory. In addition, the chapter addressed different modules and frameworks about service quality like the perceived service quality, SERVQUAL, Critical incident model and talked about the Grönroos model, then explained the Dimensional model

2.10 Conclusion

The hospitality industry in the United Kingdom is diverse and has become dynamic concerning investment. This industry has created many jobs for many and has contributed massively to the GDP. This industry comprises many segments such as accommodation, food, and drinks, event planning, theme parks, lodging, leisure, gaming, and travel and tourism. The industry has been very active in its overall growth and development over the years, and it is the industry that suffered significant losses due to the Corona Virus pandemic. Hospitality thrives on customer involvement and satisfaction. This industry is a type that is enormously competitive and affected by quite a lot of various variables. Covid-19 is not the only one that has proved to have a detrimental impact on the industry in the United Kingdom; Brexit also had its fair share of impacting this industry negatively. For businesses within various sectors of this industry to thrive, a lot of essential elements need to be looked at, and this is why multiple discussions of this paper were based on service quality and its importance, model and frameworks involved in service quality, brand image building and improvement within the industry, service quality strategies engaged in advance of brand image as well as the measuring degrees of the effectiveness of various service quality strategies.

The hospitality industry is very dependent on its employees as they are mostly the face of the business. And the customers of this industry are continually interacting with the employees. And this is why it is essential to have employees who are well-informed and competent on service delivery and also need to be friendly. They portray a positive attitude in dealing with the customer. People skills are essential in this industry, and a healthy working environment that allows easy interactions, communication, self-improvement, and motivation must be continuously provided. For many businesses to thrive, employees must have access to

sufficient facilities that will provide the best possible service and must be mentally equipped enough to handle customer issues. Service quality is perceived differently by different people in this industry, which essentially impacts it.

Brand image is associated with the culture and essence of the business; it is what attracts the customers and makes a company stand out. Brand image heavily depends on service quality, which makes customers keep coming back. The relationship between brand image and company performance has been studied extensively. However, many of these studies were conducted outside the hospitality industry, as many were born in the manufacturing, financial, and other industries. This indicates that there is still a need to explore the relationship between brand image and business performance within this industry. Even though it has been proven through limited research that a positive impact between brand image and the performance of a business in the hotel industry exists, researchers still fail to agree with one another regarding the brand image dimensions and the performance measurement. However, these are just minor disagreements. More studies should be performed and research conducted within the hotel industry to further explore the relationship between brand image and business performance. Studies have indicated that customers indeed impact the inputs and quality control methods adopted effects on perceived service quality within the hospitality industry. It has also been concluded that the quality of a customer plays a significant role in influencing perceived service quality. A better way of assuring the improved quality of service is through a preventative approach to the quality of problems.

Service quality management has given an advanced understanding of various dimensions of service quality. Service quality management has also come out to shine some light on tools and strategies used in this industry to enhance customer satisfaction. These tools and techniques reduce mediocrity and its impact on its reputation within this industry. Research has also indicated that careful consideration of service quality management techniques and efficient quality-orientated service procedures increases customer satisfaction. An efficient quality management system is a simple tool for any business interested in being competitive and reaching the highest heights of customer satisfaction. Service quality is an aspect that is independent and sustainable within various definitions and applications. The importance of improving service quality has been discussed and the implicated strategies. Multiple levels of service quality can be applied and enhanced by using various service quality enhancement

techniques. All these processes can pose additional costs on the overall input costs, but this can be considered an investment element as it can result in future savings and earnings.

3. Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This research is based upon the descriptive analysis and sampling of primary data collected through empirical studies and quantitative findings, which is then supported by the secondary data through the scientific literature and other researchers' data and results and conclusions. The data collected as the empirical studies and primary data has been going on in the market. The way market has been trending and moving since 2008. The Pandemic restrictions and lockdown have severely hit the hospitality sector and the hotel market of the United Kingdom following Brexit, which has further impacted the whole industry of the country. The already limping sector because of the Pandemic was broken into pieces with the Brexit.

The descriptive sampling also helped determine the right metric, which can go for the current evaluation of the service quality system. It has also been found that it is not the sure-shot method yet is precise for the current system. Going further, it will need up-gradation. With the observation method, by observing the market and case studies of various hotel chains of the United Kingdom, the measures the hospitality industry should take and implement in the service quality strategy to improve their brand image were outlined. The questionnaire and survey method helped determine the customer's expectations viz. a viz—the hotels' offering. The vast gap between the two was shown, which helps evaluate the hotel industry's issues regarding service quality and what strategy they need to pivot to improve themselves in front of the customers and make them loyal towards their brand. Details of the research methodology followed in this case are presented here.

3.1 Research Philosophy

The researcher uses this systematic method of thought concerning the entire paper. It helps inform the research framework from the beginning after choosing a topic and a research object, service quality strategies that can improve brand image in the United Kingdom. The research philosophy guides the methods used for research and influences the type of data collected (Nayak and Singh, 2021). It is vital in the proper formulation of a research paper. Research papers are used to advance knowledge and better policy formation by the relevant parties or industries. Thus, the researcher needs to choose the most appropriate research philosophy for the sake of the comprehensiveness of their paper (Wilson, 2014).

The philosophy to be used in this research study is the positivist approach. The positivist approach suggests that social sciences can examine the world objectively. This means that the researcher is objective in their analysis and does not use bias in their work. Taking this scientific approach will allow the researcher to come up with solutions that are just as objective and can be applied in other cases, ones that may be different, but the rule may still apply. With correct data analysis, they provide other people with tools that can be used to make informed decisions for the betterment of their companies and other business entities.

Data collection is influenced by the research philosophy chosen. In this case, the research paper is quantitative, and positivism and post-positivism align with that. The quantitative data collection will allow the service strategies to be the most effective in creating a better brand image. This includes using as much information as is appropriate for the sake of having the best practice (Abutabenjeh & Jaradat, 2018). When relating variables related to the best practices, one needs to make objective links that are not dependent on a specific manager or one person's views. Using qualitative data, in this case, means that there will be diversity in data collection since the data collected will be within stipulated parameters. The results that come from the analysis will be logical and will withstand the test of time in line with the current trends.

Additionally, there are many more inferences due to the research paradigm used. The research philosophy will affect the paper's methodology, epistemology, and ontology (Nayak

and Singh, 2021). The process will be discussed further in the paper; the main focus is on using the positivist research philosophy to guide the rest of the article.

As has been previously mentioned, reality in the positivist approach is objective. One's values and morals are not considered when research is conducted, nor are the researcher's worldviews used. For example, in creating a better brand image, the researcher thought it suitable to use the positivist approach (Wilson, 2014). This is because having a good brand image is entirely objective. If people generally have a good impression of one's brand, it will be visible in the critical performance metrics that the company checks. Checking one's reviews online, especially in the hospitality industry, is crucial. Knowing what one's customers think means that the business will identify their weak spots and correct them for their current and future customers.

An example of things that are objective is good customer service. The customer will appreciate good manners from staff, and help offered on a constant will make them feel valued. This goes for most clients as they feel like the company is not just in the business for profit but also delivers their services with a human touch. Giving such customers a survey will show where they were given the best care and attention and what areas may be shaky. While human responses to the same stimuli or event may not always be the same, most people confirm that a good product or service is a surefire way for business owners to know that they are on the right track.

This method states that reality is objective regarding ontology, the truth about reality. This is where assumptions come in handy. Without certain assumptions, science and, by extension, research would not progress. There is much speculation in this situation even before the study begins (Nayak and Singh, 2021). Some of them are implicit, such as the company in question knowing the value of a good brand image. Good brand imaging is what every company aims to attain, which is another assumption. Without these two assumptions, the reason for working on getting better imaging would not exist. The assumptions made make it much easier to have a firm basis for conducting research.

Additionally, there are several reasons for assumptions to be made. Some of them are based on previous research, which emphasises the importance of building the knowledge base for future researchers. Through the work of researchers that have come before, researchers can

conclude models that have been provided back and thus use the assumptions from those times to better the industry. It is natural to assume people want good things, but it is the researcher's work to determine what good things are enjoyed by most people who need a particular service. Standing out from other goods and service providers when the bare minimum is established becomes much more attainable. The foundations are fine-tuned, and thus the rest of the exploratory approaches can be researched. Through this gradual process, things that used to be fresh and new become part of the usual, and the cycle begins again. But this would not be possible without research and development of new strategies.

The use of the positivist approach over interpretivism, for example, is quite clear. The interpretive approach deigns that the world is more about perception than objectivity (Nayak and Singh, 2021). In the hospitality industry, especially when it comes to service delivery, it is imperative to get it right. Some of the bad experiences that a customer may have had will ensure that they will never bring business to a particular place again, but they will also influence their friends and family. With the advent of social media, one viral piece can make or break a business. In this manner, having a research method that centres on the data provided and the researcher's views are not considered is a much better option than one where the parameters of good service delivery are debatable.

In addition to that, the data collection methods used in an interpretive approach are more synonymous with qualitative data. The use of interviews, for example, is not very suitable for understanding efficient service delivery and creating a plan of action from it. This is because interviews can be more biased than questionnaires. The researcher can ask leading questions, and the volume of data collected here is insufficient for use in the quantitative data analysis (Creswell, 2003). Additionally, interviews are a lot more involving. This time can be spent in a more constructive way for the researcher, in distributing questionnaires to relevant parties, and in later stages, in data analysis and writing up the final discussion resulting from the study mentioned above.

The aim of positivism, otherwise known as the scientific method, is to explain phenomena or show links between certain things (Wilson, 2014). The connection between a better brand image and efficient service delivery techniques is one that this paper aims to find out. Understanding the cause and effects of certain events or phenomena is essential in understanding where adjustments are made. Using this approach, a step-by-step procedure

that establishes the differences between what can be termed excellent and lousy service and what causes each is made a lot clearer. This means that change-makers in a company can focus their efforts in the right places to get the change that they are looking forward to in their departments or the company in general.

Knowledge is gained through data in this method. There are many ways that learning can be achieved, but within this approach, knowledge acquisition is mainly through data collection. This takes out biases that the researcher may have or any views that may change the solutions offered. Through analysis of data, decisions made from this study will be the best practice ideally.

3.2 Research approach

A research approach is a system by which one decides to do their research. The necessity for such is born out of the need to mesh theory and reality to obtain actionable results and data (Abutabenjeh & Jaradat, 2018). Different research approaches are taken from differing perspectives on the complementary nature of theory and reality and how they affect each other. The available options for research are three; deductive, inductive, and abdicative. The research approach to utilise is usually based on the research hypothesis in question.

A hypothesis is the researcher's assumption concerning a specific event or phenomenon. This assumption is usually educated and is drawn from relevant research, and seeks to answer a question that has not been answered by research they have found online. Thus, they need to find the validity of their claim whether their claim is correct or incorrect (Nayak and Singh, 2021).

An inductive research approach requires the researcher to collect data relevant to their hypothesis; once the data collected is judged adequate, the researcher then retracts and endeavours to identify links and patterns from the accumulated data. This tends to have the researcher begin with observations made from said patterns and then link the data back to the hypothesis. This can be considered moving from data back to theory (Ragab and Arisha, 2018).

On the other hand, a deductive approach can be considered a reversal of the steps followed in the actualisation of an inductive approach. A researcher employing a reasoned approach will read through the current theories about their interest and then build hypotheses arising from those established pieces of view (Ragab and Arisha, 2018).

The abductive approach to research balances the methods employed in inductive and deductive studies to eliminate the weaknesses associated with the two (Nayak and Singh, 2021). The researcher identifies puzzles in data patterns that existing theories cannot explain through this approach. The researcher thus endeavours to choose the most fitting explanation and then compares both empirical and reasoning to search for a duly satisfying answer.

Considering the research philosophy used in this paper, it thus logically follows that the method used is deductive. The positivist philosophy dictates that the worldview used is objective. The aim of positivism, otherwise known as the scientific method, is to explain phenomena or show links between certain things. The link between a better brand image and efficient service delivery techniques. This means that data is collected and observed without researcher bias. Assumptions can be made from previous studies and can be proven or disproven. The approach that does this is the deductive approach.

Considering that the critical data garnered by the research is quantitative and the nature of the research objective itself. The deductive approach is considered most suitable as it allows for a broad scope of data accumulation and analysis. This is key as, to determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in improving brand image, numerous existing methods must be analysed to achieve such brand superiority and various attempts and failures to do so.

Considering the necessity to maintain congruence between the research philosophy, research approach, and methodological choice. The deductive approach is the most effective tool to parse the data accrued through the data collection methodologies chosen as the data itself is more empirical. Pattern and cycle identification features of the inductive approach increase the ease of research.

3.3 Methodological choice

The choice of methodology to be employed is predicated mainly on the data to be accumulated. Qualitative data is often not born of cognitive deductive reasoning and presents itself in words, images, or descriptions. Quantitative data, on the other hand, tends to present itself in the form of either figures or graphical representations.

Qualitative data's advantages lie in that it is usually richer in detail and specifics, with most findings grounded in a subjective perspective that is generally very in-depth (Ragab and Arisha, 2018). It has its limitations. However, it usually involves a small number of participants, and the sample results cannot be generalised to the rest of the macro population. Using qualitative data, in this case, means that there will be diversity in data collection since the data collected will be within stipulated parameters. The results from the analysis will be logical and will withstand the test of time.

Quantitative data is preferred because of the ease of collection and analysis of data. The nature of the data itself is such that the analysis methods employed are largely statistical analysis and comparisons of figures. This gives it a certain visual clarity and clear causal connections between the figures themselves and the studied actions. Technological means have it such that qualitative data analysis can be done with relative ease, allowing the research process to take far less time than it would otherwise (BRYMAN, 2003). To identify a metric to measure the effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK, a large amount of data must be accumulated.

With hotels having different views on the aspects to emphasise the most concerning quality, all must be collected to ensure the exhaustiveness of the research results and hence their relevance. To ensure that there will be diversity in data collection, data collected must be within stipulated parameters. The results that come from the analysis will be logical and will withstand the test of time in line with the current trends.

After all, the research is being carried out to optimise service provision in the hospitality industry. This heavily emphasises the necessity for the actionable potential for the results garnered from the research. Qualitative research methods usually entail a small sample size

which would not allow for the generalisation of the data accumulated, a major stumbling block in the implementation process.

With all the considerations mentioned above in mind, the most suitable research methodology to collect data should be the quantitative method. The relatively short data collection and analysis period allow quickly implementing findings, which is crucial in an industry heavily affected by trends and widespread opinion shifts.

The actionable potential data accumulated through this method takes out biases that the researcher may have or any views that may change the solutions offered. Through analysis of data, decisions that are made from this study are going to ideally be the best in terms of clarity as well as providing much need longevity to strategies born of the data exemplifying the research framework all through from the beginning after choosing a topic and a research object, which in this case is service quality strategies that can improve brand image in the United Kingdom.

3.4 Research strategy

For a research project to be effectively actualised, a suitable research strategy must be employed to support the birth of reasonable and logical hypotheses from empirical data and logical arguments. The choice of research strategy depends very heavily on the type of data accumulated, whether qualitative or quantitative (Bairagi and Munot, 2019).

The most employed descriptive research strategies are observational, survey, and case study methods. All the procedures allow for an effective, targeted strategy for accumulating data and its representation in a transparent manner.

Observational methods employ choosing a field where the researcher can observe the research object in their natural environment. The most significant advantage of such a method is its high ecological validity. However, this method would require immersion of the researcher in new environments without disrupting the order of the field of observation which is not easy to do. It is also very time-consuming, and there is a danger of data misinterpretation as this method carries heavy researcher bias.

The case study method entails garnering qualitative data from an individual group. This method is not ideal for use to base results on a larger population than the sample population due to the existence, which may not fit into the norm of the society being used as reference. The researcher's biases also add to the poor validity of generalised from such a sample size.

The survey method usually entails the administration of questionnaires or interviews. The researcher samples data from individual units of a population to be used as aids for the formulation of hypotheses about the population to which the sample members belong. Data garnered from such a method is generally devoid of researcher bias and is easily analysed into empirical representations through technological means.

With the research objectives in mind, the use of the survey method is arguably the aptest. This is since it allows the collection of data that can be used to generalise the situation of the whole population in consideration as it contains little to no researcher bias. Speed is also optimised in the employment of the survey method as collection and analysis can be done through computer software.

The method employed by the researcher here is the administration of online questionnaires. This was in consideration of the fact that interviews are a lot more involving, and this time can be spent in a more constructive way for the researcher, in distributing questionnaires to relevant parties, and in later stages, in data analysis and writing up the final discussion resulting from the analysis. Thus, allowing for gathering the views of various sample sets on the methods different hotels employ to improve and maintain the brand image in terms of service quality. The key determinants of such, from the partakers of the hotels' services, could also be gathered through targeted questions in the questionnaire.

An analysis of the answers from the clients of the UK establishments considered top-notch by those sampled will provide much headway into identifying the mental metric used by the populace to measure superiority of service quality and the attractiveness of a brand to a consumer.

3.5 Time horizon

Time horizons usually refer to periods to be studied and during which data collection is undertaken. Cross-sectional studies are situations where data is gathered once over a variable period to affirm or disprove the hypothesis (Bairagi and Munot, 2019).

In Longitudinal studies, data is gathered at different points in time. In some situations, the researcher may want to capture data before, during, and after a phenomenon to capture the changes and the cycles and patterns contained therein concerning the research question and objectives.

For ease of data navigation, a researcher can use research time frames with appropriate parameters to study the data. The start and end of the structures are determined depending on the subjects being studied and their number. The phases involved in the research project could be years or days.

For this research, a cross-section study system was used. Data were only collected once as time was not relevant to the study's objective. The main aim was to make objective links that are not dependent on a specific manager or one person's views and use qualitative data to derive the unique points of the systems employed by the different establishments.

As the data collection tools employed were questionnaires, an analysis of the answers from the clients allowed for the gathering of the views of various sample sets with the whole population in consideration as it contains little to no researcher bias.

The actionable potential data is easily analysed into empirical representations through technological means. This allows for findings to be implemented quickly, which is crucial in an industry such as the hospitality industry. Also considered is diversity in data collection, and since the data collected is going to be within stipulated parameters of time and hotel.

3.6 Sampling

As per Nayak and Singh (2021), sampling identifies a smaller representative group from a particular population under study. In this case, the sample identified is customers of the hospitality industry from the UK. Sampling was carried out randomly within this identified

group. In random sampling, everyone in the selected population has equal chances of being a part of the sample. In this case, as many as a possible number of customers from the hospitality industry in the UK were reached. An online questionnaire was shared with them. Although the questionnaire was sent out to a much more significant number, 300 completed responses were received through this random sample. The most important advantage of the sampling technique is that it helps reach reliable evidence with a smaller number of participants or respondents.

3.7 Data collection and analysis

The data collection method chosen by the researcher was through online collection consisted of a series of targeted questions and prompts to ensure that the clients of the UK hotels who were sampled provided adequate and detailed information in line with the research objectives. Data collection is influenced by the research philosophy chosen. In this case, the research paper is quantitative.

The aspects in consideration when drafting the questionnaire itself were the study's objectives and the design to ensure interactive effectiveness with the respondents in the sample. The questionnaire was then pilot tested within a limited target demographic of one hotel before full-on administration of the questionnaire. The entire administration was wholly online.

On the front of Data analysis, the methods employed were simple statistical analysis. Simple statistical analysis is a system of statistical methods for estimating the relationships between a dependent variable and more independent variables in descriptive form. The primary use of this analysis is to create rudimentary models of prediction and forecasting and relies on the causal connections between variables.

In practice, the researcher should select a model to estimate the stipulations of a predictive model; they can then employ their chosen method to estimate the positions of the variables and the functions that most fit the data. This analysis method allows the researcher to determine the most factors and the dross, which can be disregarded (Creswell, 2003). The nature of this research being undertaken provides for full use of simple statistical analysis to find trends in the patterns of hotel goers and their attachments to said hotels. This is

incredibly important in quantifying the attractiveness of certain brands presented by the hotels, a significant movement in achieving the research objective of identifying a metric to measure the degree of effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels.

Simple statistical analysis methods were also employed as an auxiliary tool to increase the clarity and specificity of the data collected. This enabled the initial sifting through large magnitudes of the data accrued and a more straightforward interpretation of the implications brought by the data. The simple statistical analysis adds valuable insights into the decision-making process of the sample and generalised populaces.

In employing the above statistical analysis methods, the researcher avoided pitfalls associated with the fundamental problems of over-complicated analysis systems. The methodology, epistemology and ontology of the paper as affected by the research philosophy called for a high degree of congruence at all levels of the research, achievable only through the simplification of analysis tools employed, which is critical in the proper formulation of proper analysis.

3.8 Reliability and validity of the research

As per Wilson (2014), the reliability of research is related to the degree of stability and consistency in the methods used to find answers to the research questions. The reliability of a study can be judged by reproducing the same. If the study has a high degree of reliability, it will produce similar results with accuracy if it is born. In this case, reliability was ensured by comparing the results from primary data with those obtained from the theoretical underpinnings identified in the previous literature study. The validity of the development is related to the accuracy with which the variables are being studied. The research can be considered valid if the results correspond to actual characteristics or elements. In this case, comparing the findings from the literature review and quantitative data shows that the investigation is valid.

According to Creswell (2003), the validity of research is defined as how accurate the data representation is within the study. The more the information is tangible, the more credible it would be. This research ensured validity by collecting data through an online questionnaire.

This provided accurate data for further review. Also, due to the social distancing requirement, the researcher was not present when the respondents filled out forms. This ensured that no bias from the researcher's approach was added to this research. The questions were framed objectively. They were not leading. Bryman (2003) and (2008) argued that each study could adopt a different approach. To ensure the reliability of the data, any secondary data used was taken from reliable sources. The point of view presented by the authors were read more than once to get a deep understanding of the concept before the author represented it. This information was duly referenced.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

While any research is conducted, various factors are considered very important. Although reliability and validity of study are the pillars on which the strength of research relies, ethical considerations are equally crucial for the successful completion of the study. "Ethics is the use of ethical principles to evaluate, conduct and report the results of research" (BRYMAN, 2003). Every research must follow ethical considerations; the most critical aspect of the moral concern is that the information used in the research should be obtained with due permissions and protocol. Researchers must consider multiple factors, such as privacy, honesty, and plagiarism when collecting data (WILSON, 2010).

Any secondary data that has been used in this research is obtained from the public domain. Researchers used and referred in this research are publicly available. Also, the primary data was collected after informing the participants in detail about the nature of the project. The participants took part in this research through their own free will. None of them was forced to be a part of this research. During this research, it was ensured that ethical requirements were followed thoroughly. When the participants for this research were approached, complete details of the research project were shared with them. The researchers were informed that their input in this research would be anonymous. Also, the data will be kept safe, and the researcher will be the only person with direct access to the data. The data is saved on a USB drive, with only the researcher having access to raw data. The raw data will be deleted two years after the publication of this research. Everything conducted in this research according to the ethics regulations of UWS.

3.11 Summary

This research has been carried out following the positivist approach. This philosophy has been used to ensure that the research question can be answered objectively. This means that the researcher is objective in their analysis and does not use bias in their work. It is an essential aspect of any research. A researcher's bias can negatively affect the reliability and validity of the research. In this case, the research is done by following a positivist approach to ensure that the findings are presented objectively. The philosophical underpinnings provide an accurate overview of this research. It has been confirmed that the findings do not reflect the researcher's point of view. The methodology is chosen to keep this point in sight. The focus of this research was to ensure that quantitative data is collected without any researcher's bias involved in the whole process. This is what was provided by following the positivist approach. The approach to this research is deductive.

As discussed in the chapter, analysis can be inductive or deductive, or a mixture of these approaches. In deductive research, the findings are deduced from the data. In this case, the findings have been compared with the objectives to see if the research has achieved its goals. It is quantitative research in which data has been collected through a random sample of 300 participants who have filled out the online questionnaire. One factor that played its role in finalising the methodology of this research is the social distancing requirements due to covid-19.

Due to the social distancing requirements, the researcher couldn't meet the participants personally. All contacts were initiated online. The questionnaire was shared digitally, and the participants were requested to fill out the questionnaire and submit it. It proved to be a significant limitation of this project because this acted as a hurdle for the researcher. The sampling carried out was random sampling among the group of people who have worked in the hospitality industry in the UK in any capacity. It was essential to target only the hospitality industry because this survey required some internal industry knowledge. Without having that knowledge, it would not have been possible for the respondents to fill out the complete questionnaire. However, within this population sample, sampling was carried out randomly. It means that anyone who has worked in the hospitality industry of the UK has an equal chance to be a part of this survey. The research strategy is based on the online questionnaire survey. Data collection was carried out through an online questionnaire. A literature review was conducted thoroughly to provide theoretical underpinnings for this

research. It was born as a cross-sectional study. Being a cross-sectional study, data for this research was collected only once.

4. Chapter 4: Data presentation and Findings

For this research, an online questionnaire was filled out by 300 participants. The questionnaire is presented in the appendix. The results from this survey are shown below.

Demographics:

There were 300 filled questionnaires received from the respondents. The age group of the respondents are shown in the graph below.

Figure 4.1 Age groups of the respondents

The next question dealt with the **work experience** of the participants. Many people were working, although their occupations differed. Some worked in professions with a high level of education, such as accountants, lawyers and doctors. There were also quite a few business owners. A few people did not work but had passive income in property, business, and other income. However, most of the participants who worked had more than 2/3 years of work experience in their relative fields. Many had more than five years of work experience. While there were a few common industries where most people worked, there were also people who worked in entirely different industries.

The following responses were received when the respondents were asked about their travel frequency for work, leisure, or business. Many participants frequently travelled within the country for work, leisure or business. Many professionals such as doctors and lawyers travelled more regularly within the country. It was also found that the majority of people that travelled within the country did so for work or business purposes compared to leisure travel—many people who also travelled quite frequently within the country for business purposes. Many of the participants travelled within the country at least twice a year.

The following responses were received when the respondents were asked about the frequency of travelling outside the country. Many participants did not travel outside the country for work travel or leisure purposes frequently. Most of the participants who travelled outside the country more than once a year did so for business purposes, although quite a few travelled for work purposes. Most of the participants preferred to stay in hotels when travelling abroad, although a few say they have considered Airbnb and other options.

In response to **preferred places to stay while travelling within the country**, most of the participants stayed in hotels when travelling within the country. However, there were also quite a few people who stayed in guest houses and Spa Hotels. The number of people who remained at Airbnb was also relatively high. The results showed that most people preferred to stay in Airbnb or hotels when travelling within the country. There were also distinctions between the types of accommodation with relation to the occupation of the participant.

When it came to choosing **accommodation while travelling overseas**, most participants said that they prefer to stay in hotels. A few prefer to stay in golf or spa hotels. The number of participants who chose to stay at Airbnb was significantly less than when travelling overseas. Also, many people prefer to stay at hotels 3 star or more when travelling overseas. A few said that security was the main factor that affected their choice of accommodation, while others preferred to look at comfort. People who travelled more to holiday destinations were more likely to stay at a guest house or Airbnb. People travelling on a business trip preferred hotels because of the convenience.

Section I

Service quality and the critical elements of successful service quality strategies

When describing service quality, there were many different opinions on which aspects of service quality are more important. However, there were a few factors that most participants identified which could be used to gauge service quality. One of the main elements was cleanliness. Many participants said that a hotel's value on cleanliness was a factor in their perception of its service. This included cleanliness of the rooms, lobby, and other areas and the provision of clean sheets, towels, etc. Another central aspect that many participants highlighted was the behaviour of the staff. Polite staff usually indicated that the hotel emphasised high-quality standards. The experience with the team was found to be one of the defining factors regarding the customer's perception of whether the hotel provided good service quality or not. One factor that was identified by many was the system of booking and whether it accommodated customers or not. A few people said that the hotel management's speed and resolution were also factors in their perception of the hotel's service quality.

Brand image and its measurement

Brand image is the customers' perception of a particular brand related to the value of the product or service. Many customers had an opinion on the brand value of several hotels. Many indicated that the brand value strongly affects their choice of hotel. If they chose between a five-star hotel they were aware of because of solid brand value and an unknown five-star hotel, they would opt for a better brand image. Many participants said that the quality of services that the hotel provides is a measurement of the brand value. Others cited the duration of the hotel and its reputation in the local and international community as a measure of its brand value. A few participants attributed the brand value to ratings that the hotel had received through review sites or critics. Some participants said that the price of the service could be a factor when deciding the brand value of a hotel. Therefore, there were mixed responses when it came to measuring the brand value of a hotel, although each one of these factors is relevant.

Implementing service quality strategy that demonstrably improves brand image

While each hotel has a different strategy for improving its brand image, a few common aspects were identified in this case. One of the main aspects that many participants identified is that the hotel should improve its promotional strategy. Many people choose a hotel based on whether they know the hotel. Therefore, a good marketing strategy is an effective way to enhance the hotel's image. Another method that many people highlighted was improving their reviews. Many customers find hotels through review sites or on Google, which is one factor that affects brand image. By enhancing their service quality, hotels will get more positive reviews, which will help improve their brand image. Many people also said that staff training is an excellent way for hotels to enhance their service quality. Implementing best practices in terms of customer service and quality assurance was another factor in improving the hotel's brand image. Some had indicated that the customer complaints department also played an essential role in customer satisfaction and brand image. Hotels that address their customer complaints more professionally are more likely to have a better brand value.

Section II

This section carried closed-ended questions mostly. The findings are presented in the following charts.

Figure 4.2 Hotel selection based on Google rating

Most of the participants agreed and strongly agreed to choose the hotels based on the Google reviews. Significantly few people did not rely on previous customer ratings when choosing a hotel. This shows the importance of having a high Google rating and keeping customers satisfied.

Figure 4.3: Hotel selection based on location

From the research, primarily participants strongly agreed on the location and accessibility of the hotel before booking the hotel. This shows the importance of positioning and proximity to critical areas for the success of hotels. Many people choose hotels because of their convenience. One of the essential factors determining how convenient the hotel is is the accessibility to infrastructure and critical city areas.

Figure 4.4: Do your research and read about the hotel’s service quality?

Most of the people agreed to their research before booking a hotel. More than 88% of the people did some research before deciding which hotel they would stay in. This research could include pricing, brand image, location, or other factors, but it shows the importance of providing accurate information to potential customers.

Figure 4.5 Researching and reading feedbacks about the quality of food and beverage and a menu of the hotel before booking and after the stay.

This graph reveals that most participants agreed that they research food and beverage before booking and leaving reviews on food and drink after staying. Less than 2% of the people did not do any research on the food and drink of the hotel or leave a related review before leaving.

Figure 4.6: Do you research or read feedback about the staff of the hotel before booking and after the stay?

Many participants agreed to research staff behaviour before booking and leaving reviews after staying. More than 98% of the participants did some research on the hotel staff or left a review regarding this area. Many participants' wants to know what previous customers had experienced in the hotel, what kind of services they received and how staff dealt with the problems customers encountered.

Figure 4.7 Do your research or read feedback about the hygiene of the hotel before booking and after the stay?

Most participants agreed to research hygiene before booking and leaving reviews after staying. None of the participants did do any research on hygiene, which shows the importance that customers place on the cleanliness of the hotel.

Figure 4.8 Do you research or read feedbacks about the interiors of the hotel before booking and after the stay?

A high number of participants agreed to research interiors and comfort before booking and leaving reviews after staying. However, several participants did not keep this in mind, which is a secondary factor.

Figure 4.9 Do you research or read feedbacks about the infrastructure of the hotel before booking and after the stay?

Most participants agreed to research infrastructure before booking and leaving reviews after staying. However, more than a third of the participants did not research or give feedback on the hotel's infrastructure or were unsure of the topic. This also shows that it is not a significant factor that people consider.

Figure 4.10 Do you research or read feedback about the promptness of the hotel staff before booking and /or after the stay?

Most of the participants agreed to research prompt services offered by the hotel staff before booking and leaving reviews after staying. This is related to the staff's effectiveness and is one factor affecting the hotel's image.

Figure 4.11 Do you research or read feedback on the grooming, cleanliness and appearance of the hotel staff before booking and after the stay?

Most participants agreed to research about staff overall appearance before booking and leaving reviews after staying. Just as with other aspects of staff performance, customers are impacted by their cleanliness and overall appearance. This is the primary aspect customers always tries to experience the best environment and experience where they stay. Employees play a significant part in this. Participants preferred to select a particular hotel where their employees pay attention to their cleanliness and grooming.

Figure 4.12 Do you research or read feedback on the delivery time of the order made from your hotel room before booking and after the stay?

Around 140 participants agreed to research the delivery time of the services before booking and leaving reviews after staying. Less than 13% did not explore the delivery time of services or were not aware of the topic. This shows the importance of timely service delivery in the hospitality industry. Customers find it way too crucial to deliver food to their rooms in tia timely manner. From the feedback, the delivery of food should be a priority.

Figure 4.13 Do you research or read feedback on the courtesy and behavior of the hotel staff before booking and after the stay?

A majority agreed to research staff behavior before booking and leaving reviews after staying. This is one of the primary factors people consider when reviewing a hotel. A high number of participants wants to know how well hotel employees' behavior is to their customers. Approximately 280 participants preferred to read feedback on the courtesy of hotel staff before booking.

Figure 4.14 Do your research or read feedback on the colour theme, music and temperature of the hotel common area and your hotel room before booking and after the stay?

One hundred sixty participants agreed to research overall interiors and soothing ambience before booking and leaving reviews after staying. Significantly few people did not consider this factor. This highlights the importance of hotel design and its impact on customers. A large number of participants wants to book hotels after reading and looking the hotel up it on the internet. They prefer to see and know what they are getting into.

Figure 4.15 Is the brand name important for you while picking the hotel for your stay?

A high percentage of the participants agreed that they chose brand names while choosing the hotel. This shows the importance that people place on brand names and is an indication that hotels should work to improve their brand name if they want to gain more customers.

Figure 4.16 Does quality of service offered by the hotel brand makes for its image?

A clear majority of the participants agreed that the quality of service offered influences their thoughts of the brand's image. Only two people did not believe that the quality of service affects the brand image, which shows that there is a consensus amongst customers that hotels with good quality service will also have a strong brand image.

Figure 4.17 Does the hotel staff behaviour make for the hotel brand image?

A high percentage of the participants agreed to staff behaviour being a key determinant informing the brand image. Just as with a brand image, customers place importance on the staff behaviour when choosing a hotel. Hotels with better-trained staff will also have a better brand image.

Figure 4.18 Does the interiors and the décor of the hotel makes for the brand image?

The majority agreed to interiors being a key determinant informing the brand image. This is also closely tied with the hotel’s brand image, affecting customer perception.

Figure 4.19 Does the infrastructure make for the brand image.

Many participants agreed that infrastructure is a key determinant informing the brand image. This shows the importance of the hotel design and infrastructure, which includes stairs, lifts, room size and other factors.

Figure 4.20 Does the new technology advancements opted by the hotels for various purposes makes for the hotel brand image?

A clear majority agreed to advance technology as a key determinant informing the brand image. This means that hotels who want to gain a competitive edge in the market should invest more in the latest technology as it helps improve their brand image. Around more than 100 people believe that hotels' technological advancements influence the hotel's brand image.

Figure 4.21 Does hotel location and accessibility makes for the hotel brand image?

Most of the participants agreed to location and accessibility as key determinants informing the brand image. However, there were a few who disagreed. Nevertheless, hotels should be situated near the main areas of the city in which they are located as these areas have real estate value.

Figure 4.22 Does the variety and quality in the food-beverage and drinks make for the brand image?

In most cases, the participants agreed that the quality and variety of food and beverages offered are key determinants informing the brand image. Remarkably few people disagreed about the quality of food, which is why hotels should ensure that their food quality is of the highest standard.

Figure 4.23 Do the events and other evening surprises, workout facility, swimming and leisure experience make for the brand image?

A clear majority agreed to surprises, leisure facilities, and night events, which is crucial for the brand image. However, quite a few people were unsure of this, and some disagreed. This shows that the different events and facilities are a premium factor, but they are not the first things people consider while booking a hotel.

Figure 4.24 Do you think hotel market as an industry is going through tough times?

Most of the participants agreed that the hotel industry is facing a crisis. This shows that people are aware of market factors, which could ultimately affect pricing and quality of service.

Figure 4.25 Do you think hotel industry has been hit by the Pandemic ?

A majority agreed that the hotel industry is facing a crisis due to the Pandemic. None of the participants disagreed, which shows that most people know about the effects of the pandemic on the hospitality industry and its implications.

Figure 4.26 Do you think hotel industry is affected by the rules and policies made by the government?

Almost half of the participants agreed that government policies impact the hotel industry. However, quite a few people disagreed or were unsure, which could indicate the lack of knowledge on the laws and policies that affect the hospitality industry.

Figure 4.27 Do you think hotel industry focus on guest needs and demands?

There was an apparent disagreement with this statement. Some participants disagreed with to hotel industry focus on customer needs and demands. This could result from a bad customer experience with previous hotels or because the hotels are ignoring specific key customer demands.

Figure 4.28 Do you think Hotel industry lives up to its image portrayed in its advertisements and brochures?

The majority disagreed with the hotel industry living up to their promises made in advertisements, brochures, and other communication. This further proves that many hotels do not back up their promises during promotions with actual service delivery. It could also be the result of the advertising industry's use of pictures that fail to represent the current state of the hotel.

Figure 4.29 Do you think hotel industry match the guest perception and expectation?

Not many participants agreed to this statement. More than 90 participants disagreed with the hotel industry matching the guest perception and expectation. This could be related to how many hotels create false expectations through advertisements, resulting in customer dissatisfaction.

Figure 4. 30 Do you think the hotel industry needs to better its servicing in terms of the guest's needs and demands?

There was much agreement with this statement. Many agreed to the hotel industry's need to focus on customer needs and demands. This shows that there is a gap in the way hotels cater to the needs of their customers.

Figure 4.31 Do you think hotel industry lacks a metrics or tools to measure its service quality?

Participants agreed that the hotel industry lacks a metric system to measure service quality. This shows that around 140 participants know their feedback is not being used to measure service quality effectively. It could also indicate that customers are disappointed by how hotels handle their complaints.

Figure 4.32 Do you think the hotel industry pays attention to training their staff in empathy, promptness, and customer interaction?

Most of the participants agreed that the hotel industry needs to train its staff in empathy, promptness, and customer interaction. This is another area where customers feel that hotels are lacking. It also shows how vital adequately trained staff are to maintain its image.

Figure 4.33 Do you think the hotel industry spends time, money, and effort grooming its staff?

Many of them said that the hotel industry does not spend time, money, and effort in grooming their staff, implying that this is something the hotels should do. This also shows the importance of staff appearance and manners and its effect on customers.

Figure 4.34 Do you think hotel industry spend more time, money, and effort on housekeeping hygiene?

Most of the participants agreed that to hotel industry should spend more time, effort, and money on housekeeping and hygiene. Only 60 participants disagreed that hotels should pay more for hygiene. However, most of the participants may have had bad experiences with the hygiene of hotels before. Customers spend their money to get the service they are paying for, including clean linens, pillows, and toilets.

Figure 4.35 Do you think the hotel industry should work keeping the customer perception and expectation in mind?

Most of the participants agreed that to hotel industry should work keeping customer perception and expectation in mind. Only two people disagreed with this, which means that customers like to know that hotels value their expectations and are working to meet them.

Figure 4.36 Do you think hotel industry should ensure the accessibility of their property?

A majority agreed that to hotel industry should ensure accessibility of the property. This could include location, ease of access to rooms, ease of booking and other factors.

Figure 4.37 Do you think the experience of the guest feels much better during check-in than check out?

A majority agreed that the customer’s experience is better during the check-ins than check-out. This shows that hotels should improve their check-out process to keep customers satisfied and retain customers longer.

Figure 4. 38 Do you think hotel industry should work on the experience of the guest while checking out?

According to the participants, the hotel industry should improve the check-out experience. This could involve better staff training, emphasis on checkout quality from managers and other strategies designed to improve the checkout experience.

Figure 4.39 Do you think hotels should focus on the Value-added services?

The majority of the respondents were inclined that the hotel industry should provide better value-added services. This provides a challenge to the hotel industry to improve the quality of their service to ensure customer satisfaction.

Figure 4.40 Do you think hotel should work on their cost factor?

Many participants said that the hotel industry should work on their price bifurcation. Most people think that there are differences between the hotel's quality of service and the pricing, which means that hotels should either improve their quality or reduce the pricing.

Figure 4.41 Do you think hotel should have 24x7 check-in and check out and the cost of the room starts when the person checks in and checks out rather a set time?

Many agreed that the hotel industry should ensure a 24x7 check-in and check-out and the meter if the bill starts whatever time the check-in happens. This means that most customers are not satisfied with the fixed time check-in and check out system.

The findings show that the business, which was soaring up, has reduced to 50% and has lost many jobs. The government furlough in-fluxed a breather, but the whole industry was brought down to seven years. It may take the United Kingdom's hospitality sector government support to revive and add to that another five to seven years to come to its pre-Covid glory. The data shows the situation of the market. At the same time, the secondary data through various scientific literature and other research work has analysed the four models to figure which are the critical determinants of service quality that helps in improving the brand image.

The other researchers on the real-time market applied various tools to assess the evaluation process of service quality and the factors which lead to the betterment of the service quality in the eyes of the customer, in terms of their perception of the service and the brands and expectation of the service quality and brand. This research has used various empirical studies of hotels like Intercontinental, Whitbread, and select hotels to figure out the lag and gap these hotels have faced since the past decade. Their businesses were analysed further for 2018 till 2020 and 2021. Data was additionally represented on the graph for comparing and analysis. Various key determinants and factors were analysed of luxury hotels, midscale hotels, upper scale hotels, golf hotels, and Spa hotels of the United Kingdom. The data was shown in the graph through which the critical determinants of service quality were derived, which the hotel managers and marketers could use to improve their brand image. Further, the analysis of the extensive research work and study done by various other researchers was used and collected as the secondary data, which helps in analysing the various told and the four models presented by researchers in the past and whether they have any impact on the assessment of service quality and or improving the service quality. Studies through empirical research, studies through the scientific literature, studies describing the connection between service quality and brand image, peer-review papers were included.

Through the quality assessment and research, the research questions were answered by this research. The data was focused on answering the question about service quality and the key elements that define service quality for the consumers. Also, the service quality strategies that the hospitality industry should rely on are considered necessary in this data. To meet the objectives of this research, data has also focused on the brand image and its measurement. In the hospitality industry, brand image is an essential factor. A company that carries the image of being hospitable and efficient is preferred over others that are not considerate or hospitable

for the customers. This research has also focused on the hotel industry's issues regarding service quality. After identifying these issues, the hotel's current service qualities strategies are also identified. Also, it is a crucial point to note that for service quality strategy and brand image building, the hotels overall hospitality industry needs to rely on thorough measures that can help the organisations identify their strengths and weaknesses to remain competitive.

5. Chapter 5: Discussion and Analysis

Data collected through the questionnaire is presented in the previous chapter. In this chapter, the analysis of the data collected will be conducted. Analysing the data will be identified if the research objectives are met or not. Along with the data analysis, the discussion of the findings will also be carried out in this chapter.

5.1 Analysis

In the research, around three hundred people were surveyed as frequent travellers within the country and outside the country. In the quantitative survey done, it was found that today's consumer has become a prosumer, as mentioned time and again. The data analysis is being carried out by studying simple statistics identified from the data and the results of interview content analysis. This consumer has well-defined service quality parameters, which are crucial for them. The key elements, which they consider essential for them in service quality, extend from tangible to intangibles, whether it hygiene, housekeeping, decor, infrastructure. Hygiene factors such as clean and disinfected hotel premises, the scent across the rooms and the hotel corridor, public space and lounges, sanitisers to the hotel's colour theme, rooms, and play in the room. The rest of the hotel, greenery inside and outside the hotel, staff behaviour and experience during the check-in and check-out, staff promptness, quality of food and beverage, availability of the drinks of the customer's choice determine, 24x7 availability of work out areas and swimming pools are the key elements of service quality as per the customer to make or break the brand image, to get the high rating or average or poor ratings by the customer rate. The presence may not impact much on the rating; however, the absence of these critical elements may get the hotel to poor rating and lousy brand image. Therefore, these key elements need to be focused upon in the service quality strategy for a hotel to better its brand image.

Thus, the survey helped find another critical determinant in the service quality: the physical appearance of the staff—the delivery of the service and the showcasing matters for the customer. Trust, which hotel staff can generate through their interaction, goes a long way in sustaining the customer's loyalty. The appearance of the team is not just limited to their dressing. It also includes other important aspects through which the team creates positive or

negative images. The team's appearance could also interact with the guests and the manner and tone with which they address the guests. It was found that many people prefer to go to hotels where the staff are more professional and well-trained. Most participants listed this as one of the critical factors in determining service quality. Considering that service quality is directly related to brand image, a hotel with better performing staff will also have a better brand image. Therefore, hotels need to ensure that the key determinants are staff appearance are appropriately covered so that it does not hurt the overall brand image. This could include many things, such as ensuring that the staff are always well dressed. The team should also correctly adhere to the required hygiene standards and ensure that they care for the hotel's hygiene and appearance. One of the key findings of this study shows that most people are not satisfied with the service quality and appearance of the staff. Most of the participants have indicated that poor staff performance was one of the critical factors that made the hotel lose its credibility, which is why this is a crucial area that hotels should address.

Performance of staff could be linked to a few factors. One of them includes poor management or mistakes in the hiring process. However, there was no mention of this factor in the study or participants' responses. Another factor highlighted was the relationship between poor staff performance and quality of staff training. Most participants had indicated that proper staff training is one of the significant factors that impacted whether the staff performed well or not. A high number of participants also said that hotels should do more to train their staff to adhere to quality standards, hygiene, and other aspects of customer service. This shows that there is a gap that hotel's need to fill in the way of staff training and quality assurance. Without a proper focus on these aspects, the ratings of the hotel will be affected.

One of the study findings showed that most participants researched the quality and professionalism of the staff before choosing a hotel. Many people also look at Google reviews to help them decide which hotel is suitable for them. If the hotel has poor reviews due to a lack of staff training, it will affect the brand image and, therefore, its ability to attract new customers. It will also have a negative effect on customer retention. Consider the fact that most participants indicated that they usually do some staff research or leave a review regarding staff quality. The hotel should assess its customer feedback and use it to determine whether they need to conduct additional training sessions aimed at improving the quality of their staff or not.

As per the customer, which helps in their trust-building, are reliability, empathy, competence, personal touch, politeness, promptness. It was also found that usage of the Hitech and updated technology in the hotel for their execution and other purposes directly impacting the customer delivery time is another critical determinant of the service quality strategy. Technology is one of the critical factors determining a hotel's image in the current age. Many people responded that this is one of the areas where hotels are lacking. Technology is also linked with the accessibility and infrastructure of the hotel. Many newer hotels have been designed to incorporate the latest technology, which helps them attract more clients. However, combining the newest technology in the hotel design can be challenging for older and more established hotels because of the time and disruption caused by renovation. The cost factor could also be an issue for the hotel. However, since most participants have indicated that technology impacts the image and rating of a hotel, the investment in the latest technological additions will pay off in terms of better brand image and better customer satisfaction.

A company's ability to achieve excellence in service quality depends on these critical elements of service, which forms the brand image post the hotel stay experience. The outside world creates the perception and expectation of the customer like advertisements done by the brand, position of the brands, review of the brands, etc. It is significant for brands in the hotel market to use the quality improvement index and prioritise their service quality attributes for accurate and straightforward results. Now, let's consider the hotel price and its star classification (one-star, two-star, three-star, four-star, five-star, seven-star, etc.) as critical determinants of the brand image of hotels in the United Kingdom. It is found that most of them have harmful feedback that pots the experience of the services owing to the customer's perception and their expectations. The price with the age of the infrastructure or brand has also hurt the service quality assessment. Now the guests of these hotels, especially those who pay higher for the comfort and luxury, are immensely demanding, and any shortcomings, no matter how small it is in the services and facilities, consequentially bring negative ratings for the hotels because these guests come with certain expectations which are relatively higher. The current performance of the hotels in these areas is relatively poor.

Firstly, many people have indicated that the hotels are not performing according to the standard described in their ratings. This could be an issue for many established hotels, indicating low customer satisfaction. Many customers have suggested that the hotels need to invest more money in improving their hygiene standards and quality of services. Many

people agree that hotels need to enhance their value to customers. The fact that many people are not satisfied with the current performance of the hotels could be attributed to two factors. The first factor is that the hotels are falling back on their quality standards, resulting in more bad experiences for guests. This practical issue needs to be addressed by identifying the fundamental problems and tackling them individually. If the customer feedback indicates that the staff performance was poor, the hotel management can organise training sessions to improve this aspect. If most customers are dissatisfied with the hotel's hygiene, then the hotel should try and invest more in the quality and provision of hygiene. Hotels should also ensure ease of accessibility, including proper lifts and disability-friendly infrastructure. The findings also indicated that most hotels did not take the customer demands into perspective when providing services.

This shows the importance of maintaining high-quality standards and meeting customer demands. The second factor influencing the customers' perception of the hotel is the lack of fulfilling promises made in advertisements. Many customers have indicated that the hotel did not correctly describe its services when advertising. In most cases, the hotel may have advertised to give the customer the impression that the quality of service was excellent when it was not. In some cases, the pictures used in advertisements did not correctly represent the actual setting of the hotel, which caused customers to have higher expectations. This is one of the main factors hotels have to address to gain customer trust.

The more honest an advertisement is, the more likely the customer will have reasonable expectations, and therefore they will not be that disappointed. This issue is influenced by the fact that many customers are becoming savvier and recognise that they have several options to choose from. Therefore, it puts pressure on hotels to deliver the promise they make in advertisements. Subsequently, the lack of promises made in ads and the actual service quality will affect the hotel's brand image.

The key determinants that impact the customer's expectations of the hotel brand's image are the star category level of the hotel promised services that raise the perception and expectation, price, and the location in terms of accessibility of the property. The higher the cost higher is the expectation and perception of excellence in service quality levels; the lower the price, the lower is the perception and expectation of the customer from the hotel and service quality.

The star category level process introduces a metric of quality indicators, which primarily increases higher star rating levels or category hotels. Location influences the customer's expectations. The exotic location of the hotel raises the expectations of customers.

This survey found out that other critical determinants of the service quality that influence customer satisfaction and repeat customers are hygiene and housekeeping, quality of food and beverage, check-in experience, front office operations, and hotel staff appearance and interaction. In terms of signs of which key determinants are more crucial when putting against the customer's perception, the front office operation, check-in, and check-out win the number one position as the critical determinant. Quick check-in checks out, and well-behaved staff across the counter increases the chance of high brand image ratings. On the second position is well-behaved staff interaction followed by the housekeeping that includes hygiene, cleanliness, quality of furniture, attractive interiors, and décor of the hotel and the hotel rooms, appealing and warm theme, temperature, and music as the third position holder. The food and beverage hold the fourth position. Therefore, the hotel needs to consider these four key determinants in terms of service quality strategy for a positive, strong, and successful brand image.

In the customer's eyes, the brand's perception makes for the brand image. As per the customer survey, the brand image is determined by the quality of services offered by the brands when out against the customer perception and expectation. The critical determinant which came out in the survey which makes for the hotels brand image are hotel hygiene, hotel staff behaviour which includes helpful and empathetic interaction, promptness, fast delivery, and quick response, hotel location and accessibility, the décor, and the comfort of the hotel and spaciousness of the room offered, quality of food and availability of drinks which customer prefer, and hotels technological advancements.

The pandemic COVID-19 has severely hit the hotel industry. This pandemic has taken the hotel industry at least five years behind. However, the hotel industry at its foundation is trying to figure out the problems it has been facing for ages and has not been able to find a solution. The survey done with the three hundred people reveals that the industry has not yet been able to work as per the customer needs and demands. The hotel industry has its own rules. Hotel managers have their perception of customer needs. The strategies in terms of service quality are the developed basis that is not aligned with the customer's needs and

demands. This gap creates a huge problem, which the hotel industry has not yet figured out. Adding to that, the hotel is responsible for making a certain kind of perception about their hotel and services by advertising and making promises and positioning themselves at a certain level basis which customer expectation is created. If the same level of expectations which was somehow created through their perception which the hotel itself formed is not met, then the brand image goes for a toss. The current service quality strategy, which is followed by the hotel industry, is making high level or affordable or excellence in service quality perception through various brochures, outgoing communication, public relation, and advertisements, which later forms the expectation of the customer or guest.

With such a strategy, the hotel attracts many customers, but when these customers experience the same promised services live while staying in the hotel do not get the same promised level of quality of services. This results in them hoping for the new brand or hotel. Therefore, the hotel cannot sustain and or get repeat customers guests. Their strategy is notwithstanding the customer's needs and demands, customers perception and expectation, resulting in the loss of business.

One of the significant factors that the participants identified was the impact of the quality measurement standard on the hotel's brand image. Most participants indicated that hotels should improve the metric system to measure service quality. Firstly, this shows that most customers think that hotel managers are not aware of the hotel's quality standards. Many also believe that the hotel does not consider their needs when assessing quality standards and providing quality services. This could mean that more customers are beginning to lose their trust in the feedback system of the hotel. Another issue with this is that it shows that hotels are lacking in their ability to gather and process customer feedback. The study has indicated that many people will leave feedback before leaving the hotel. The system used to collect this feedback should be assessed, and a better approach would be implemented. One of the factors that could affect the gathering of feedback when customers are leaving the hotel is the quality of customer service at the check-out point. The study has shown that most people are not satisfied with the quality of service by the checkout staff. This could indicate an issue with the hotel's vision when training staff. It could also interfere with the effectiveness of gathering feedback. The fact that many hotels are not aware of the poor-quality standard of the checkout staff shows that they are missing out on customer retention while focusing more on customer acquisition. However, this causes many customers to have bad experiences as

they are about to leave, which could eventually impact the hotel's brand image. These findings also show a gap in the system used to measure quality service; hotels should have a method of taking the feedback from customers and integrating it with other business processes to ensure continuous improvement in the quality of the services provided. They should also communicate effectively with the customer and inform them that their feedback was received and addressed. This will give customers more belief in the feedback system of the hotel.

If the hotel industry needs to seriously re-think their strategy, they need to fill in the gap between the customer or guest perception and expectation viz. a viz. the service they offer. They need to understand the kind of high-quality service they promise, whether in terms of accessibility, cost, affordability, events planning, leisure services, hygiene, comfort, and luxury. They need to work on what they offer and send out in their communication. The survey was done with the three hundred people also points out that there is a gap between customer expectation and hotel understanding of customer perception and expectation. It was revealed that hotels need to spend more time, money, and effort in training their staff, grooming their team, accessibility to the hotel property by providing the services of transport, comfort, events planning, and surprises, filling the gap of customer expectation and quality of service offered in real during their stay, smooth check-outs like the smooth check-ins, promptness in resolving customers queries. If the hotel can work on these critical attributes, they can improve their customer relationship, which will enhance their brand image.

Good brand image results in increased revenue. As it has been derived that there is a gap between customer expectation and perception viz. a viz. the service delivery, the hotel management should improve the service attitude. The actual expectations and the intangibles are crucial for a great customer experience, which in turn breaks and makes the hotel's brand image. Since they live off their service quality, it is imperative for the hotels to improve the quality of services in the continuum. A set policy does not work for long, so the strategies need to be in sync with the changing times and generations. Each generation is brighter than the previous; the value for eth last may not be of any value to the current generation. Therefore, hotels must understand their customers, tweak their service quality and technological advancements, and align with the age. This will ensure hotels maintain and sustain their brand image in the eyes of the customer and earn more revenue. Not only are customers aware of the hotel's brand image, but customers are also aware that their feedback

and reviews can have a positive or negative effect on the brand image. If they are not satisfied with the services, they are more likely to leave a negative review on Google and other platforms. Not only will this affect the hotel's rating on these sites, but it will also affect the overall brand image. Most customers have indicated that they consider the brand image when looking for a hotel, which is why hotels need to manage their brand image by providing high-quality services.

Regarding improving customer relations, hotels also need to look at their pricing. The research has shown that most customers know economic conditions, and the pandemic most impact hotels. However, most of the participants also say that the hotel's pricing is not correct. Many of these participants have experience with various hotels means that the hotels should reconsider their pricing strategies. One reason for this customer response could be that the customer is not aware of the demand in the hotel's area. However, in most cases, it's not the pricing that the customers have an objection to. Instead, it is the level of service provided within that price that the customers feel is not right. Therefore, if hotels want to maintain their current pricing strategy, they should improve the quality of the service provided. Otherwise, they should reduce the prices. Another method that can be used to address this issue is to create offers where frequent customers can get benefits or booking more than one room can come with a discount. The study has shown that most customers feel that the pricing should be adjusted to be in sync with the time that the customer spent at the hotel rather than through fixed timings. This could indicate that many people may have flexible schedules, which the hotels' pricing or booking strategy. While the hotel might face specific issues in terms of cost and bookings, it will gain in terms of customer satisfaction and brand value. As with all other aspects, the hotel needs to analyse whether it focuses on cost-cutting strategies or value-driven strategies. However, many responses through the questionnaire have indicated that customers prefer hotels that create more value than those that only focus on cost.

The personal interactions between the staff and the guests play a significant role in customer experience, which is consequential to positive reviews and a positive brand image of the hotel. The study has shown that most customers have indicated that empathy and personal interactions of staff should be a pivotal aspect of their training. This suggests that most customers include this as part of quality service and do not only look at the external appearance of the staff. It also provides hotels with an objective that they need to achieve

through the design of more effective training systems. Since this is *prima facie*, the hotels of the United Kingdom need to be dedicatedly committed to the continuous improvement of the customer and staff interaction and the other dimension gap of these services. For a positive brand, image hotels need to take the cues to better their services from the customer's expectations and perception by asking questions and taking feedback.

5.2 Discussion

The hospitality industry in the UK is one of the fastest evolving industries in recent times. There are many factors that affect the success of a business in this industry, and the level of threat from external factors is often higher than in other sectors (Ali et al., 2021). Hotels, Guest Lodges and other businesses operating in the hospitality industry are all affected by the changes in the external environment. These could include economic, social and political changes that affect how companies use, the regulations under which they operate and customer behaviour (Li et al., 2021). To remain successful in this industry, businesses have to address these external threats and be prepared to face any changes that may come unexpectedly. As Mishra et al. (2020) have discussed, like all other industries in the world, Covid-19 has affected the hospitality industry in the UK.

Hospitality is among the most critical industries in the country, and it has faced a severe setback due to Covid-19. Mishra et al. (2020) has identified the uncertainty created by Covid-19 as a significant threat to the industry. One of the main threats that the hospitality industry often faces is in the form of increased regulations and political change (Kenyon et al., 2020). While the political environment of the UK has mainly been stable compared to other countries, it still influences various industries (Jones and Comfort, 2020). This often comes in the form of regulations targeted towards specific industries. For example, rules on the quality of hygiene may affect the way in which hotels approach this aspect. Most customers are also aware of the fact that regulatory influences can affect the customer service procedure and other parts of the hotel's services (Kasiri et al., 2017). While this is a factor that the hotel often has little control over, it is more predictable than external factors. This makes it more manageable as well. Most of the legislation that affects business practices is often proposed long before it is implemented, which gives businesses sufficient time to change their systems accordingly (Al-Ababneh, 2017).

As Richardson et al. (2021) have discussed, the hospitality industry in the UK and the world over need to be future-oriented. The focus should be on globalised culture and the impact of technology on future life. Covid-19 has affected the hospitality industry, as identified by Mishra et al. (2021). However, as Li et al. (2021) discussed, this also means that the industry has the opportunity to evolve and grow in the futuristic direction now. This requires a clearer understanding of the threats that the industry is facing.

However, not all external threats are predictable. One example is the economic changes that influence businesses. Many businesses may be affected by the difference in the buying power of consumers, an increase in taxes and other economic factors. Studies have shown that economic regression can negatively affect the hospitality industry (Agwa et al., 2017). Less buying power means that people prefer to travel less, which could have a negative effect on the revenue generation of hotels. An increase in taxes on businesses or certain items can increase the cost of operating the hotel, which may force the hotel to increase its prices (Florivic, 2020). Economic factors are often less predictable and require prior preparation to overcome. However, some findings show that many more established hotels have survived many financial issues, mainly due to their successful brand image and reputation. Therefore, by focusing on customer service and quality, the hotel can increase its chances of surviving economic threats and sustain its brand image (Tan and Despotis, 2021).

However, some threats are wholly unavoidable and can only be managed. One recent example is the COVID19 pandemic, which most affected the hospitality industry. The pandemic had caused the closure of hotels in many parts of the country (Jones and Comfort, 2020). Some had to ensure complete closure for a few months. This has an effect on the revenue of the business; it also causes more problems because the hotels still have to endure maintenance and other costs. The pandemic also affected how many customers approached the subject of hygiene. Many people who travel nowadays now look at the hygienic aspect of the hotel more carefully (Li et al., 2021). The study had shown that the majority of people had recommended that hotels invest more in hygiene and maintaining cleanliness in the hotel. A failure to do so could result in the closure of the hotel, and its ratings may also be affected. However, training staff to enforce social distancing and other hygiene protocols often take additional time (Kenyon et al., 2020).

There are also additional costs that the hotel may have to endure for following the new procedures. Therefore, the pandemic is an external threat in many ways, which is why hotels should create strategies to cope with it rather than succumb to its pressure. The benefits of addressing the issues that the pandemic caused may outweigh the costs in the long run (Wong and Tseng, 2019). One of the main advantages of increasing spending on hygiene and mess handling is that the hotel will maintain its brand image, which may affect future business. Studies have shown that there is likely to be a boom in travel after the pandemic. Hotels that have implemented better hygiene protocols and spent more on training staff to accommodate these factors are more likely to be successful in gaining new customers during this period. Therefore, while the pandemic is a risk, it can also be approached in a way that creates more opportunities in the long run. The way the hotel handles this crisis will affect its future brand image and sustainability (Chivandi et al., 2019).

The analysis of the findings in the previous chapter reveals that customers prioritise certain factors in assessing service delivery, such as access to infrastructure, hotel location, the reputation of staff, hotel hygiene, feedback system, etc. One very effective way to understand the implications of the data is to look at the findings through the lens of the service quality model, also known as SERVQUAL.

The SERVQUAL Model's five service dimensions (reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness) are commonly referred to as the 5 Dimensions of Service Quality.

While the SERVQUAL model had ten dimensions, its simplified model- the RATER model, which contains just five variables, was able better to explain the concept to a variety of customers. Perceived service quality is evaluated using service quality dimensions, such as punctuality, timeliness, courtesy, helpfulness, and other such characteristics.

SERVQUAL is a multi-dimensional research process aimed at measuring the gap scores between customers' expectations and their perceptions of service quality.

These dimensions illustrate a scale for gauging customer perception of quality of service. Additionally, customers benefit from knowing about the business, and this is why service marketing is deeply integrated with customer research.

The five service quality dimensions of service quality are

- Reliability
- Assurance
- Tangibles
- Empathy
- Responsiveness

5.2.1 Tangibles

The research findings reveal that customers experience has several factors that can be viewed through 'Tangibles' lens, such as 'Access to Infrastructure', 'Hotel Hygiene', and 'Technological Factors'.

5.2.1.1 Access to Infrastructure.

Some external factors are independent of the circumstances and must do more with customer behavior. Studies have shown that the trends of where people stay when travelling have been changing over time. According to the research, most frequent travellers still prefer to stay in a hotel (Baker, 2017). Many factors affect their choice of which hotel to stay in, which are internal factors and will be discussed later. However, the arrival of competitors in the form of Airbnb and guest lodges have taken a significant portion of the market share away from hotels (Ahmad et al., 2019). Many more people have found that such alternatives are less costly and, in many cases, provide a similar service to hotels. Many smaller guest lodges often cater to people staying at a location for a couple of days. They offer more space and privacy than a hotel and are more convenient for people who travel for leisure or family holidays (Koc, 2019). However, hotels remain pretty relevant in the provision of accommodation as they often have a better location and access to infrastructure.

Most of the people who are frequent travellers have said that access to infrastructure is one of the critical factors that affect their choice of accommodation. Another key finding of the study was the relationship between people's professions and their preferred choice of accommodation (Tan et al., 2017). People who are professionals such as lawyers and doctors often travel for work purposes and may require a hotel for a day or two. This group of people

prefer to have easy access to infrastructure, and location matters the most. However, they usually stay in 2-, 3- and 4-star hotels.

On the other hand, business owners are more likely to take trips for a couple of days and prefer more luxurious accommodation. They are also more likely to recognise and report poor service, which is why higher-rated hotels should take more care to provide exemplary customer service to their guests. These factors often affect the pricing of hotels as well. If the hotel is located in a popular tourist area, it will receive more business visitors in the offseason. They may have to reduce their prices or give discounts to regular customers (Wong and Yang, 2020).

While many of these external factors can be viewed as either opportunities or threats, they are often difficult to predict, and businesses have to remain prepared for such situations. However, when it comes to internal problems and weaknesses, the business has more control over these situations and should devise strategies to manage them accordingly. The study revolved around the factors that were important for customers and which affected the customers' behavior. Many of these problems have to do with internal weaknesses, which the hotel management can address (Florivic, 2020). It is essential to look at alternate solutions to these problems as well so that hotels can be provided with a proper framework on how to resolve common customer issues.

5.2.1.2 Location of hotels

One of the main factors that affected service quality was the location of the hotels. Many customers had identified the location as a critical factor in choosing which hotel to go with. Location is something that the business can manage, although it may not have complete control over all of the location aspects (Agwa et al., 2017). The first part of a suitable location is whether it is close to proper infrastructure or not. The study indicated that potential clients researched the proximity and accessibility to infrastructure before choosing a hotel. Therefore, hotels closer to Airports, business hubs, tourist spots, and roads are more likely to be successful than those far away from these locations.

Before building a hotel, the management should assess the location and incorporate future planning to ensure that the hotel is accessible. Another critical factor that comes under location is the safety of the area. The study indicated that people research the safety and history of the hotel's location before booking. While this is something that may be an external factor, hotel ownership does have some control over this (Wong and Tseng, 2019). For example, providing extra security and other strategies can make customers feel safe. Lastly, the hotel's location should be close to points of interest for the customer. If the hotel is located near a major business hub, it is more likely to get more professionals or business owners.

Similarly, if it is located near a popular tourist destination, it may get more family visits, etc. These factors may help hotel management identify their customers' needs and train the staff accordingly. At the same time, certain aspects of customer service may remain the same, some change according to the background of the customer (Naumov, 2019).

5.2.1.3 Hotel hygiene

When it came to internal factors that affect a hotel's success, hotel hygiene was one of the significant identified factors. Most frequent travellers often do research on the hygienic quality of the hotel they are visiting. This usually has a substantial impact on the ratings of a hotel. Hotels with no history of poor hygiene practices are more likely to have a better rating. Many studies, including Wong and Yang (2020), have shown that customers often develop long term perceptions of a place based on hygiene quality. A single bad experience, in this case, could have a lasting effect on the reputation of the hotel. During the study, it was found that many participants rate good hygiene practices as one of the main factors when it comes to good service delivery. Good hygienic practices often differ between hotels and the area in which they are located, but there are a few common aspects that all hotels should implement. Timely replacement of towels and bedsheets is something that most customers look at in a good hotel. Every hotel should have a system to clean each area regularly and maintain the rooms on a fixed schedule. However, good hygienic practices are limited to this (Baker, 2017).

One of the primary factors that hotels must consider is the hygienic protocols followed by staff. The study showed that many people did research or left feedback regarding the quality

of hygienic protocols of the hotel staff. Therefore, proper training is essential to prevent bad reviews and ensure that the hotel maintains a high standard for good hygiene. While good hygiene was always a necessary part of the hotel's functioning, the pandemic has increased the importance of following proper protocols in terms of cleanliness (Koc, 2019). Many hotels have to train their staff to follow the correct protocols to avoid the spread of the virus and ensure that the hotel is in compliance with the regulations set out in this regard. However, the research also shows that this is one area where many hotels are lacking. A high number of participants who participated in the study were not satisfied with the current hygienic quality of many hotels. Many people said that this is one area where hotels should invest more in. Therefore, hotels should review their current shortcomings when following proper hygienic practices and address them to maintain customer satisfaction (Li et al., 2021).

5.2.1.4 Technological factors

A key finding from the survey was that today's customers like fast things and instant, which does not take much time they do not have time to spend. They preferred hotels with instant checkout and check-in. They prefer hotels where check-in and checkout can happen through the hotel app. And they love to receive gifts coupons and redeem them while staying in the hotels. This finding shows us a way forward of how hospitality will have to take a steep step towards integrating technology in their service quality. Currently, the technology has been adopted by a few hotels in the check-in and checkout but not yet in other bits of the service like food and beverage, Cleanliness, Hygiene, Customers queries, etc. The survey points to a direction of using more technology, especially in service quality, which will benefit the hotels (Kasiri et al., 2017). For example, hotels can use technology to give the customer's feedback while still in their room. They can send personalised feedback on what they like, dislike, and want to be added in the future. Now the hotel can use this feedback to serve the customer better in the future. The hotels can also use technology in answering the queries of the customer. Most of the customers struggle with many fundamental issues while they enter a hotel. In the current situation, they call the reception, and then the person responds to resolve the query, which takes much time. Suppose the customer has a tab in their room that can answer all the possible queries of the customer. In that case, it will save time and effort and help the customer resolve the issue in no time, which in turn will better the experience of the hotel's customer and help strengthen the hotel's brand image.

5.2.2 Assurance

The research findings reveal that customers experience has several factors which can be viewed through the lens of Assurance, such as “reputation of staff.”

5.2.2.1 Reputation of staff

Another internal factor identified was the reputation of the staff (Chivandi et al., 2019). Many customers had indicated that they researched the staff’s reputation before choosing a hotel. This shows the importance of having the right team in a hotel. Many of the studies on this topic have shown that the relationship between the hotel staff and the customer is a critical factor in determining the hotel’s success. The professionalism of the team and their level of training is one of the main factors that hotels should consider when hiring new staff. This includes the quality with which they perform their duties as well. One of the factors that affect the quality of staff in a hotel is the training they provide (Kenyon et al., 2020). Many more successful hotels either spend much time training their staff or hiring highly qualified staff. The study showed that many customers had expressed the need for hotels to improve the quality of their training processes so that staff performance could increase. This training includes both the fulfilment of duties and responsibilities and the way the staff address any issues that they might come across. Because the hospitality industry is dynamic, the staff may have to be given regular training to stay in line with the constant changes in the market. For example, after the pandemic, staff may have to be trained in new hygiene protocols and how they implement the COVID-19 protocols established through regulation (Comfort and Jones, 2020).

This shows the need for a proper system which the hotel should implement to ensure that the staff are a strength rather than a weakness. The training should also be based on any shortcomings identified in performance or through customer feedback. This way, the hotel will ensure successful customer service quality, which results in a higher retention rate. One of the critical factors that should be incorporated into staff training is the ability to interact with and understand customers’ problems. The study by Floricic (2020) showed that many people had supported training that includes the practice of empathy and understanding the

customer on a deeper level. This indicates more to staff performance than simple professionalism and completing the duty requirements. As per Haming et al. (2019), customers are more likely to have a positive impression of a hotel if the staff are empathetic and have emotional intelligence compared to being dry and without spirit. By incorporating all of these aspects into staff training, the hotel will turn its staff into a competitive advantage rather than a weakness.

5.2.3 Responsiveness

The research findings reveal that customers experience has several factors which can be viewed through the lens of Responsiveness, such as 'Feedback from the customers'

5.2.3.1 Feedback from the customers

Another critical aspect involved in maintaining high-quality standards and ensuring customer satisfaction is the feedback system of the hotel. The research has shown that many customers will research the ratings of the hotel, its quality of food and beverages, the staff professionalism and many other factors before booking their room. The research also indicated that most people will or might leave feedback based on their experience when staying at the hotel. This feedback could be direct to the hotel management or through a feedback system that the hotel implements (Chivandi et al., 2019). It could also be in the form of a review on a third-party site. The feedback is a good indication of the success or failure of the hotel to ensure customer satisfaction and provide customers with high-quality service. This is why hotels need to provide customers with the necessary platform to leave their feedback. The hotel should also ensure that the customer is satisfied that their feedback was taken into consideration, and steps will be taken to implement the customer's recommendations. Unfortunately, the research had indicated that this was one area where many hotels failed to satisfy customers (Ali et al., 2021). Most travellers stated that they were not convinced that their feedback was valued and that the hotel did not consider the customers' needs. This shows a gap in the quality of service provided by many hotels. However, it also indicates that many hotels do not have a proper system for taking customer feedback and evaluating their performance based on this feedback (Tan and Despotis, 2021).

This could result in a high ratio of customers who are unsatisfied with the service and may opt for alternatives in future travels. Due to it being much more expensive and time-consuming to attract new customers than to retain existing ones, hotels should implement a system that ensures maximum customer satisfaction (Lai et al., 2018). They can do this by reviewing the current feedback system and ensuring that the customer is satisfied that their concerns are taken care of before leaving the hotel. This will result in better customer retention, but it will also ensure that customers post positive reviews, which can improve the hotel's brand image. Therefore, the checkout process is just as necessary as the check-in process to ensure customer satisfaction (Florivic, 2020). One of the study's key findings was that many hotels had a significantly lower service quality at the checkout than the check-in. This is often a significant blunder in the case of the hotel as it loses the opportunity to retain customers. While previously, many customers would not be as interested in leaving feedback, nowadays, most customers are savvier and request that their feedback be considered. In most cases, the feedback is taken near the end of the stay or during checkout (Kasiri et al., 2017).

A poor experience with the checkout staff may cause the customer to leave a negative review, damaging the brand reputation. Therefore, hotels should improve their checkout process and ensure that the staff are well trained to provide the customers with the best final impression (Agwa et al., 2017).

5.2.3.2 Fast check in check out

A key finding from the survey was that the customer of today like fast things and instant, which does not take much time as they do not have time to spend. They preferred hotels with instant checkout and check-in. They prefer hotels where check-in and checkout can happen through the hotel app. And they love to receive gifts coupons and redeem them while staying in the hotels. This finding shows us a way forward of how hospitality will have to take a steep step towards integrating technology in their service quality. Currently, the technology has been adopted by a few hotels in the check-in and checkout but not yet in other bits of the service like food and beverage, Cleanliness, Hygiene, Customers queries, etc. The survey points to a direction of using more technology, especially in service quality, which will benefit the hotels (Kasiri et al., 2017). For example, hotels can use technology to provide customer feedback while still in their room. They can send personalised feedback on what

they like, dislike, and want to be added in the future. Now the hotel can use this feedback to serve the customer better in the future. The hotels can also use technology in answering the queries of the customer. Most of the customers struggle with many fundamental issues while they enter a hotel. In the current situation, they call the reception, and then the person responds to resolve the query, which takes much time. Suppose the customer has a tab in their room that can answer all the possible queries of the customer. In that case, it will save time and effort and help the customer resolve the issue in no time, which in turn will better the experience of the hotel's customer and help strengthen the hotel's brand image.

5.2.4 Empathy

Empathy means caring for your customers by giving importance to their needs and providing quality service. However, to practice kindness, the focus is not on what you 'perceive' customer needs to be but what the customers say about their needs. In this modern era, a critical customer need is being eco-friendly.

The research findings reveal that customers experience has several factors which can be viewed through the lens of Empathy, such as 'Eco friendly'.

5.2.4.1 *Eco friendly*

Another crucial key element found in the research was the eco-friendly hotel image (comfort and Jones, 2020). Most of the customers of this generation prefer to stay in a hotel which is environment friendly. As much as they seek comfort, they want a better life and future for themselves. With the global warming issue sword hanging to their neck, this generation is clear on what they want and how they want. They go for green hotels, support green, ensure less waste and ensure that they are not a significant contributor to the polluting water, nature, and air. They are stressed about their quality of life and the gift they will leave for their kids. They are conscious about nature and therefore seek hotels that align and sync with them through the process and use such methods in their service quality to impact nature in the bare minimum way possible (Richardson et al., 2021).

5.2.5 Reliability

The research findings reveal that customers experience has several factors which can be viewed through the lens of Reliability, such as ‘Misleading advertising.’

5.2.5.1 Misleading advertising

Another important finding of the study was that many customers are not satisfied with hotels’ pricing and promotional strategies. Many customers had indicated that they believe the hotels should work on their cost factor (Kenyon et al., 2020). While it may be understandable that many people would like to pay lower prices as consumers, there is more to this problem than a simple cost factor. The findings also indicated that many people believed that the hotels do not live up to the customer perception and expectations. This is often the result of the differences between the image of the hotel's services advertised and the actual service provided. Hotels should review their advertisements and ensure they are more realistic to prevent this issue (Ali et al., 2021). Most customers nowadays are more likely to be smart when viewing advertisements. Suppose the hotel is a 3-star hotel and indirectly gives off the impression that it provides five-star services. In that case, the customer will not have the same level of satisfaction, even if the service quality was up to the required standard. Hotels should also review any customers experiencing quality service and ensure that these issues are resolved. It can also consider the packages it advertises and identifies which type of people are frequent visitors (Tan et al., 2017).

The hotel can arrange for a benefits program for frequent visitors to improve its customer retention rate. Another key finding related to the pricing was the customer’s response to the current billing strategy used by hotels. Most people prefer to change to a time-based billing strategy where they will be charged from the moment of check-in till they check out instead of on a fixed time basis. While this could result in a loss for the hotel in terms of longer bookings, it can help resolve a common issue that frequent travellers often face. Many people might only need to stay at a hotel for a few hours but must pay for the whole day because of the billing strategy of the hotel (Kasiri et al., 2017). The hotel will increase its customer satisfaction rate by changing this towards a time-based billing strategy. It can also increase the number of new customers that choose to stay there because of the better billing strategy.

This is also an effective way of improving hotels' competitive advantage over other forms of accommodation. While no fixed pricing strategy can be applied in all cases, a dynamic and flexible pricing strategy is often the best way to increase customer satisfaction while keeping the business profitable at the same time (Agwa et al., 2017).

5.2.6 Role of service quality strategy in improving brand image

All the previously mentioned factors are vital towards improving the hotel's interaction with customers and will result in better customer satisfaction. However, they are also closely linked with the concept of brand image and its role in retaining customers. Brand image is often defined as its perceived value based on its history, customer ratings, and other factors (Lai et al., 2018). Brand value is often a critical factor in determining the success or failure of any business. It is often challenging to build a strong brand image, but small mistakes can quickly ruin that image. Therefore, most companies strive to create a positive brand image that helps increase their brand value. In the hospitality industry, brand value is crucial in attracting new customers. The brand image of the hotel can influence the customers' decision on whether to book a room at that hotel or choose an alternative (Wong and Tseng, 2019). The study showed that many customers value the hotel's brand image when selecting an accommodation option. They often research the history of the hotel, its ratings, the quality of service and other factors that affect the overall brand image. While previously, word of mouth and other sources were used to influence a hotel's image, nowadays, the ratings on Google play an essential role (Comfort and Jones, 2020).

A high majority of people involved in the study have said that they look at the hotel's reviews and ratings on Google before booking accommodation. This shows the importance of maintaining good customer relations, ultimately resulting in good ratings. Brand image is also influenced by how the hotel handles customer feedback and the quality standards. When it comes to achieving a good brand image, the hotel must focus on internal factors to ensure success (Chavindi et al., 2019). The hotel staff's appearance, professionalism, and level of training were all critical factors in maintaining a positive brand image. Similarly, the overall appearance of the hotel, its design, the technology applied, and the accessibility have to be taken into account when determining the hotel's brand image. To maintain a positive brand image, hotels should consider all these factors and work on areas that need improvement (Kasiri et al., 2017).

It has been established that hotels have to ensure customer satisfaction to maintain a positive brand image. They also have to ensure that all aspects of this are taken into account. This includes hygiene policies, customer feedback systems, hotel design, staff performance, and various other factors that determine customer service quality. However, the results of this

study have shown that most frequent travellers are not satisfied with any of these factors included in customer service (Koc, 2019). Many customers have complained that the level of hygiene is not up to the mark and that hotels should invest more in ensuring proper cleanliness of the hotel. Many people have also complained of the quality of the staff, which they attributed to a lack of adequate training. Some indicated that many hotels do not take customer feedback seriously and often ignore guests' needs (Ahmad et al., 2019). This shows that there is a gap in the quality-of-service provision in the majority of hotels. Many customers are also becoming savvier and may be offended by poor service quality, especially if a hotel has a good brand reputation. To avoid such issues, hotels should first look at their current feedback and identify key problems that arise. They should then devise strategies to address these problems to improve service quality and brand image (Florivic, 2020).

By reviewing the findings from this research, the future trends of the hospitality industry can be identified. The descriptive analysis and research have given a direction to the future trend of hospitality. The Pandemic era has taught the industry a great deal, and the Millennials have realised what is significant for them. They have demarcated the sustainability factor being the foremost criterion (Apornak, 2017). Now that Millennials have officially surpassed the baby boomers and are to reign for the next fifteen years, i.e. till 2035, post which Generation Z is will be employed 100%. The hospitality cannot ignore Millennials' needs and demands. They are tilted towards save the greens, go green. They are likely to support and adopt an environmentally friendly brand. Around 90% of the Millennials think that hospitality should be measured by its impact on Mother Nature (Saad Andaleeb and Conway, 2016).

This generation is not significant in trusting businesses so that eco-friendly brands will have a better opportunity than the rest. The hospitality industry should inculcate green service quality in their strategy to avoid waste and pollution in the water, air, and nature. Hospitality in their food and beverage should include organic food fresh from the farms. They should stop using Plastic and should closely monitor the usage of water. Hospitality is known to use the leading water resource in any state.

The hospitality of the United Kingdom needs to think internationally on the global level. The chains with a worldwide presence are more likely to be trusted and taken services of than the rest. However, it has also been seen in this research that today's generation is experimental; they love to experiment and try new things. So, whether it is an Air BNB setup or couch

surfing to the expensive fine dining and hotels, this generation has done it all by the time they turn 30. Hospitality needs to pick up from these cues, learn and implement them in their service quality to sustain the present and the future.

The Post Pandemic Era will be different from the Pre Pandemic era. The world will operate differently. The hospitality sector will have to pivot from in-house events to online events, live streaming, and musical evenings for guests and potential customers (Mishra et al., 2020). Tourism and hospitality have always gone hand in hand; with tourism being shut hospitality sector were given for a toss. Hospitality needs to find its bearing through collaboration and being a stand-alone winner even if people stop travelling. Attracting domestic, within-the-city guests and potential customers will be the significant trend further. As much as travellers from outside the city and country cannot be ignored, the focus should shift towards the 'within the reach' customers (Iwaarden *et al.*, 2003). The brands which will realise it and start taking the steps towards luring these domestic customers will win the race in the long run.

The hospitality brands will have to satiate the creative flow of the millennial through their service quality. The research was done in the past, and through this study, it has come to the knowledge that Millennials are not straight off the plate people. They like creative and punk elements. The brands which can live up to their expectation by being creatively intelligent and crisp with the fast process, which includes using the technology as much as they can on whatever process possible to make the Millennial life easy, will be ahead in the game.

Technology is the future of Hospitality, and the hotels of the United Kingdom should gear up to hug technology as much as hygiene and comfort (Taxler, 2018). The service quality will have to upgrade itself with technological advancements. Usage of Artificial Intelligence to ease the guest's life, Usage of Augmented reality for the guest's comfort. They can decide on the menu by looking at how it looks natural while sitting inside their hotel room. As soon as they check in to their room and connect to the hotel's Wi-Fi, the meetings and emails should be integrated with the environment of the room personalised for the guest so that the hotel service in the form of Artificial Intelligence can remind them of their essential commitments like meetings time, etc. Right before the checkout, Artificial Intelligence should ask the feedback on the services, and then it should be personalised for the respective guest in the future. Such integrations of their service quality with the technology will ensure better service (Kaplin et al., 2019).

Hotels may have to adapt to the smaller and more personalised environment regarding room service and the whole setup. Today's generation is highly individualistic regarding their needs and demands. Standard service does not cut it for them. For example: in the car service Uber and Ola adopted a music system method where a customer can take the exceptional service and play the music as per their demand. Now, whenever they take another cab, they will get their personalised playlist to play from; no matter how many their customer may have sat in the car after them, their playlist will be saved for them and whenever they check in the other cab of Ola or Uber with excellent service they can use play their music. This way, these two brands generated a loyal customer base. Hospitality will have to take cues to form such innovation and offer individualistic service to guests to make them feel special (Chaston, 1994). Now, whenever they check-in in the hotel in the future, anywhere in the world of the same chain, they should be offered their preferences and then more options just in case they want to try out. This will ensure loyalty and customers' love for the brand. These practical experiences on the individual level offered to this generation will go a long way. The better it gets, the better the chances of retaining the customer. Such personalised services will be the future of hospitality and will make or break a brand's image. Early adopters to this trend will sustain the future, and the rest may succumb to the ancient methods and be dusted in ruins.

5.2.7 Limitation of SERVQUAL

It is critical to remember that SERVQUAL is more viable than several instruments used in service quality analysis and that other approaches may be more effective at closing gaps. "According to Buttle (1996), the validity of SERVQUAL has been questioned on both theoretical and operational grounds. SERVQUAL, while having some benefit to a service manager, provides only a portion of the picture when it comes to all the different needs, expectations, and perceptions that exist in a service business context. Serving others often requires listening to and understanding their concerns. The task is complex because, as Gaster (Gaster, 1995) notes, "service provision is more complex than simply meeting expressed needs, as it involves identifying and understanding unexpressed needs, identifying priorities, allocating resources, and publicly justifying and accounting for what has been done." Citizens and communities and customers and service users rely on service organisations to be responsible and accountable. Although service quality improvement is essential, there is a

wide range of other organisation activities, including developing access to existing services, providing equitable and equal service provision, and providing efficient and effective services in even the most difficult circumstances. As a result, service quality measurement becomes more complex and challenging.

5.2.8 Advantage of SERVQUAL

Apart from the shortcomings discussed previously, a distinct advantage of SERVQUAL is that it is a tried and tested instrument that can be used for comparative benchmarking purposes (Bryslan and Curry, 2001). SERVQUAL benefits from statistical validity because of extensive field testing and refinement. As a result, it avoids the pitfall of being perceived by service users and providers as "something made up on the spot" or a questionnaire skewed to elicit types of response. SERVQUAL can also be administered repeatedly and used for comparative benchmarking purposes as a generic and universally applicable instrument. To fully appreciate the benefits of SERVQUAL, annual surveys should be conducted for the following reasons:

- to enable year-to-year comparisons
- to ascertain the impact of service improvements on customers' perceptions and expectations of the service over time
- to determine the effectiveness of service development and improvement initiatives across targeted components.

It is critical to remember that measuring systems are frequently ineffective because they lack sufficient knowledge about the object being measured. Measuring customer perceptions of service may raise expectations, and measuring too often may demotivate customers to provide accurate responses. Finally, there is no point in assessing service quality if no action is taken in response to the findings.

6. Chapter 6: Conclusion: Final Thoughts

6.1 Introduction

To summarise it all, the purpose of this research was to determine the critical determinants of the service quality strategy that can improve the hotel's brand image in the United Kingdom. Through the various empirical analysis, which included quantitative and qualitative data from the primary and secondary sources of research and literature through evidence, it was derived that for the brand image hotel to improve, the hotel needs to focus on filling the gap between the customer perception and customer expectation. The brand forms customer perception through various communication methods like advertisements, public relations, brochures, website communication, etc. Through the image the brand portrays, the way they position themselves through such communication creates a certain kind of perception and image in the customer's mind, which consequentially becomes the expectation. However, when the same expectation is not met in the real-life experience of the customer's stay in the hotel property, the brand image goes for a toss. Other things which the hotel needs to focus on, which act as a key determinant in improving the brand image of the hotels of the United Kingdom, are staff and customer interaction.

6.2 Conclusion

According to the finding of this research, it is concluded that dimensions of SERVQUAL crucially affect the quality of service; therefore, service quality significantly affects brand image. This may imply that high quality of service will lead to a higher brand image of the hotels. Thus, by improving service quality, brand image will generate and create more value for customers. Furthermore, this helps hotels to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors.

While this research contributes to the field of service quality by providing some new viewpoints, it is felt that further work needs to be done to corroborate the approaches that have been proven and increase the usage of SERVQUAL in the design and improvement of high-quality services.

Just as the SERVQUAL instrument is widely used to assess external service quality, it can also be modified to determine internal service quality provided by departments and divisions within a company to employees in other departments and divisions. The current study's findings demonstrate that organisations can assess at least five service quality dimensions to determine the level of services provided and identify which dimensions require improvement.

It is necessary to keep in contact with employees and assess their service experiences to improve service quality. Like the external customer, an internal customer will judge the quality of the internal service based on attributes like reliability and responsiveness (Mehta, Lalwani and Han, 2000). Since service organisations know different internal service quality dimensions, they can use this information to evaluate the organisation's performance or employees on each size, while managers can use the information to pinpoint where improvement is needed.

A qualitative analysis of the survey, administered to a pool of 300 respondents, reveals that the staff behavior influences the customer's perception and expectation. All of the interactions guest experiences as soon as they enter the hotel directly affect their perception of its brand image. These interactions can be the length of the wait in a queue and whether the hotel staff apologised for the inconvenience caused by a long wait. The interactions with hotel staff at the check-in counter, and simple conversations like greetings of "how are you?" and "hope you had no issues finding the hotel", etc. go a long way in influencing brand image. It is worth noting that until these first direct interactions, the brand image was based on the brand's communication with their customer through indirect advertisements. However, the staff interaction doesn't end at this first experience of the guest, and it extends to the overall staff promptness and responsiveness towards the customer issues, queries, orders, and communication.

If the customer orders room service, how quick is the staff's response and how smooth is the delivery of what is requested.? If the customer has some issues in the room, how quickly are these issues tackled, resolved, and taken care of? All these things fall under the umbrella of responsiveness and staff promptness. Apart from staff and guest interaction in terms of empathising and courteous conversation (Lewis and Mitchell, 1990), another factor that is important for the customer's perception and expectation in improving the brand image is the grooming of the staff in terms of appearance, cleanliness, sharp look, and approachable

persona. A willing and smiling staff earns more customers for the hotel brand than anything else. In addition to these intangible factors, tangible determinants such as the décor, infrastructure, music, colour pattern, interiors, and comfort of the room also stay actively influence the brand image. Another key determinant in service quality strategy found during the research through various quantitative and qualitative analyses was the hotel's hygiene, housekeeping, and cleanliness.

The moment the customer enters the hotel and reaches the lobby area before coming to the reception for check-in, the first thing the customer notices is the cleanliness, the hygiene of the standard room, cleanliness, and upkeep of the furniture and the floor. The following key element, which was noticed as a critical determinant of the service quality strategy for improving the brand image of the hotels in the United Kingdom, is the quality of the food and beverage. Guests are driven to be satisfied or unsatisfied customers based on the quality of food and drinks regardless of whether they are in the hotel for leisure or business.

Additionally, many customers are not very experimental with their drinks. If the hotel does not stock their preferred beverage or brand of choice, this creates dissatisfaction, resulting in a negative brand image. Then there is another set of guests who like to experiment while staying in hotels. They want some new drinks to try, and if the hotel has an excellent bartender to tend and makes delicious, fun drinks, brownie points are earned right there.

Another critical determinant in improving the brand image through the service quality strategy is location. The location decides on the accessibility, and it was found through the research study that the site of the hotel matters to the customers. They book the hotels depending on the accessibility of the location. However, if it is a leisure trip, they may go for the exotic location hotel property. However, guests still prefer that transportation be provided by the hotel, which saves them the hassle of finding transport. Customers like to save time and reach the hotel without stress, and therefore they frequently leave feedback on the accessibility of the location.

Apart from the location, another critical determinant of the service quality strategy that improves the hotel's brand image in the United Kingdom is the service cost. It is a general notion of a consumer that the higher the price of these, service the better their quality of service should be. Now, this perception or image becomes the reason for the high

expectation of the customer and when they get the natural feel of the service by staying in an expensive hotel. On the other hand, the less expensive the hotel, the lower the expectation of the service quality. The result is that customers tend to ignore minor errors. The research also suggests that little factors that seem like the hotel's prerogative are disproportionately important and major service quality strategy determinants. These factors include but are not limited to evening events, leisure activities, a gym, a swimming facility, a spa, and other such facilities. They make for the customer's experience and influence customer perception and expectations of the hotel's image.

Another minor yet crucial element that came forward as a critical determinant in service quality strategy is the Value-Added services provided by the hotels. Whether it's a surprise welcome party, a gift hampers for an extended stay, a complimentary spa session, or other things that constitute a Value-added service, they all uplift customer mood. This improves the quality of their stay experience with the hotel, enhancing brand image.

The research suggests another critical factor for improving the brand image in the form of technology adoption by the hotel. The more the hotel is prone to using such technologies and apps which can make the customers life easy in terms of waiting in queues or waiting for the luggage or the car in the valet, the better the experience of the customer and the better is the chance for them perceiving the hotel brand as progressive and up to date. Through this research, several of these critical elements were identified, which can significantly help improve the brand image of hotels in the UK.

The objective of this research was to determine the superiority of specific service quality strategies over others in improving brand image. Research findings revealed that factors like hygiene and housekeeping, quality of food and beverage, check-in experience, front office operations, and hotel staff appearance and interaction are the key determinants of a successful service quality strategy. The critical determinant, the first element in influencing the customer's perception and expectation, is the front office operation interaction. The quick and easy check-in and check-out with well-behaved empathetic staff who are fast enough to apologise for any delay or problems caused due to the process to the customer wins the race and enhances the customer experience. The second position is staff interaction with the guest. If the staff is smiling and courteous and talks with respect and approachability while being

well-groomed in their physical appearance leaves the customer thinking positively about them and the hotel image.

The third key determinant is housekeeping. The housekeeping department does not only include not only the hygiene, cleanliness the quality of furniture, attractive interiors, and décor of the hotel cost bet to squeaky clean bathrooms and the hotel rooms, appealing and warm colour theme, and piece of art which is welcoming, the temperature and the music. It has been seen that even if the whole hotel is clean and hygienic, the customer room bed sheet is not so neat or has a foul odour spoils the entire experience of the customer. Even if the room experience is good yet the temperature or the overall music played in the hotel is loud or not to the taste of the customer, it spoils their mood. It furthers their experience, which in turn hurts the brand image of the hotel.

The fourth determinants are food and beverage. In the modern times, while seeking an experience in a nice hotel the customer wants variety. They seek quality in food and drinks offered. If they have a particular taste for food or cuisine and prefer a particular brand for drinks, they may want that on the menu if the hotel does not have it, it brings upon the negative experience in the customer stay. In another scenario, if the customer is experimental and prefers experimenting with their food and drinks then they would rather want a good bartender in the hotel who can play with their drinks in terms of some sassy fun mixing and they would also want the hotel to offer a variety of cuisines from each continent and countries which helps the customer to pick and taste or experiment as per their wish a will. If such kinds of varieties are not available for the customer to experiment with, the customer is not satisfied, leading to negative service quality rating in their stay and consequentially ruining the brand image of the hotel. Therefore, the hotel needs to keep these four key determinants in mind and the same order for their service quality strategy for a positive, strong, and successful brand image of their hotel.

This study aimed to identify a metric to measure the degree of effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK. This research and study have successfully managed to identify the metric to measure the degree of the effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK. Through various dimension gap analyses and four-dimension theory, it was found out that SEVQUAL, for now, is the valuable metric tool to measure the degree of effectiveness of

different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in the UK. When the qualitative analysis of the secondary data was done during the research while the experts reviews, and peer research study was analyzed and considered it was found out that SERVQUAL which stands for service quality tool is immensely effective. The five components of SERVQUAL are Assurance, Tangibles, Responsiveness, Empathy, and Reliability(Barney, 2010). These five dimensions of SERVQUAL were further into Tangibles: Decor, infrastructure, interiors, visual appearance, temperature, music, fixtures, room, etc., Intangibles: Responsiveness, reliability, empathy, assurance. Many experts and researchers have suggested SERVQUAL be used to benchmark performance to improve the service quality and the brand image of the hotel(Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1985). When the tool SERVQUAL was tested through various hospitality structures it clearly showed that SERVQUAL as an assessment and evaluation tool consists of matching and managing customer expectations concerning the design of the service or product (Bryson and Curry, 2001). It was found in this research that the metric tool SERVQUAL serves the purpose.

According to the research of Luk and Layton (Luk and Layton, 2004) and Akbaba (Akbaba, 2006) the five-dimensional structure of service quality in the hotel industry was confirmed, but dimensions differed. This is supported by all these findings, which mean that the numbers of service quality characteristics depend on the type of service being provided, and separate measurements should be created for each service setting (Bailey and Ball, 2006).

The study's findings are relevant to hotel managers, according to the research. Clearly, the use of the SERVQUAL scale provides valuable information to hotel managers in the development of quality improvement strategies and the pursuit of a competitive advantage in the industry.

The cost-of-service quality survey is necessary to carry out the survey of service quality in the hotel industry (Luk and Layton, 2002). Hotel managers should concentrate on specific items (improvement areas) that relate to the tangibles dimension. This consists of various facilities, from equipment to physical locations, and how it appears to customers. Similarly, hotel managers should not forget that a guest's ability to empathize was one of the key service quality dimensions that contributed to overall hotel guest satisfaction.

When the quantitative application of SERVQUAL was done the result provided some extremely useful insight to the hotel managers concerning the customer's perception and expectations. SERVQUAL results also helped them in objective learning of gaps in the quality dimensions. The five gaps which the hoteliers came to know about through the metric tool SERVQUAL is: Gap between the customer perception and expectation, the gap between management perception of customers expectation, the gap between the service quality specifications and actual deliverables, the gap between service quality and the promising company makes to the customer through advertising and external communication, the gap in the customer's perception of few services and the expectation regarding the services(Keller and Lehmann, 2003).

Through this research, it was further derived that the usage of SERVQUAL provides insights into dimensions of service quality, which is immensely important from the customer's perspective. Also, because often the hoteliers and the hotel managers have no clue of the customer's perception and the expectation. As they operate through the notion of their own therefore, they do not have any idea of customers' perspectives, demands needs, and expectations. This is where this metric tool SERVQUAL, provides them, the hoteliers and the hotel managers, a clarity of scene by showing them the gaps and reporting them the quality of service provided to the customers with regards to the customer's expectations, need, and wishes of the customers or guests.

In the research, it was found out that many spa hotels have successfully used SERVQUAL. After using and SERVQUAL as their metric tool they have confirmed that it is crucial to realize the goal through service which aptly suits the customer's needs, wishes, expectation, and demands.

To reduce the gap between the services offered and the services expected, and customers expected perception of the services delivered each staff member should aim that each time they service the guest, they provide them with a positive experience. The hoteliers and the hotel management should keep a standardized service quality system that is well defined, and transparent always. The hotel brand to improve its brand image should ensure smoothness, precision, and promptness in the attributes of the quality dimensions and social dimensions. The quality dimensions include meeting the customer's requirements and serving the customer with zeal, quickness, and utmost respect and care, and controlled smooth

coordination across the services, whereas the social dimension includes promptly solving the customer's problems and queries positive and ever-smiling warm attitude and providing individual attention to the customers. The interactions between the staff and the guests are consequential to the positive brand image of the hotel. It is of prima facie; therefore, hotels of the United Kingdom need to be committed to the continuous improvement of the customer and staff interaction. To improve and strengthen the brand image, the hotel needs to take the cues from the customer's action, behavior, and better their services which are aligned to the customer's expectations and perception.

This research identified the best practices that the hospitality field could utilize in the UK to overcome the difficult situation that has been impeded after the Covid-19 situation. Although there are ongoing debates whether the qualitative research would be reliable and valid in the academic field, this research has demonstrated that the propositions of Bryman and Creswell were taken into consideration in filling this gap within the paper. The purpose is to provide a high-quality outcome based on evidence and valid data. This research has demonstrated the background and provided a clear overview of the organizational structure in the UK, in addition to the impact of external influences such as Brexit and Covid-19 on the hospitality field. We have also tackled the different theories of the importance of service quality demonstrating the different models and frameworks about service quality such as SERVQUAL, critical incident, Grönroos, dimensional and SERVPERV model highlighting the differences between each one and provide clear guidance about the situation that each one would be the best practice to ensure reaching the goals. Through the paper we have discussed the measuring degrees of the strategies, and how the entity could benefit from each model and framework separately.

6.3 Contribution

This study was successful in deriving through the research theories qualitative and quantitative analysis of data and empirical evidence the objective, aim, and purpose of the research. For now, the metric tool best to be used is SERVQUAL while keeping the key detriments in mind hotels can reach their objective and goal of attracting new customers while keeping things loyal, retaining them by strengthening and improving their brand image.

The academic contribution that this research can make is related to the issues that hospitality industry has faced since the covid-19 pandemic began. Hospitality industry has suffered a lot in this time, as there were many travel restrictions. By studying the service quality issues pertaining to the hospitality industry already affected by covid-19 and political issues like Brexit, this research can contribute towards shaping the future policies of hospitality industry in the UK.

Also, the researcher has provided primary quantitative data that can be used as a steppingstone for further research. By providing primary data about service quality issues that the hospitality industry faces in the wake of covid-19 pandemic, the researcher has provided a theoretical basis for more research in the area. Hospitality industry is a very important industry in the UK economy. It has faced major setbacks, and this research contributes towards future policy making by providing in depth information regarding the service quality approach that the hospitality industry in the UK should take now. This is also an academic contribution by this research as this research has provided further lines of thought for detailed study.

In addition, although there is positive impact between brand image on hotel performance in limited studies, there is still a slight disagreement between different researchers regarding the dimensions of brand image as well as the measurement of the performance. Further studies will be discussed later a more comprehensive index for branding and corporate performance in the hospitality industry.

This research assists in closing the gaps between the studies from literature and the current modern world. Through the discussion, this research was able to determine the best practices for the hotels to ensure the service quality in addition to enhancing the customer experience. The SERVQUAL model has proven to be very efficient in fulfilling the objectives and goals especially during this tough period with the precautionary measures of the pandemic. The research also helps in providing primary data for future researchers that could help them as a starting point. This research also discusses in detail the different approaches and the different aspects and models that could benefit the new scholars in the future to complete the path of knowledge and find the most suitable framework that levitates the industry.

6.4 Limitations

Just like any other research, this research is not without its limitations. The biggest limitation of this research was the problems or hurdles faced in data collection due to the covid-19 social distancing requirements. Due to these requirements, the researcher had to rely solely on the online data collection method. Also, due to the covid-19 restrictions, it was not possible for the researcher to meet the participants. The desk research was also carried out mostly from home. The research is limited in the sense that there is a small sample of the population that has been studied in this case. Another limitation of this research is that it is a cross-sectional study. A similar study should be conducted in future too, to compare the findings of one with the other. That would provide the comparative basis for the findings of this research. This study is limited in the sense that the participants are from a limited geographic region. The approach of these participants might be too similar. This has affected the generalizability of this research.

6.5 Future Research

The future research in this area should be comparative study of the service quality issues and metrics being utilized in the UK and in other parts of the world where tourism and hospitality are among the top three industries making noticeable contribution to the country's GDP. As this research is a cross-sectional study, one good approach would be to replicate this research at another time, to compare the findings from this research. Also, there is a requirement of more conclusive evidence about the topic under discussion here. It is thus suggested that more research should be conducted on niche areas. More in-depth research on various variables should be conducted.

Chapter 7: Critical Reflection

As per Gibbs Reflective cycle (1988), true learning takes place not only by going through an experience, but by reflecting on the same after the experience. Gibbs' reflective cycle takes this reflection through different stages (Husebo et al., 2015). The cycle is presented in the appendix too. Description is the part where the experience is described. In this case, a primary research was carried out. This research was a detailed project that needed a lot of focus. Thorough literature review was carried out to identify gaps in the literature. On the basis the same, research gaps were identified. For quantitative data collection, online questionnaire was created and distributed. It was a tough task as data collection was carried out during the lockdown due to Covid-19. As per Gibbs' reflective cycle, the second important element to consider is the feelings. My feelings at the time of this research were a mix. I started off very excited, however, soon there was a roadblock due to Covid-19. The normal ways of conducting desk research were altered to meet the covid-19 social distancing requirement. That is where fear or anxiety took over the excitement. Data collection and literature review became a challenge due to limited access to libraries. All research was shifted online. However, this challenge brought out the best in my work, as I showed resilience and remained focus on my work. Evaluating the whole research project, I would say that my commitment to the project and the guidelines provided to me by my supervisor were the best parts. The disruptions and uncertainty added to the whole process by covid-19 restrictions were the bad part. Analyzing the situation, I would have to say that due to my social support system and my commitment to the project, I have been able to complete this research. There were many hurdles and roadblocks in the process, but eventually it turned out to be a great effort. I would conclude this reflection by saying that if I had to do it all over again, I would prefer to do it in a more systematic manner. Uncertainties and risks cannot be taken out of any project. Same is the case with any research project. Considering this issue, I would organize my work better to avoid all possible roadblocks in the future.

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9. Appendix

9.1 Appendix A

Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

The key determinants of a service quality strategy that improves brand image of hotels in UK.

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the Project's Purpose?

This research project aims to investigate how the key determinants of a service quality strategy that improves brand image of hotels in UK.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen _____, or person in a similar role, you will have knowledge about research data services in your hotel.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the online consent form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to complete a web-based questionnaire which we estimate will take you 15 minutes. You may also wish to agree to a follow-up interview to find out more about your approach.

7. What do I have to do?

Please answer the questions in the questionnaire. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

8. What are the possible disadvantages/risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life.

9. What are the benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on service quality. Results will be shared with participants in order to inform their professional work.

10. What if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way we will tell you and explain why.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you have any complaints about the project in the first instance you can contact any member of the research team.

12. Will my taking part be kept confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Your institution will also not be identified or identifiable. Any data collected about you in the online questionnaire will be stored online in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies.

13. Will I be recorded?

You will not be recorded in any way other than your input to the questionnaire without separate permission being gained from you.

14. What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

The questionnaire will ask you about your opinions and current practices in relation to service quality. Your views and experience are just what the project is interested in exploring.

15. What will happen to the results of the research project?

Results of the research will be published. You will not be identified in any report or publication. Your institution will not be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

16. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved by the Information School's ethics review procedure and subsequently endorsed by the ethics procedures of.

17. Contacts for further Information

Name: Mudassar Arshad

Contact: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this research.

9.2 Appendix B

Consent form

The key determinants of a service quality strategy that improves brand image of hotels in UK

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw any time prior to submission of the thesis.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves...[outline briefly in simple terms what participation in your research will involve].
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in...[list all forum in which you plan to use the data from the interview: dissertation, conference presentation, published papers, etc.].
- I understand that if I inform the researcher that I or someone else is at risk of harm they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with me first but may be required to report with or without my permission.
- I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in [specify location, security arrangements and who has access to data] until [specific relevant period – for students this will be until the exam board confirms the results of their dissertation].
- I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for [specific relevant period – for students this will be two years from the date of the exam board].
- I understand that under freedom of information legalization I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.

- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of research participant

Signature of Participant

Date

Signature of Researcher

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature of Researcher

Date

9.3 Appendix C

Questionnaires

The key determinants of service quality strategies that improves brand image of hotels in UK.

The aim of this research is to find the key determinants of service quality strategies that improves brand image of hotel sin the United Kingdom. After the determinants are derived, this study will determine the superiority of certain service quality strategies over others in improving brand image which will further help in to identify a metric to measure degree of effectiveness of different service quality strategies in improving brand images of hotels in UK.

Your participation in filling out this questionnaire will be a great help in completing this research at the standards required by hospitality industry. All your personal information is to be kept confidential and the data in terms of your answers will be shared anonymously. The ethics policies and practices followed by Hospitality research industry will be followed in completing this research. You have the right to withdraw your information/data from this research.

Demographics:

1. Which age group do you belong to? (22-35 years; 36-45 years; 46-59 years; 60+ years).
2. Please share your work experience if you are working
3. How often do you travel within the country for work, leisure or business?
4. How often do you travel outside the country for work, leisure, or business what type of accommodation do you prefer?
5. When travelling within the country what hotel do you stay :
 - 1 star, 2 star, 3 star, 4 star, 5 star, 7 star
 - Guest house, motel

- Spa hotel or Golf Hotel
 - Air Bnb
 - Others
6. When travelling outside the country for work, leisure, or business what type of accommodation do you prefer?
- 1 star, 2 star, 3 star, 4 star, 5 star, 7 star
 - Guest house, motel
 - Spa hotel or Golf Hotel
 - Air Bnb
 - Others

Section I

7. What are service quality and the key elements of successful service quality strategies?
8. What is brand image and how it is measured?
9. Evaluate the issues hotel industry is facing in terms of service quality and analyze the hotels current service qualities strategies are?
10. What measure hospitality industry (hotels) can take to implement service quality strategy that demonstrably improves brand image?

Section II

11. Do you choose your hotel basis the rating on Google?
 - a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
12. Do you consider and decide the hotel after checking on the location of the Hotel?
 - a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
13. Do you research and read about the service quality of the hotel?
 - a) Strongly agree

- b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
14. Do you research or read feedback about the quality of food and beverage and menu of the hotel before booking and after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
15. Do you research or read feedback about the staff of the hotel before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
16. Do you research or read feedback about the hygiene of the hotel before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
17. Do you research or read feedback about the interiors of the hotel before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
18. Do you research or read feedback about the infrastructure of the hotel before booking and/or after the stay?

- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
19. Do you research or read feedback about the promptness of the hotel staff before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
20. Do you research or read feedback on the grooming, cleanliness and appearance of the hotel staff before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
21. Do you research or read feedback on the delivery time of the order made from your hotel room before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
22. Do you research or read feedback on the courtesy, and behavior of the hotel staff before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree

23. Do you research or read feedback on the color theme, music and temperature of the hotel common area and your hotel room before booking and/or after the stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
24. Is brand name important for you while picking the hotel for your stay?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
25. Does quality of service offered by the hotel brand makes for its image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
26. Does the hotel staff behavior make for the hotel brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
27. Does the interiors and the décor of the hotel makes for the brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
28. Does the infrastructure make for the brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree

- c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
29. Does the new technology advancements opted by the hotels for various purposes makes for the hotel brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
30. Does hotel location and accessibility make for the hotel brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
31. Does the variety and quality in the food-beverage, and drinks makes for the brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
32. Do the events and various other evening surprises; workout facility, swimming and leisure experience makes for the brand image?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
33. Do you think hotel market as an industry is going through tough times?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure

- d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
34. Do you think hotel industry has been hit by the Pandemic?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
35. Do you think hotel industry is affected by the rules and policies made by the government?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
36. Do you think hotel industry focus on the guest needs and demands?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
37. Do you think Hotel industry lives up to its image portrayed in their advertisements and brochures?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
38. Do you think hotel industry match the guest perception and expectation?
- a) Strongly agree b)
 - b) Agree c)
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree

39. Do you think hotel industry needs to better its servicing in terms of the guests needs and demands?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
40. Do you think hotel industry lacks a metrics or tool to measure its service quality?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
41. Do you think hotel industry pays attention in training their staff in empathy, promptness, and customer interaction?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
42. Do you think hotel industry spend time, money and effort in grooming their staff?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
43. Do you think hotel industry spend time, money, and effort in housekeeping, hygiene?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
44. Do you think hotel industry should work keeping the customer perception and expectation in mind?

- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
45. Do you think hotel industry should ensure the accessibility of their property?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
46. Do you think the experience of the guest is much better during check in than check out?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
47. Do you think hotel industry should work on the experience of the guest while checking out?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
48. Do you think hotels should focus on the value-added services?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Not sure
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree
49. Do you think hotel should work on their cost factor?
- a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree

- c) Not sure
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

50. Do you think hotel should have 24x7 check in and check out and the cost of the room starts when the person checks in and checks out rather a set time?

- a) Strongly agree
- b) Agree
- c) Not sure
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

10 List of figures

Gibbs Reflective Cycle (1988)

